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SYMBOLS

- // encloses morphological forms.
- [] encloses phonological forms.
- <> encloses graphological forms.
- + morphological (morpheme) boundary.
- \$ phonological (syllable) boundary.
- # graphological (word) boundary.
- '' encloses glosses.
- * marks a wrongly generated form.
- () encloses symbols, if more than one is allowed.
- ə is used to mark schwa, since I do not have the symbol on my word processor.
- j marks a nonsyllabic high front vowel.
- w marks a nonsyllabic high back vowel.
- ^ marks a nonsyllabic non-high vowel.
- C_s a consonant with a syllable boundary as a subscript denotes a consonant on which the syllable boundary falls.
- bold** highlights segments being discussed.
- oral oral differentiates phonemes pronounced in the oral cavity from laryngeals (in this paper only /h/).
- son sonorancy differentiates sonorants (vowels, liquids and nasals) from obstruents (stops and fricatives).
- cont continuancy differentiates liquids and fricatives from stops and nasals.
- fort fortition differentiates two obstruents of like continuancy and place.
- lab labial identifies phonemes pronounced with the lips.
- dent dental identifies phonemes pronounced with the tip of the tongue.

unk unknown is an additional feature used to distinguish dental fricatives in more than just fortition.

vel velar identifies phonemes pronounced with the velum.

INTRODUCTION

In his 1972 book, Penzl stresses that historical phonology must be based on the texts:

"Historische Sprachwissenschaft muß textbezogen sein" (Penzl 1972:8).

"Das Lautsystem ist an den Text gebunden" (Penzl:1972:17).

"Die Lautbestimmung muß selbstverständlich von den Schreibungen der Handschriften selbst ausgehen" (Penzl 1972:17).

Synchronic analyses of these texts need to be done, in order to posit diachronic changes between them:

"Die historische Sprachwissenschaft ist aber nicht nur entwicklungsbeschreibend (diachronisch), sondern auch systembeschreibend" (Penzl 1972:14).

"die [Beschreibung] des Wandels von Sprachstufe zu Sprachstufe, die sich durch diachronischen Vergleich synchronisch erforschter Perioden ergibt" (Penzl 1972:14).

A by-product of such analyses would be a text's graphology--those spelling mergers conditioned by orthography, not phonology:

"Alle direkten und indirekten Schreibungsvarianten gehören zum Schreibungssystem, ebenso jeder nur graphisch deutbare Schreibungswechsel wie z.B. Isidors *gh* und *g*; *k* neben *c* und Zusammenfall wie Überschneidung der Zeichen" (Penzl 1972:34).

Before attempting such an analysis however, Penzl felt he should first lay out his methods:

"Die Methoden der Lautbestimmung aus den Graphien werde ich unten genauer beschreiben" (Penzl 1972:19).

After developing these methods (Penzl 1972:17-36), he applied them to texts--several larger manuscripts in Old High German.

"Ich beabsichtige in dieser Studie die Methoden der historischen Lautlehre auf das sprachliche Material der ahd.

Periode anzuwenden." (Penzl 1972:16).

"Ich habe daher die wichtigsten ahd. Großtexte gewählt, um die Methoden unter verhältnismäßig günstigen Umständen vorzuführen" (Penzl 1972:17).

Following Penzl then, this paper breaks into two sections; functions, and walkthrough. The first section develops functions, a term I prefer to methods because of its roots in programming. The second section, or walkthrough, applies them to some of the larger manuscripts in Old High German; those of Notker.

Functions

Presentation

Each function is titled, so it can be referenced in the walkthrough. Then comes the function definition, followed by discussion. No scholar works in a vacuum, and so the discussions will cite several authors, but will probably miss most. Perhaps this is unavoidable, given the evolving nature of our discipline. Lass is only partly joking when he writes that phonology:

"involves a lot of old wine in new bottles (as well as new wine in old bottles, new wine in new bottles, and some old wine left in the old bottles)" (Lass 1984:8).

Scope

The functions limit themselves to those needed to reconstruct some of the phonology and graphology of Notker's consonants.

This does not make them complete enough yet to output the entire system of any one text, nor any of the system for some texts. Some topics beyond the scope of these functions would be: vowels, texts by non-natives, and texts not written in alphabets.

Vowels

Ideally, one would address all the phonemes. However, processes for vowels depend heavily on supra-segmentals (stress and syllabification). So, for example, Notker's texts may contrast eight vowels, but only four in open, unstressed syllables. Fortunately, other than positing syllable divisions, consonants might be addressed without reference to supra-segmentals. Of course I need to decide on the vowels in order to cite any words. Their values were not arrived at through functions though, and

might best be ignored.

Texts by Non-Natives

Notker is assumed to have been a native speaker of the language he wrote in. Not all scribes were. So, for example, some Old High German glosses are presumed written by French speakers.

Not all the functions proposed here are meant to apply to non-native scribes. For instance, it will be argued that scribes only mark rules when they merge phonemes. This should perhaps not be true for a text transcribed by a foreigner--someone who may have marked allophones that were separate phonemes in his native language, but not necessarily in the one he was writing down.

Texts not Written in Alphabets

That the functions won't work on hieroglyphics will of course be obvious, but it brings up an important point. Eventually, one would want to automate historical phonology. The same body of functions used on Notker's Boethius could be verified against the syllabary of 19th century Cherokee newspapers. A program proposed for Mayan pictographs could be checked out with the the Nibelungenlied as input. Perhaps few of the individual functions used in each case could be shared. Such a goal however, would force an accountability on our discipline. Whatever functions a scholar uses on one text, he should also be prepared to run against any other text.

Walkthrough

Presentation

Before writing code, a programmer will often do a "deskcheck" or "walkthrough" of his functions. He takes different input, and with pencil and paper "walks through" his functions to see what they would output. The results of each input in this walkthrough are summarized in the form:

```

Input
Functions
Output

```

So, for example, one walkthrough for a billing application might be:

Input

Date of Billing: 4/1/1995
 Date of Order: 1/1/1995
 Amount Owed on Order: \$100.00
 Credit Rating of Customer: Good

Functions

If an order is overdue three months, add a 5% penalty to the amount owed.

If a customer is delinquent on over \$100, change the customer's credit rating to bad.

Output

Amount Owed on Order: \$105.00
 Credit Rating of Customer: Bad

One might follow a similar format for critiquing phonology. Take, for example, Penzl's 1972 analysis of Notker's word initial <ch> (ex: <chòpf> 'head').

Input

Penzl is able to contrast several velar obstruents word initially, but not /kχ/ and /χ/:

"Im Anlaut sind *ch* und *h* in Opposition: *chòrn* >Korn< und *hòrn* >Horn<...*g* und *k* (*c*) stehen in Opposition mit *ch*: *chùninga*(84), *chèiser*(124); *chòmene*(86) und *gòmenes*, *còmenes*(690,6) >Mann< (Gen. Sing.)" (Penzl 1972:97).

In Modern Swiss, Notker's <#ch> in <chòpf> corresponds to [χ] in [χopf]:

"*ch* des Anlauts (*chùninga*, *chèiser*) die Spirans /χ/, wie...die Werte des gegenwärtigen Stadtdialektes von St. Gallen zu zeigen scheinen" (Penzl 1972:103).

Word internally, the same <ch> graph could be contrasted with <cch>, to give word internal <ch> a value of [χ]:

"Wir finden unter den Gaumenlautzeichen solche für Reibelaute wie *h ch cch* und für Verschußlaute wie *g k*, manchmal *c*, und *q* vor *u*: *kehîez*(3), *nechâme*(15), *richo*(30), *dïccho* >oft<, *begòndi*(23), *ke-*(3). *h ch cch* stehen im intervokalischen Inlaut in Opposition" (Penzl 1972:97).

"die Spirans /χ/, wie die Inlautsschreibung (*richo*)" (Penzl 1972:103).

Functions

Posit a phoneme in an environment if you can contrast it in near minimal pairs:

"die Feststellung von Schreibungsoppositionen, die uns zeigen können, welche Schriftzeichen oder Zeichenfolgen systematisch Oppositionen ausdrücken" (Penzl 1972:31).

If unable to posit a phoneme through minimal pairs, use the modern dialects to propose a probable phoneme:

"Der Vergleich mit vorhergehenden, zeitlich früheren Werten und mit folgenden, zeitlich späteren Werten ermöglicht oft durch das Erkennen von Lautwandlungen auch Schlüsse auf die Lautwerte in der untersuchten Zeitstufe." (Penzl 1972:21).

"Unter den späteren Werten sind die Lautwerte in Mundarten und der Gemeinsprache der Gegenwart besonders wichtig" (Penzl 1972:21).

If unable to posit a phoneme through minimal pairs, use similar graphs in other positions to propose a probable phoneme:

"Ist auch aus anderen Formen eine Schreibungsopposition deutlich, so können die Wechselformen ihrerseits als nahezu minimale Oppositionspaare angesetzt werden" (Penzl 1972:9).

Output

<#ch> probably marked [χ]:

"Ich sehe im *ch* des Anlauts (*chùninga*, *chèiser*) die Spirans /χ/" (Penzl 1972:103).

In 1968 Penzl used the same functions, but with slightly different input. Modern dialects still of course pointed to /χ/. However word initial <ch> was not compared to word internal <ch>

this time, but word final <ch> after nasals. Here Penzl had posited [k], from underlying /kχ/. Quite naturally, he got different output:

Input

Able to contrast several velar obstruents word initially, but not /kχ/ and /χ/:

"ch im Anlaut in *chùning* 'König'" (Penzl 1968a:146).

"h im Anlaut...*hòh* 'hoch'" (Penzl 1968a:145).

"velare Verschlußlaute...Beispiele für den Anlaut...*gelîh* und *kelîh* 'gleich'" (Penzl 1968a:146).

In Modern Swiss, Notker's <#ch> in <chòpf> corresponds to [χ] in [χopf]:

"Auf Grund der modernen Dialektverhältnisse wäre die Spirans [χ] im Anlaut durchaus möglich." (Penzl 1968a:146).

The same <ch> graph word finally is taken for /kχ/, so that it can be realized as [k] after nasals:

"Nach Konsonant könnte *ch* das Zeichen der einfachen Affrikate sein, die im Auslaut bei Nasal als Verschlußlaut (*dàng*), bei Liquida als Spirans (*uuèrh*, *scàlh*) vertreten ist." (Penzl 1968a:146).

Functions

Posit a phoneme in an environment if you can contrast it in near minimal pairs:

eine orthographische Bezeichnung auch nur beim Umlaut von *a* und *u*, sporadisch bei dem von *ûo* und anderen Phonemen belegt ist. Das muß aber als Beweis für die volle Reihe von Umlautsvokalen genügen." (Penzl 1968a:141).

If unable to posit a phoneme through minimal pairs, use the modern dialects to propose a probable phoneme:

"Die Lautwerte der Dialekte der Gegenwart, die der unmittelbaren Beobachtung zugänglich sind, gehören auch zum Beweismaterial." (Penzl 1968a:134).

If unable to establish a phoneme through minimal pairs, use similar graphs in other positions to propose a probable phoneme:

Die Orthographie der Schriften Notkers ergibt mit all den einschlägigen Fragen von Zeichenwahl, Zeichenvariation und Zeichenwechsel das Hauptmaterial für unsere Phonembestimmung." (Penzl 1968a:133).

Output

<#ch> could mark [χ], [kχ] or maybe even [k^h]:

"ch im Anlaut in *chuning* 'König', *chràft* 'Kraft', *chòmen* 'kommen', *chlèine* 'klein' auch als Affrikate [kχ] bestimmt werden könnte. Auf Grund der modernen Dialektverhältnisse wäre die Spirans [χ] im Anlaut durchaus möglich. Der erwähnte paradigmatische Wechsel mit *g* spricht aber dafür, daß *ch* auch das Zeichen für die Affrikate sein kann. R. Pestalozzi nahm für *ch* im Anlaut den Wert eines stark aspirierten Verschußlautes an." (Penzl 1968a:146).

Such a format for criticism hinges on how well one scholar extracts the arguments of another, and I am unsure whether I have done justice to Penzl. It is maybe too easy to misrepresent the logic of someone else, especially when disagreeing with him. In this paper, I only use the format for my own arguments.

Phonemes will be handled first, followed by phoneme mergers, and then grapheme mergers. Each issue will get handled as if in a walkthrough. Functions take input (usually a spelling merger) and produce output (usually either a phoneme merger or grapheme merger). In addition, each issue has literature on it, and the differences between scholars are cited in the commentary.

Scope

Input

Input of the walkthrough would be limited to all texts attributed to Notker. For the purposes of this paper, that would be anything listed in the Notker Wortschatz (Sehrt 1955). Individual words can get referenced as indexed in the Wortschatz. This index is to volume, page and line in Piper's edition of Notker's works (Piper 1895). So to know which manuscript a form comes from, one needs to cross reference it in the table below:

<u>Reference</u>	<u>Work</u>
I,5-363	De Consolatione Philosophiae

I,367-495	De Categoriis
I,499-588	De Interpretatione
I,591-595	De Partibus Logicae
I,596-622	De Syllogismus
I,623-684	De Arte Rhetorica
I,687-647	De Nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii
I,651-661	De Musica
II,3-644	The Psalms, Cantica and Katechetische Denkmäler

So, for example, I contrast dental stops syllable finally after vowels:

	/d/	/t/
Syllable	/toʌd/	/tuʌt/
Final	[toʌd]	[tuʌt]
After	<tôd>	<tûot>
Vowel	'death, nom sg'	'do, 3rd pres sg'
	I,8,8	I,9,26

<tôd> is in the first of Piper's two volumes, on page 8, line 8. <tûot> is also in the first volume, on page 9, line 29. This puts both words in De Consolatione Philosophiae.

Unfortunately the Wortschatz does not give strings of words. To be consistent, it would be best to reference these against Piper's edition too. Since I did not have access to it however, I have referenced strings of words against King's edition of De Nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii (King 1986). These will always have 'Nps' in the reference. So, for example, I cite examples for Penzl's argument on word initial /v/ and /pf/:

	/v/	/pf/
Word	/žo+vilo/	/iro+pfleg+ə(ž,s)(t,d)/
Initial	[žo\$vil,ø]	[iro+pfleg,ə(š,s)t]
After	<so uilo>	<iro flègest>
Vowel	'so much'	'care for her, 2nd sg pres subj'
	Nps 151,17	Nps 134,13

Both the above strings are found in King's De Nuptiis. The page

and line though are as in the manuscript, following King's convention. So King refernces <so uilo> on manuscript page 151, line 17. He has <iro flègest> on manuscript page 134, line 13.

Functions

Functions would be limited to those outlined in the first half of the paper.

Output

Output would be limited to some of the phonology and graphology of the consonants.

FUNCTIONS

Posit as Little as Possible

Definition

Posit as little phonology and graphology as possible--only enough to account for the text.

Discussion

Perhaps no function would fly in the face of as many scholars as this.

So, for example, Clausing explores the Anlautgesetz and a lenition of [t] to [d] after [n]. In both processes he sees that:

"Notker's German must have lacked precise syllable and word boundaries, so that the language was more flowing, and less choppy than Modern German is today. This, in turn, leads me to the conclusion that the glottal stop was not present in Notker's time, since the use of a glottal stop would institute a pause which would make sound assimilations arising out of close juncture impossible" (Clausing 1979:364).

Even if you accept that a glottal stop blocks assimilations, the above quote raises two questions. The first is purely technical. A glottal stop in Notker, if like the one in Modern English ['unʂdər] and German ['unʂtər], would have only appeared before syllable initial vowels. Neither the lenition of [t] to [d] nor the Anlautgesetz deal with syllable initial vowels.

A second, more fundamental issue is the motivation for the analysis itself. Glottal stops are not needed to account for Notker's texts. Why discuss them then?

Already in 1968 Penzl had tried to answer this question. In the section on methods, he outlines the task of historical phonology:

"Die historische Lautlehre darf sich nie damit begnügen, nur das Phoneminventar zu erforschen. Die Erkenntnis der Allophone ist wichtig, ebenso eine Bestimmung der Lautwerte, denn die phonetischen Tatsachen ermöglichen erst die genauere Analyse des Systems" (Penzl 1968a:133).

So, for example, Notker's stops get distinguished by fortition.

Penzl needs this to account for the near minimal pair:

	/d/	/t/
	Lenis	Fortis
Syllable	/toʌd/	/tuʌt/
Final	[toʌd]	[tuʌt]
After	<tôd>	<tûot>
Vowel	'death, nom sg'	'do, 3rd pres sg'
	I, 8, 8	I, 9, 26

In addition however, Penzl also decides on values for the secondary, and as far as the text is concerned unnecessary, features of voice and aspiration.

"Wir müssen *b d g* als stimmlose Lenisverschlußlaute bestimmen, *t* in *tâg* als stimmlosen, aspirierten Fortisverschlußlaut, ebenso *p* und *k* in den Stellungen in denen sie vorkommen" (Penzl 1968a:147).

The near minimal pair would then be:

	/d/	/t/
	Lenis	Fortis
	*Voiceless	*Voiceless
	*Unaspirated	*Aspirated
Syllable	/toʌd/	/tuʌt/
Final	[toʌd]	[tuʌt]
After	<tôd>	<tûot>
Vowel	'death, nom sg'	'do, 3rd pres sg'
	I, 8, 8	I, 9, 26

This approach to text reconstruction is not limited to the structuralist school. So Lass, in a generative approach to Old English phonology, admits that:

"as far as we can tell, historical investigation does not permit us to recover much more than grossly binary (i.e. classificatory) specifications" (Lass 1973:203).

Nevertheless:

"this does not mean of course that we can permit ourselves the luxury of a purely 'algebraic' approach to historical phonology, where only 'oppositions' and not their content count. We must attempt, as we have all along here, to achieve reasonably full specification at the phonological

and systematic phonetic levels" (Lass 1973:203).

In their epilogue, each consonant in Old English gets described with respect to thirteen features, two of which, [hi] and [lo], are not needed to distinguish any consonant (Lass 1973:225).

Only Use Text Input

Definition

Only allow the text as input.

Discussion

According to Penzl, some types of admissible input would be:

Earlier Texts:

"Der Vergleich mit früheren St. Galler Denkmälern" (Penzl 1968a:135).

Contemporary Texts:

"diagraphische Vergleiche mit alemannischen, oberdeutschen und anderen althochdeutschen Texten" (Penzl 1968a:135).

Modern Dialects:

"Die Lautwerte der Dialekte der Gegenwart" (Penzl 1968a:135).

Source Writing System:

"Die zeitgenössischen Alphabets...durch eine Reihe von mehr oder weniger genauen Beschreibungen lateinischer und griechischer Grammatiker vermittelt" (Penzl 1972:20).

All four of these types of input get used in his 1968 analysis of Germanic */h/ in Notker:

Earlier Texts:

"Man könnte aber auf parallele Schreibungen mit intervokalischem *h* wie z. B. das merkwürdige *emezzihic*, *stehic* (2mal) im St. Galler Paternoster hinweisen" (Penzl 1968a:139).

Contemporary Texts:

"Oberdeutsch heißt es *siuh* vor ahd. *h*, aber *ziohan* vor germ. *h*; das weist eher auf velare Artikulation von ahd. *h*" (Penzl

1968a:140).

Modern Dialects:

"Die modernen Dialekte der St. Gallener Gegend scheinen die Diphthongierung von *î* zu *îe*, *û* zu *ûo* vor Velarspirant zu bestätigen" (Penzl 1968a:140).

Source Writing System:

"Notker benützt folgende Zeichen, bei denen die lateinisch-romanischer Tradition spirantische Aussprache vermuten läßt" (Penzl 1968a:143).

Germanic */h/ in Notker is not taken for a laryngeal, but rather a velar fricative (Penzl 1968a:150), with:

"eine stärker velare Aussprache als für die ahd. Fortis *h(h)*" (Penzl 1968a:139).

If our discipline is to develop rigor however, it needs to separately establish the phonology of Notker's texts, the St. Gall Paternoster, and Modern Swiss. Then combine these to build Old Alemannic. Later combine the reconstructed languages from the literary period (Old Alemannic, Old Bavarian, Old Saxon, Old Norse) to build a reconstructed language from the preliterate period (Proto-Germanic).

Of course no text can be analyzed without any reference to diachronics. When discussing <h#> in Notker's <rûoh> and <bûh>, scholars have looked at fricatives and laryngeals. No one bothers to prove <h#> is not a nasal. This is partly because of the spelling, and partly because of their Modern German glosses, 'roh' and 'Bauch'. Penzl does not contrast every phoneme pair:

"Besonderen Wert legen wir auf Oppositionspaare, in denen Opposition zwischen graphisch und auch lautlich nahestehenden Zeichen, wo Variation oder Aufhebung möglich wäre, ersichtlich ist" (Penzl 1972:31).

Such diachronic evidence gets couched into the assumptions that go into the input. Much like a billing program assumes that the customer for an order is not dead. The trick, however, is to make sure these assumptions are obvious. A computer may not allow you to arrive at one address for a customer. Different addresses may have been entered for him in the customer, order, and contacts files. A thorough billing program should allow for

that, and send out bills to each address. Likewise, perhaps Notker's texts do not allow us to assign one value (fricative or laryngeal) to his Germanic */h/. A thorough analysis should allow for that, and not resort to diachronic evidence to posit more than is necessary to account for the text.

Distinguish Phonological from Graphological Boundary

Definition

The base phonological boundary is a syllable, the base graphological boundary is the word.

These base boundaries may of course be intensified. So, a syllable boundary that doubles as a word boundary may be a "stronger" phonological boundary. A word boundary that doubles as a sentence boundary may be a "stronger" graphological boundary. Nevertheless, differentiating phonological and graphological boundaries will help differentiating the two types of processes--something not always done.

Morpheme boundaries may affect phonological or graphological processes. To allow for this, integrate morpheme boundaries into whatever rule places syllable or word boundaries.

Discussion

Syllable and Word Boundaries

Some phonological processes in Notker apply across syllable boundaries. Dental stops lenite after [n], even across a syllable boundary.

Dental Lenition:

/(d,t)/ Separated
by Syllable Boundary
from Nasal

/vi(m,n)(d,t)+ət/
[fin\$dət]
<findet>
'find, 3rd sg pres'
I, 65, 18

In Modern German, obstruents are made fortis not only syllable finally, but also of course when that syllable boundary doubles as a word boundary:

Syllable Final Fortition:

/d/ Followed by
Syllable Boundary

/d/ Followed by
Syllable and Word
Boundary

/end+liχ/
[ent\$liχ]
<endlich>

/hund/
[hunt\$#]
<Hund>

Benware argues that, for phonological processes, the word boundary is:

"always interchangeable with the syllable boundary" (Benware 1986:86).

Assuming that this is true for Notker, one would like to see rules also apply across word boundaries, if they apply across syllable boundaries. And often they do:

Dental Lenition:

/(d,t)/ Separated
by Syllable Boundary
from Nasal

/vi(m,n) (d,t)+ət/
[fin\$dət]
<findet>
'find, 3rd sg pres'
I, 65, 18

/(d,t)/ Separated
by Syllable and Word
Boundary from Nasal

/mijn+tejl/
[mijn\$dejl]
<mîn dèil>
'my part'
Nps 16, 17

That scholars have lauded Notker's ear for marking this seems a little overblown. Of course a syllable boundary that doubles as a word boundary may be a degree "stronger" than a simple syllable boundary, but there is no fundamental difference between the two.

No fundamental phonological difference that is. What separates words from syllables is a very large graphological difference. Words can be bordered by spaces. They can be moved around in a sentence. Syllables cannot.

Perhaps only the most pedantic scholar would insist that every spelling merger should be interpreted phonologically. Notker did not write in the International Phonetic Alphabet, but rather his writing system was constrained by the Latin alphabet, Latin spelling mergers, concerns about saving parchment, and other non-phonological, but rather graphological factors.

Distinguishing phonological from graphological spelling mergers is difficult. Perhaps many scholars have been hindered in this because they conditioned both types of processes by the same boundary--the word boundary. So, for example, in Notker <sk> and <sc> appear word internally, but <sg> word finally:

Word Internally Before <i,e>	Word Internally Before <a,o,u>	Word Finally
/vi(ž,s)(g,k)+ən/ [fi(š,s)ʂken] <fiſken> 'fish, dat sg' I,751,23	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)+a/ [fi(š,s)+ka] <fiſca> 'fish, nom pl' II,243,25	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)/ [fi(š,s)k] <fiſg> 'fish, nom sg' I,167,28

Penzl writes:

"sg im Auslaut wie bei *fiſg*, *flèiſg* stimmt mit der sonstigen Schreibung des velaren Verschlußlautes überein" (Penzl 1968a:149).

But what does this mean? Should "im Auslaut" be translated as "word final", "syllable final", or both? Does this merger show a phoneme merger, a grapheme merger, or both? I understand him as saying that we should interpret <g> <fiſg> as fortis. [k] is just written <g> word finally. If so, then along with this purely graphological conclusion, Penzl goes on in the next sentence to draw a phonological one too. For the velar stops:

"Es besteht keine phonemische Opposition zwischen Lenis und Fortis im Auslaut" (Penzl 1968a:149).

Degrees of Boundary

For Notker, I will use the syllable boundary as the base phonological boundary. It increases in intensity as:

Syllable
Syllable and word
Syllable and low point
Syllable and high point

Similarly, the word boundary will be the base graphological boundary. It increases in intensity as:

Word
Word and low point
Word and high point

Morpheme Boundaries

An issue would be how to incorporate morpheme boundaries---a morphological, rather than graphological or phonological

boundary--that nevertheless affects graphology and phonology.

So, for example, in Modern German phonology, a morpheme boundary may affect syllable division, and so Syllable Final Fortification (Benware 1984:86). So <Feigling> should divide to maximize onsets, but may divide on the morpheme boundary:

Syllable Division
not Influenced by
Morpheme Division

/fajg+liŋ/
[faj\$gliŋ]

Syllable Division
Influenced by
Morpheme Division

/fajg+liŋ/
[fajk\$liŋ]

A graphological example could come from American advertising. Often the second element of a compound is capitalized, as if the morpheme boundary was really a word boundary:

Word Division
not Influenced by
Morpheme Division

/dejta+bejs/
<Database>

Word Division
Influenced by
Morpheme Division

/dejta+bejs/
<DataBase>

To exclude morpheme boundaries from phoneme or grapheme mergers, yet account for their effect, they can be included in whatever rule determines syllable or word boundaries.

So, for grapheme mergers, if the two elements of a compound word also occur as separate words, then a word boundary could get set between those two elements. Grapheme mergers then would not get conditioned by the morpheme boundary directly, but by the word boundary it helped place.

For phoneme mergers, the morpheme boundary could be part of the rule that determines where to put syllable boundaries (Benware 1984:86). Phoneme mergers then would not get conditioned by the morpheme boundary directly, but by the syllable boundary it helped place.

Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs

Definition

Ideally, only posit phonemes contrasted in minimal pairs. However, since texts have a limited amount of words, do not insist on perfect minimal pairs (English <bit> <pit>), but accept near minimal pairs (English <man> <land>).

In addition, accept even near minimal pairs of spelling patterns.

Do not be content only to contrast phonemes in one environment, but in as many as possible.

In addition, for each minimal pair, list its:

morphological form in //
 phonological form in []
 graphological form in <>
 gloss in ''
 place in text

Discussion

Near Minimal Pairs of Graphs

So, for example, word internally Penzl can contrast /pf/, /f/ and /v/ with different graphs. However the minimal pairs are not perfect, but only "near". <òuene>, <òffen> and <òpfer> differ in more than just their labial obstruents.

"im Inlaut steht /v/ wie in zuivelon, òuene, finuiu mit /f/ in begrifen, rùofen, òffen in Opposition" (Penzl 1968a:144)

"bei Notker pf im Inlaut: òpfer, chàpfe, wo also die Opposition zu f(f) deutlich ausgedrückt ist" (Penzl 1968a:144)"

Near Minimal Pairs of Spelling Patterns

Word initially however, Penzl would contrast only two labials, /pf/ and /v/. Unfortunately, both are usually written with <f>, but /v/ is sometimes written as <u> when not preceded by a sonorant.

	/v/	/pf/
Word	/žo+vilo/	/iro+pfleg+ə(ž,s)(t,d)/
Initial	[žo\$vil _o]	[iro+pfleg _s ə(š,s)t]

After	<so uilo>	<iro flègest>
Vowel	'so much'	'care for her, 2nd sg pres subj'
	Nps 151,17	Nps 134,13

/žo+vil_o/
[žo\$vil_o]
<so fìlo>
'so much'
Nps 159,11

/waž\$vil_o/
[waž\$fil_o]
<wàs fìlo>
'was much'
Nps 23,2

Penzl contrasts here, if not a near minimal pair of graphs, at least a near minimal pair of graph patterns:

"Im Anlaut steht neben dem mit *u* wechselndem *f* von *fàren*, *fàhen*, *frûo* ein *f*, das nicht mit *u* wechselt und ahd. *ph*, *pf* entspricht: *fàfen* 'Pfaffen', *fàlanza* 'Pfalz', *frûondo* 'Pfründe', *flègen* 'pflegen', *geflànzot* 'gepflanzt'" (Penzl 1968a:144).

"Es ist kein Zusammenfall der beiden Labiale erfolgt. Das nicht wechselnde *f* muß den Lautwert einer Affrikate, also [pf], haben" (Penzl 1968a:144).

Multiple Environments

The above quotes should show that Penzl was not content to just posit /f/, /v/ and /pf/ by contrasting them word internally. Indeed, the scholar always takes pain to contrast phonemes in at least three environments: Anlaut, Inlaut and Auslaut (Penzl 1968a, 1972). Those scholars disagreeing with him have had to take similar care in positing phonemes. So Moulton contrasts obstruents after vocalic, liquid and nasal sonority (Moulton 1979). Perhaps both these techniques could be combined. In this paper's section on minimal pairs, obstruents are contrasted syllable initially and finally after vocalic, liquid, nasal and obstruent sonority. ✓ Syllable internally, syllable peaks of sonority prevent them from being contrasted after anything except other obstruents. ✓

Multiple Forms

Penzl is usually careful to differentiate morphological forms (in

//), phonological forms (in []), and graphological forms (in *italics*). He also usually glosses a word if its meaning is not obvious and, in his 1972 book, cross references graphological forms against extracts from texts (in parentheses).

"Bei den Nasalphonemen /n/ /m/ weisen die Folgenentwicklung auf ein velares Allophon vor Gaumenlaut, z.B. [ŋ] in *dìng*(64), *làngo*(144)" (Penzl 1972:102).

My only break from Penzl would be to always list all five pieces of information about each minimal pair, and to list minimal pairs in tabular form. I also mark in **bold** those segments of a form being discussed.

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/w ijb +ən/	/((ž,s)ka [^] pa [^] re/
Initial	[w ij \$ b ən]	[(š,s)ka [^] \$pa [^] \$re]
After	<uu iben >	<skâpâre>
Vowel	'woman, dat pl' I, 776, 32	'sheepskin, dat sg' II, 283, 25

Use Frequency Distributions to Posit Phonemes

Definition

When positing phonemes differentiated by place of articulation:

Velars imply Labials

Labials imply Dentals

For manner of articulation:

Affricates imply Fricatives

Fricatives imply Stops

Discussion

Lass cites a 1979 language survey by Nartey. The survey had established for obstruents:

"cross linguistic frequency hierarchies for place of articulation" (Lass 1984:154).

Nartey concluded that dentals were "more frequent across languages" (Lass 1984:154) than labials. Labials were in turn more frequent than velars. As far as manner of articulation, stops were more frequent than fricatives, which were themselves more frequent than affricates.

Besides just being a survey of language typologies, Lass believes that:

"the frequency distributions can serve as a partial check on the reconstruction of unattested language states: the 'odder' the system we construct, the more argumentative support it needs." (Lass 1984:155).

If so, perhaps a phonemic contrast posited in a text's labial fricatives should imply one in the dental fricatives, and in the labial stops. Through both of them, the contrast would be implied into the dental stops too.

Such a rigorous application of frequency distributions, especially for place of articulation, is not born²out in all modern languages. Hawaiian, according to Lass, has a labial and velar stop, but no dental one (Lass 1984:152). Rotokas contrasts

②

two velar stops in voice (Lass 1984:149). Nevertheless it has only single voiceless labial and dental ones. Maori has a labial fricative, but no dental one (Lass 1984:152).

Syllable Division

Definition

At the beginning of the walkthrough, assume that syllables divide in the text in the same way as they do in modern related languages.

At the end of the walkthrough, use rules conditioned by syllable boundaries to refine syllable division.

Discussion

Modern Syllable Division

Benware offers three rules for dividing syllables in Modern German:

"Onsets are maximized" (Benware 1986:85).

"Syllable boundaries coincide with word boundaries" (Benware 1986:85)

"Syllable boundaries within the interlude must not result in sequences of phonemes which do not also occur in word initial or word final position" (Benware 1986:85).

These rules also seem general enough to apply to English. Perhaps they could be used to provisionally divide syllables in any Germanic text.

Later Refinement

At the end of the analysis, rules conditioned by syllable boundaries could be used as input to determine if syllable division should be refined. So, for example, say that Syllable Initial Fortition is posited for Notker. Later, multi-syllabic words could be scanned for "fortis" spellings syllable initially. Such spellings could refine syllable division.

Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes

Definition

Derive an allophone by a phoneme merger, if this allows you to avoid positing a separate phoneme for it.

Even if other forms force you to posit a certain phoneme, derive an allophone by phoneme merger, even if it only allows you to be less specific about what the underlying phoneme in a form is.

Do not, however, prefer absolute neutralizations to phonemes.

Discussion

Phoneme Mergers to Allow for Less Phonemes

So, for example, Penzl does not posit /ŋ/ for Notker. Instead, he derives it by a phoneme merger of /m/ and /n/ to [ŋ] before velars:

"Bei den Nasalphonemen /n/ /m/ weisen die Folgentwicklung auf ein velares Allophon vor Gaumenlaut, z.B. [ŋ] in *dīng*(64), *lāngo*(144)" (Penzl 1972:102).

For Old High German, the issue is treated more fully (but with the same conclusions) in an article devoted to /ŋ/:

"It is generally assumed that /n/ before velars as in *lang*, *danc*, *bringan* had the velar allophone [ŋ]" (Penzl 1968b:342).

Although this adds a phoneme merger, it eliminates a phoneme:

Without Nasal Assimilation	With Nasal Assimilation
/ŋ/	/(m,n)/
/ʒiŋg+ən/ [ʒiŋ\$gən] <siŋgen> 'sing, inf' I, 96, 16	/ʒi(m,n)g+ən/ [ʒiŋ\$gən] <siŋgen> 'sing, inf' I, 96, 16

As Lass writes:

"Phonologists in general seem, whatever their theoretical

allegiances, to...use rules to minimize units" (Lass 1984:25). ✓

Phoneme Mergers to Allow for Less Specific Underlying Forms

I would further argue that Penzl should posit Nasal Assimilation here even if some other forms forced him to posit /ŋ/ anyway. Although Nasal Assimilation would not eliminate a phoneme for him, it would still allow him to be less specific about what nasal phoneme was in a form.

Without Nasal Assimilation	With Nasal Assimilation
/ŋ/	/(m,n,ŋ)/
/ʒiŋg+ən/ [ʒiŋ\$gən] <sìngen> 'sing, inf' I,96,16	/ʒi(m,n,ŋ)g+ən/ [ʒiŋ\$gən] <sìngen> 'sing, inf' I,96,16

Phonemes instead of Absolute Neutralizations

Penzl could have also derived just [ŋ], instead of [ŋg], from /(m,n)g/. To do this, a second phoneme merger would get ordered after Nasal Assimilation. In, say, Velar Deletion, after [(m,n)] assimilated in place to [g], [g] could merge with zero, by deleting after the homorganic nasal [ŋ].

	/(m,n)/
Nasal Assimilation	/ʒi(m,n)g+ən/ [ʒiŋ\$gən]
Velar Deletion	[ʒiŋ,əŋ] <sìngen> 'sing, inf' I,96,16

The phoneme /g/ here however was only posited to condition a change in /(m,n)/, and then conveniently delete off. This would be an "absolute neutralization", a tactic that Lass calls:

"a pretty unconstrained theory, and in principle might allow you to do almost anything to get the right results" (Lass 1984:211).

Relevant Spelling Mergers

Definition

Do not require a spelling merger to be carried out in %100 of all cases to be phonologically or graphologically relevant. To differentiate the relevant from the irrelevant, accept spelling mergers as relevant if they occur more frequently in a likely environment for a process, than they do in other environments.

Discussion

So, for example, Lloyd writes that <h> in Notker often disappears in the sequence /VhVC/, where /V/ is any syllabic vowel, /C/ is any consonant, and /h/ is the laryngeal:

/ʒlah+ən/
[ʒlaʌn]
slâh
'slay, inf'
I,105,9

More often than not however, the <h> does get written:

/ʒlah+ən/
[ʒlaʌn]
slâhen
'slay, inf'
I,34,8

Deletion of laryngeals is linked to an intervocalic environment, so Lloyd takes the spelling as phonologically relevant. The spellings with <h>, even though in the majority, are explained away as due to analogy. Notker was:

"taking pains to preserve the 'correct' spelling-pronunciation and combat the 'sloppy colloquial speech'"
(Lloyd 1968:122).

Penzl too does not insist that spelling mergers be %100 regular in order to take them as phonologically relevant. He even touches on statistical analysis in his section on methods:

"Genauere Häufigkeitsangaben sind wichtig...Schon aus der statistischen Erfassung der Zeichen ergibt sich die Bedeutung gewisser Zeichengruppen" (Penzl 1972:31).

Only Phoneme Mergers

Definition

The only allophonic changes scribes marked were the merger of phonemes. Do not extract any less noticeable phonological change from spelling mergers.

Treat phoneme addition or deletion a merger of a phoneme with zero.

Discussion

An example from Modern German might illustrate this best. Benware proposes that German obstruents contrast in fortition. While fortis inherently implies voiceless, lenis obstruents can be either voiced or voiceless. In at least Standard German however, lenis obstruents are voiced (Benware 1984:36). These lenis and fortis obstruents merge to fortis (and so voiceless) ones syllable finally.

Standard German Syllable Final Fortition:

Voiced and Lenis Allophone

/ra [^] d+əs/	[ra [^] ʂdəs]	<Rades>	'wheel, gen'
------------------------	------------------------	---------	--------------

Voiceless and Fortis Allophone

/ra [^] d/	[ra [^] t]	<Rad>	'wheel, nom'
/ra [^] t/	[ra [^] t]	<Rat>	'council, nom'
/ra [^] t+əs/	[ra [^] ʂtəs]	<Rates>	'council, gen'

A lesser known process, according to Benware, occurs syllable initially. Lenis obstruents (which are also voiced) become voiceless, but not fortis, after obstruents.

Standard German Syllable Initial Devoicing:

Voiced and Lenis Allophone

/dem+dankən/	[dem ^ʂ dan ^ʂ kən]	<dem Danken>	'thanking, dat'
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Voiceless and Lenis Allophone

/das+dankən/	[das ^ʂ d ^ʂ an ^ʂ kən]	<das Danken>	'thanking, nom'
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Voiceless and Fortis Allophone

/dem+tankən/	[dem ^ʂ tan ^ʂ kən]	<dem Tanken>	'filling, dat'
/das+tankən/	[das ^ʂ tan ^ʂ kən]	<das Tanken>	'filling, nom'

The syllable final process is a phoneme merger, the syllable initial process is not. It is disputed whether native Germans

recognize either of these rules. Perhaps however, no one would dispute that they are more likely to notice the fortition than the devoicing. Curiously, in Middle High German, before spelling was standardized, Syllable Final Fortition was often marked:

Middle High German Syllable Final Fortition:

Lenis Allophone				
/raʌd+əʒ/	[raʌʒdəʒ]	<rades>	'wheel, gen'	
Fortis Allophone				
/raʌd/	[raʌt]	<rat>	'wheel, nom'	
/raʌt/	[raʌt]	<rat>	'council, nom'	
/raʌt+əʒ/	[raʌʒtəʒ]	<rates>	'council, gen'	

Syllable Initial Devoicing was not marked. An exception might of course be in those mostly southern dialects, where the process may have been, as it is today, a fortition, and so a phoneme merger.

"Southern" German Syllable Initial Fortition:

Lenis				
/dem+dankən/	[demʒdanʒkən]	<dem Danken>	'thanking dat.'	
Fortis				
/das+dankən/	[dasʒtanʒkən]	<das Danken>	'thanking nom.'	
/dem+tankən/	[demʒtanʒkən]	<dem Tanken>	'filling dat.'	
/das+tankən/	[dasʒtanʒkən]	<das Tanken>	'filling nom.'	

In 1968 Penzl argued that it is "eine große Seltenheit" (Penzl 1968a:147) that a writing system would mark more than just phonemes. In 1972 he reiterates this:

"Nur selten gibt uns der Gebrauch des lateinischen Alphabets die Möglichkeit, durch die Schreibung, nicht nur durch Folgentwicklung und moderne Werte, auf Allophone schließen zu können" (Penzl 1972:34).

Moulton is even more to the point:

"Wir fragen einen Deutschen: 'Sprachen Sie das *p* von *spare* genau so aus wie das *p* von *Paare*?' Ohne phonetische Ausbildung wird der Sprecher kaum den Unterschied zwischen dem normalerweise unaspirierten [p] von *spare* und dem aspirierten [p^h] von *Paare* bewußt hören. Und weil er diesen Unterschied nicht bewußt hört, würde er nie auf die Idee kommen, die allophonisch verschiedenen /p/'s verschieden zu schreiben" (Moulton 1987:73).

Given this, one might reconstruct from texts only the most noticeable of allophonic changes, those that merge phonemes.

Such a function however would cut through a bulk of scholarship written on spelling mergers. Take, for instance, three examples from Moulton and Penzl.

The Anlautgesetz might be a full or partial fortition:

"Notkers Wechseln zwischen den Zeichen *u* und *f* (*uàren fàren*) deutet auf diese Anlautsallophone hin, wobei wie bei den Verschlußlauten zumindest eine "Halbfortis" *f* im engen Anschluß an vorhergehende Geräuschlaute wahrscheinlich ist" (Penzl 1972:102).

Modern dialects are cited to support this. And indeed, perhaps Swiss dialects had and still have "half" fortis allophones. A "half" fortition however would not merge the phonemes, and so could not be extracted from the text.

Nasals get written <n> before Germanic */f/, but <m> before Germanic */p/. This marks before Germanic */f/:

"ein labiodentales Allophon des /m/" (Penzl 1972:102).

Modern dialects are again cited to support this. And indeed, perhaps Swiss dialects had and still have a labialdental nasal before a labialdental fricative. I pronounce nasals this way in English and German. Nevertheless, a merely labiodental [m] is not a merger of labial /m/ with dental /n/. That nasals merge to <n> before Germanic */f/, but <m> before Germanic */p/ must mark something more noticeable, a phoneme merger. In this paper I develop it as a merger of /p/ with zero (so epenthesis), between nasals and the fortis /f/ fricative from Germanic */p/.

For all Old High German dialects, Moulton posits only one labial fricative /f/ (Moulton 1987:76). Nevertheless:

"Wir sind jetzt anscheinend in der glücklichen Lage, die verschiedenen Allophone des labialen Frikativs beschreiben zu können. Inlautend geminiert war er fortis und wohl relativ lang, allerdings länger nach kurzem Vokal, kürzer nach langem Vokal oder Diphthong; Schreibung: -ff- und -f-. Anlautend war er kurz und lenis; Schreibung: *u-* neben *f-*. Inlautend einfach war er auch kurz und lenis; Schreibung wieder *-u-* neben *-f-*. Auslautend war er kurz und fortis: kurz weil niemals -ff- geschrieben, fortis weil niemals *-u* geschrieben" (Moulton 1987:79).

The geminates could be considered an opposition of one phoneme versus a sequence of two /f≠ff/. Nevertheless, if there is only one labial fricative /f/, whether it became fortis or lenis in an environment would not merge it with another phoneme. Moulton is straightforward about this: /u

"Und jetzt kommt das Überraschende: Die althochdeutschen Schreiber müssen diesen allophonischen Unterschied bewußt gehört haben, denn nur so ist zu erklären, daß sie ihn (allerdings inkonsequent) geschrieben haben: u (neben f) für die Lenis, aber nur f und ff für die Fortis" (Moulton 1987:79).

Phoneme Addition

For purposes of this paper, a phoneme merger would also mean a "Zusammenfall mit Null" (Penzl 1972:25)--a special case that is often treated separately as phoneme addition or deletion. So, for example in Modern English, a homorganic, fortis, epenthetic stop merges with zero, when between a nasal and a fortis fricative:

/t/	/∅/
/sent+s/	/sen ∅ s/
[sents]	[sents]
<cents>	<sense>

Spelling Patterns Other than Spelling Mergers

A side effect of this function is that any spelling pattern that is not a spelling merger cannot be interpreted phonologically, but only graphologically. Only spelling mergers then are treated in this paper. That is not to say that other types of spelling patterns are uninteresting. So, for example, Clausning writes:

"Irish monks seem to have left no obvious traces on the German language, the word *Glocke*, stemming from Irish *clocc*, being the only known exception." (Clausning 1979:361).

Curiously, every example of the morpheme 'bell' in Notker is written with <cc>:

<clòcca>	nom sg	II,334,13
<glòccun>	gen sg	I,749,13
<clòcccon>	gen pl	II,400,5
<glòccûniòh>	dat sg	I,749,13

If the spelling can be analyzed as influenced by Irish <clocc>, then a morpheme specific rule could generate it.

Broaden Phoneme Mergers

Definition

Broaden the application of a phoneme merger until:

doing so would make the phoneme merger more complex

doing so would mean positing an unnatural grapheme merger.

Discussion

So, for example, the Tatian marks umlaut of [a] (ex: <faran> 'travel, inf'; <ferit> 'travel, 3rd sg pres' Braune 1987:304). But the Tatian does not mark umlaut of [u] or [o]. One could write a rule.

Unrounded Back Vowel Umlaut:

The unrounded back vowel /a/ becomes fronted before [i] to merge with /e/, or possibly /æ/ if ones analysis has unlauded phonemes.

A spelling merger stops a phoneme merger from broadening, only if the spelling cannot be explained as a natural grapheme merger. This will get treated in a later function, but for now one could say that since Latin does not mark front rounded vowels, allowing <u> and <o> to mark them in German would not be an unnatural grapheme merger. So Umlaut gets broadened to include all back vowels.

Back Vowel Umlaut:

The back vowels [a,o,u] become fronted before [i].

This is of course does not entail positing unlauded phonemes, those would have to be established through *Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs*.

Since fronting front vowels is redundant, the rule can "apply vacuously" (Lass 1984:95) to them. The rule gets broadened again to affect all vowels.

All Vowel Umlaut:

All vowels [i,e,a,o,u] become fronted before [i].

In this paper, long vowels and diphthongs are written as a sequence of a syllabic vowel, plus one of three non-syllabic vowels (/j,w,^/). It is in keeping with *Posit as Little as*

Possible, that these sequences are as undefined as feasible. In any case, vowels followed by a non-syllabic vowel (i.e. long vowels and diphthongs) do not show umlaut (ex: <wattan> 'clothe, inf'; <gewati> 'clothing, uninfl' Braune 1987:164). The Latin script, however, could have mark [e^] with <e>, just as it was able to mark [e] with <e> (ex: <faran>, <ferit>). So a grapheme merger writing both [e^] and [a^] as <e> would be unnatural. Umlaut then gets restricted. ed

Short Vowel Umlaut:

All vowels [i,e,a,o,u] get fronted before [i], unless another vowel comes between them.

Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place

Definition

Do not restrict the input of a phoneme merger by a place of articulation, unless its conditioning is also described with that place feature.

Discussion

Place features for the consonants would be labial, dental and velar (Bynon 1977:81).

So, for example, Syllable Final Fortition in Modern German affects all obstruents, it does not exclude the dentals. Nevertheless, in Middle High German, labial fricatives mark this fortition, but dentals do not.

	Lenis	Fortis
Labial	/hov/	/half/
Fricative	[hof]	[half]
Syllable	<hof>	<half>
Final	'court, nom sg'	'help, 3rd sg past'
Dental	/ež/	/es/
Fricative	[eš]	[es]
Syllable	<es>	<ez>
Final	'it, nom sg'	'it, gen sg'

Should we be comfortable however with a fortition rule that somehow excluded dental fricatives? Some scholars might.

So, for example, Penzl proposes Syllable Final Fortition for Notker, but only in the labial and velar stops:

"Im Auslaut steht zum Unterschied von den Reibelauten das Lenisphonem (*kàlb, tåg, flèisg*), bei dem Fortisallophone anzunehmen sind" (Penzl 1972:104).

In ^(his)their account of Old English Phonology, Lass proposes Word Final Devoicing, but only for velars. The rule, however:

"raises the problem of 'explanation' or motivation" (Lass 1973:183).

To be sure, it is doubtful that this function can stand

unamended. Lass cites three examples where labials and velars condition a change, but dentals do not (Lass 1984:98). Unfortunately, all three are from reconstructed languages: Old English, Proto-Uralic and Middle Korean. Perhaps a reduction in the phonemic inventory should be an exception to the function. Maybe the function should be limited to fortitions and lenitions, or processes conditioned by syllable boundaries.

The function though, rough cut as it is, is enough for an analysis of Notker. Its refinement could be left to a more difficult text.

Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers

Definition

Explain a spelling merger as a merger of phonemes. Only do so though, if a phoneme merger can make it through the functions on phoneme mergers.

If no phoneme merger makes it through the functions for them, explain the spelling merger as a grapheme merger. Only do so though, if a grapheme merger can make it through the functions on grapheme mergers.

Discussion

Phoneme Merger

It is of course arbitrary to first try and explain a spelling merger phonologically. This seems however to follow the bulk, but not all, of scholarship. So, for example, <t> and <d> do not contrast after <n>, but merge to <d>. Collinge, in an overview of Notker, writes that:

"Jellinek (1897:86) pointed to the internal d of *hèndi* (OHG normally *hènti*), and proclaimed an Alemannic assimilation, honestly recorded by Notker as he kinetically accompanied with his speech organs what he was writing with his pen--not a scribal carelessness, as Sehrt & Starck would have it" (Collinge 1985:122).

At least according to Collinge then, Jellinek sees the conditioning for the spelling as phonological. Sehrt and Starck however posit the conditioning as either graphological or unknown.

Perhaps a few of Notker's spelling mergers could be interpreted as either phonologically or graphologically conditioned. An interesting twist then might be to reword this function, to prefer graphological to phonological conditioning.

Grapheme Merger

Surprisingly, Penzl does not spell out when a scholar should try to interpret a spelling merger as graphologically conditioned instead of phonologically conditioned. This is strange, since I think this question should be, and should have been for the last 150 years, a core issue in historical phonology. Penzl does however, posit three grapheme mergers for Notker. One might extrapolate his method from his arguments for them.

"Bei Notker haben wir tatsächlich Grund anzunehmen, daß er gelegentlich phonemische Kontraste nicht ausdrückte und für zwei Phoneme ein Lautzeichen schrieb (*t f z*)."
(Penzl 1955:207).

Because of the Anlautgesetz, both [t] from /t/ and a "half fortis" [t] from /d/ are written <t> word initially. The merger is likened to phonetic transcriptions of Modern Swiss:

"Wir finden, daß *t* in *tàg*, *tûon* (aus westgerm. *d*) *triuua* (westgerm. *tr*) im Anlaut immer unveränderlich bleibt und so zu dem mit *d* wechselnden *t* in *taz ter* einen Gegensatz bildet" (Penzl 1955:204).

"Bei den Dentalen scheint Notker das gleiche getan zu haben wie moderne Dialektforscher (z.B. Heusler u.a.), indem er die stärkere Variante der Lenis *d* mit dem Fortiszeichen *t* schrieb, ohne damit einen Zusammenfall mit dem *t* Phonem bezeichnen zu wollen." (Penzl 1955:206).

<pf> is restricted word initially, but rather [pf] and [f] are both written <f> there:

"Bei Notker finden wir im Anlaut außer dem *f*, das mit *u* wechselt, auch ein *f*, dem in anderen Denkmälern die Schreibung *ph* oder *pf* entspricht, und für welches der Lautwert einer labialen Affrikata angenommen wird: *fàlenzcràven* 'Pfalzgraf' (Akk.), *flègen* 'pflegen (praesidere)', *fafen* 'sacerdotes', aber *skèpfo* 'Schöpfer'. Es zeigt sich, daß im orthographischen System Notkers die Lautzeichen *t* und *f* im Anlaut zweierlei phonemische Werte haben." (Penzl 1955:205).

<zz> is restricted word finally, but rather [ts] and [s] are both written <z> there:

"Für den Auslaut gilt das gleiche für *z*, das sowohl Affrikata wie auch Spirans bedeuten kann: *scùz* 'Schuß', *scàz* 'Geld, Schatz'." (Penzl 1955:205).

All three of Penzl's rules are established by referencing contrasts still found in Modern German. To highlight this, Penzl even gives us the Modern German glosses when they are not obvious. Perhaps this more than anything shows what method he uses to decide between phonological and graphological conditioning. A spelling merger is taken as graphological, only

if taking it as phonological would mean positing a phoneme merger that is not found in the modern dialects.

This function will break from Penzl in that it allows one to posit additional grapheme mergers--those that are not immediately obvious from the modern language. Phonological explanations will have to pass through several functions on them. If no phonological explanation makes it through those functions, then graphological explanations get entertained. Of course any graphological explanation would need to pass through the functions on them.

Only Posit Natural Grapheme Mergers

Definition

Only posit grapheme mergers that can be justified by spelling mergers in the source writing system.

Discussion

So, for example, the source writing system for Notker was Medieval Latin, or perhaps some other system originally based on Latin. Fitting Alemannic phonology into a Romance alphabet could understandably lead to problems. So Clausning argues:

"the primary reason for Notker's failure to indicate affricates or rounded front vowels was the lack of suitable orthographic symbols at his disposal" (Clausning 1979:367).

So, for example, Latin did not contrast [pf] and [f] word initially. So a scholar could posit a grapheme merger spelling both [#\$pf] and [#\$f] as <#f>:

	[\$f]	[\$pf]
Notker's Latin	[fa ₅ vo ₅ res] <fauores>	Did Not Exist
Notker's Alemannic	/vilo/ [fil ₅ o] <filo> 'much' I, 27, 15	/pfleg+ə(ž, s)(d, t) / [pfleg ₅ ə(š, s)t] <flègest> 'care, 2nd sg pres subj' I, 815, 20

Latin did however, contrast [b] and [p] word initially. A scholar then could not posit a grapheme merger spelling both [#\$b] and [#\$p] as <#p>:

	[\$b]	[\$p]
Notker's Latin	[bon ₅ us] <bonus>	[pol ₅ us] <polus>
Notker's Alemannic	/buw _χ / *[buw _χ] <pûch> 'belly, nom sg' II, 166, 16	/purpər+ən / [pur\$pər ₅ ən] <pürpurun> 'purple, gen sg' I, 167, 24

WALKTHROUGH

Phonemes

Input

The section on minimal pairs, contrasting obstruents in different syllable positions, after different grades of sonority. All sequences are morpheme internal.

Functions

Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs

Twelve non-sonorants can be contrasted in near minimal pairs.

Syllable Division

Syllable boundaries for the minimal pairs were placed according to Benware's three guidelines for division in Modern German.

Posit as Little as Possible

Phonemes are given only the minimum features needed to distinguish them from others. So, for example, there is only one velar fricative. It does not get assigned a value for fortis, since it does not need this to distinguish it from another velar fricative.

Use Frequency Distributions to Posit Phonemes

So, for example, Notker contrasts two labial fricatives /v≠f/:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/tiʌvə1/	/tiʌf+o/
Initial	[tiʌ\$və1]	[tiʌ\$fo]
After	<tifeuel>	<tifeo>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg'	'deep, adv'
	II, 469, 23	I, 208, 23

That should imply two labial stops /b≠p/ and two dental fricatives /ž≠s/, and through both of those, two dental stops /d≠t/.

Only Phoneme Mergers

Notker marks Anlautgesetz in stops and the labial fricative. If scribes only mark phoneme mergers, then this process alone could help posit the contrasts /b≠p, d≠t, g≠k, v≠f/.

Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place

/h/, if a lenis velar obstruent, only occurs syllable internally when next to a vowel. All the other obstruents, including lenis ones, occur syllable internally next to consonants. To allow for this phonologically, one could posit /h/ as a lenis velar fricative. A phoneme merger could merge lenis velar fricatives with zero, whenever they were adjacent to a consonant. That would, however, restrict the input of a phoneme merger by a place feature, without conditioning the phoneme merger by that same place feature, in violation of *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*. An alternative method to account for the defective distribution of /h/ would be to extract /h/ from the obstruents, positing it as a laryngeal instead. Then some phoneme merger or restriction could only allow laryngeals next to vowels. That would not be in violation of *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*.

Output

Notker contrasted six stops, five fricatives and one laryngeal. They can be minimally described as:

	oral	son	cont	fort	lab	dent	vel
b	yes	no	no	no	yes	---	---
p	yes	no	no	yes	yes	---	---
d	yes	no	no	no	---	yes	---
t	yes	no	no	yes	---	yes	---
g	yes	no	no	no	---	---	yes
k	yes	no	no	yes	---	---	yes
v	yes	no	yes	no	yes	---	---
f	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	---	---
ž	yes	no	yes	no	---	yes	---
s	yes	no	yes	yes	---	yes	---
χ	yes	no	yes	---	---	---	yes
h	no	---	---	---	---	---	---

Commentary

Sonorants

Perhaps all scholars would agree with Penzl in positing four consonantal sonorants, /l,r,m,n/.

"l r m n kommen in allen Stellungen, auch in Geminatio vor" (Penzl 1972:95).

Stops and the Labial Fricatives

The Anlautgesetz is marked in stops and the labial fricatives. Perhaps because of this, these phonemes are often treated together. Scholars are however not agreed as to how many of these phonemes Notker has, and where they occur. Penzl allows for six stops word initially and internally /b,p,d,t,g,k/. Nevertheless he only contrasts four word finally, and /p/ and /k/ are given a low functional load.

"Die phonemische Opposition zwischen Lenis und Fortis ist also nur bei den Zahnlauten /d t/ in allen Stellungen vorhanden, dagegen bei Lippen- und Gaumenlauten auch im Inlaut funktionell nur ganz schwach belastet. Im Auslaut steht zum Unterschied von den Reibelauten das Lenisphonem (kàb, tàg, flèisg), bei dem Fortisallophone anzunehmen sind" (Penzl 1972:104).

The analysis for the labial fricative is near identical as that for the labial stop. The only difference is word finally, where Penzl posits a fortis phoneme, instead of a fortis allophone of a lenis phoneme: ✓

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut (/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /χ/) vorkommt" (Penzl 1972:102).

Moulton devoted an entire paper to establishing six stop phonemes /b,p,d,t,g,k/ for Notker (Moulton 1979), along with two labial fricatives /v,f/. He can also contrast all six stops word initially, if only four word finally (Moulton 1979). In a more recent essay on Old High German consonants however, the scholar only posits dental stops and fricatives as contrasting in fortition (Moulton 1987:77-78). The analysis apparently applies to Notker since: ✓

"Der einzige mir bekannte althochdeutsche Text, zu dem unsere Schemata nicht ganz passen, ist der althochdeutsche Isidor" (Moulton 1987:85).

Clausing posits only five phonemes /p,t,d,k,f/. At least four are fortis.

"Notker tends to use p,t,k (and f) at the beginning of a sentence. This usage implies that the fortis sounds are the normal values" (Clausing 1979:364).

Dental Fricatives

In the above quote on the Anlautgesetz, Clausing only lists the stops and the labial fricative. For these, fortition is generally assumed to be the only distinguishing feature. This is however not the case with the dentals. So, for example, Penzl writes:

"Wir können nicht sicher sein ob es eine Zungenspitzenartikulation bei /s/ war, die schibilantenartig gegenüber einem /z/ des Zungenblattes wirkte oder der Artikulationsunterschied vielleicht in erster Linie auf einer retroflektierten Lautung des /s/ gegenüber einer nichtretroflexen von /z/ beruhte." (Penzl 1972:72).

He cites borrowings from Slavic and Romance; where the fricatives are differentiated by manner, not fortition:

"Die überwiegende Verwendung des ^{§)} langezogenen s-Zeichen für [⊙] postgraphisches [⊙] ž š č, von z für z, s in den altslowenischen Freisinger Denkmälern deutet auf breitere, schibilantenartige Artikulation des ahd. /s/...In französischen Lehnwörtern im Mhd. entspricht s meist frz. s, und z einem frz. c, z, das bis zum 13. Jhd. Affrikata war" (Penzl 1972:72). ✓

Velar Fricatives

There seems to be no disagreement that Notker had a fortis velar fricative /χ/. So Penzl writes:

"ch im Inlaut (*màchôn, sprèchen*) dagegen muß velare Fortis gewesen sein." (Penzl 1968a:145).

Writings on the lenis fricative are more complex. Penzl argues in his section on methods that:

"Die Struktur des Systems selbst muß stets erwogen werden, wenn dessen Teile zu erfassen sind." (Penzl 1968a:134).

Lass echoes this:

"Phonologists in general seem, whatever their theoretical

✓ allegiances, to...make systems as symmetrical as possible" (Lass 1984:25).

Six fricatives mirroring six stops is certainly a symmetrical system. Perhaps that is part of the reason why Penzl continued to posit a lenis fricative, even though he writes that the phoneme did not act like a fricative, but a laryngeal:

"Bei den Geräuschlauten stehen nach Notkers Orthographie die Lenisspiranten *f(u) s h* den Fortisspiranten *f(f) z ch* gegenüber." (Penzl 1968a:149).

"eine phonetische Erklärung der Kürzung durch Einwirkung des Lenisreibelautes *h* ist ebenso schwierig wie die der scheinbaren Monophthongierung in *zihen* (aus *ziehen?*), die wie eine genaue Umkehrung des Wandels *i* zu *ie* in *lîehti, nîeht, îeht* erscheint." (Penzl 1968a:139).

"Schwund von *h* bei Notker (*suêr, trâne*) und Variation mit Schwundformen (*slâhen, slân*) zeigt eine schwache, hauchlautartige Artikulation von /h/ im intervokalischem Inlaut an." (Penzl 1972:101).

He has word final /h/ and /χ/ already merged to /χ/ by Notker's time:

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut (/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /χ/) vorkommt." (Penzl 1972:102).

In discussing why long, high vowels diphthong^{ize} before /h/, but not /χ/, he looks to a contrast between the consonants that existed before Notker, but is now lost:

"Es findet sich bei Notker *ûo ie* vor germ. *h statt ahd. *u i: rûoh* 'rauh', *lîehti* 'levitas, Leichtigkeit', aber *bûh* 'Bauch', *gelîh* 'gleich' mit ahd. *h* aus germ. *k." (Penzl 1968a:139).

"Diese vokalische Verteilung weist nicht nur auf ein Stadium zurück, wo germ. *h* und ahd. *h* (aus germ. *k) im Auslaut noch nicht zusammengefallen waren" (Penzl 1968a:139).

"Hier spiegelt sich im Auslaut eine Periode wieder, wo *h und *χ (aus germ. *k) noch nicht zusammengefallen waren." (Penzl 1972:103).

This lowering of /uw/ to [u^] and /ij/ to [i^] showed that the

fricative /h/ had, at least before Notker's day:

"[einen] stark velaren Charakter" (Penzl 1972:103).

The Braune grammar does not decide on a phoneme, but talks about a laryngeal ("Hauchlaut") word initially and internally, but a fricative ("Spirans") word finally. The fricative is given a secondary feature of guttural, something a laryngeal would have anyway. Perhaps this echoes Penzl's "stark velaren Charakter", since both phrases are used to explain a lowering:

"Der Hauchlaut *h* im Wortinlaut zwischen Vokalen fällt bei N in vielen Wörtern nach kurzem Vokal aus, meist mit nachfolgender Kontraktion der beiden Vokale z.B. *zên* (<*zêhen* '10')...

Nach langem Vokal ist der Ausfall des *h* Ausnahme...In der Regel aber bleibt das *h* nach langem Vokal, der dann regelmäßig verkürzt wird. also *sâhen* (<*sâhen*)...

Der Spirans *h* vor dem die langen Vokale und Diphthonge nicht gekürzt werden...hat infolge seiner tief gutturalen Aussprache bei N das *i* zu *ie*, das *u* zu *uo* diphtongiert. z.B. *lîehte* (<*lîhti* 'leicht'), *dûohta* (<*dûhta*, Praet zu *dûnken*), *rûoh* (<*rûh* 'rauh') aber flekt. *rûher*" (Braune 1987 154: Anm 8).

The grammar points out that <h> often drops out intervocalically "nach kurzem Vokal" (Braune 1987:154 Anm. 8). Schatz was more specific (Schatz 1927:242). <h> gets deleted intervocalically after a short vowel, but only if followed by a closed syllable:

/Vh+VC/	/Vh+V/
/žlah+ən/	/žlah+o/
[žlaʌn]	[žlah _o]
<slâh>	<slâho>
'slay, inf'	'slay, 1st sg pres'
I, 105, 9	II, 618, 3

Deviant forms are explained by analogy:

/Vh+VC/
 /žlah+ən/
 [žlaʌn]
 <slâhen>
 'slay, inf'
 I, 34, 8

Lloyd, in a paper devoted to Notker's <h>, agreed with Schatz. He also, like Penzl and the Braune grammar, has a fricative causing lowering:

"There seems to be little disagreement regarding the behavior of vowels before a tautosyllabic (spirant) *h*; short vowels remain; the long vowels *â*, *ê*, and *ô* remain, but long *î* and *û* are diphthongized to *îe* and *ûo*. This situation is both phonetically acceptable and born out by consistent spelling" (Lloyd 1968:110).

These three processes involve vowels. I cannot treat them formally in a paper that only develops consonants. Nevertheless, it seems like all of this makes ~~so much~~ more sense if /h/ is just taken as a laryngeal.

The laryngeal /h/, by definition, is both lower and weaker than any velar fricative. To highlight this, Lass assigns it the feature [-oral], to distinguish it as a natural class from all other phonemes produced in the oral cavity (Lass 1984:84). The three phoneme mergers could then be written as:

Intervocalic Deletion of [h]:

A laryngeal deletes, when between a syllabic vowel and a closed syllable.

/ʒlah+ən/
[ʒlaʌn]
<slân>
'slay, inf'
I,105,9

Vowel Deletion by [h]:

A non-syllabic vowel deletes, when syllable final before a laryngeal.

/tʃi(j,ʌ)h+ən/
[tʃih,ən]
<zihen>
'pull, inf'
I,315,14

Vowel Lowering by [h]:

A non-syllabic vowel lowers, when syllable internal before a laryngeal.

/ru(w,ʌ)h/
[ruʌh]

<rûoh>
 'raw, nom sg'
 I,167,28

In addition, the last two processes can be seen as a generalization of processes already going on in other Old High German dialects:

"Germ. *ai und *au dagegen wurden beide in ahd. Dialekten vor germ. *h* zu Monophthongen, bleiben Diphthonge vor ahd. *h(h)*, z.B. *zeha*, *flehon*, *zoh*, *hoh* aber *eih*, *zeihhan*, *ouh*, *bouhhan*. Oberdeutsch heißt es *siuh* vor ahd. *h*, aber *ziohan* vor germ. *h*; das weist auf velare Artikulation von ahd. *h*" (Penzl 1968a:139).

I do not know if you can say for sure whether the root vowels in <zeha>, <flehon>, <zoh> and <hoh> are all short, long, or a mix. If all short, then it looks like a deletion, similar to Notker's Vowel Deletion by [h]. If all long, then it is a lowering, similar to Notker's Vowel Lowering by [h]. If a mix, then a mix of the two processes. In any case, the processes seem so much easier to explain if conditioned by a laryngeal, rather than a lenis velar fricative.

Syllable Initial Fortition

Input

Syllable initially, unless preceded by a sonorant, /b,d,g,v/ are written <p,t,k,f>. This merges their spelling there with that of /p,t,k,f/. Examples of this process morpheme internally are given in the section on minimal pairs. In addition, the following morpheme initial examples might be referenced:

	/+b/		/+p/
Syllable	/g+brex+ən/		/g+purpero^+te/
Initial	[gə\$breχ_sən]		[gə\$pur\$pe\$ro^\$te]
After	<gebrèchen>		<gepürperôte>
Sonorant	'break, inf'		'purple, masc nom sg wk'
	I, 40, 5		II, 289, 6
Syllable	/durχ+braχ+e/		No Example
Initial	[durχ\$praχ_sə]		
After	<dùrhpràche>		
Obstruent	'break, 3rd sg past subj'		
	I, 846, 22		
	/+d/		/+t/
Syllable	/vram+di^hən(t,d)/		/vər+trijb+ət/
Initial	[vran\$di^\$hənt]		[vər\$trij\$bət]
After	<fràmdiéhent>		<uertrîbet>
Sonorant	'thrive, 3rd pl pres'		'drive, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 4, 7		I, 173, 5
Syllable	/vrammært+di^hən(t,d)ən/		/uws+trijb+e/
Initial	[vram\$mært\$ti^\$hən\$ten]		[uws\$trij\$be]
After	<fràmmerttîehenten>		<ûztrîbe>
Obstruent	'thrive, m dat pl pres part'		'drive, 3rd sg past subj'
	I, 227, 24		I, 283, 23
	/+g/		/+k/
Syllable	/g+ga^t/		/g+koro^+oat/
Initial	[gə\$ga^t]		[gə\$kor_s_o^\$noat]
After	<gegât>		<gecorônôt>
Sonorant	'go, 3rd sg pres'		'try, uninfl past part'
	I, 270, 31		II, 14, 18
Syllable	/uwf+ga^/		No Example
Initial	[uwf\$ka^]		
After	<ûfkân>		

Obstruent	'go, inf' I, 355, 1		
	/+v/		/+f/
Syllable	/ər+var+ən/		No Example
Initial	[ər\$var,ən]		
After	<eruàren>		
Sonorant	'go, inf' I, 394, 7		
Syllable	/uwf+var+ən(d,t)o/		No Example
Initial	[uwf+far,ən\$do]		
After	<ûffàrendo>		
Obstruent	'go, uninfl pres part' II, 216, 26		
	/+ž/		/+s/
Syllable	/vure+žen(d,t)+ət/		No Example
Initial	[vur,ə\$žen\$dət]		
After	<fùresèndet>		
Sonorant	'send, 3rd sg pres' II, 766, 17		
Syllable	/uws+žen(d,t)+o/		No Example
Initial	[uws\$žen\$do]		
After	<ûzsèndo>		
Obstruent	'send, 1st sg pres' II, 34, 12		
	/+h/		/+χ/
Syllable	/b+heft+ət/		/ər+(kχ,χ)om+ən/
Initial	[bə\$heftət]		[ər\$χom,ən]
After	<behèftet>		<erchòmen>
Sonorant	'fasten, 3rd sg pres' I, 122, 12		'come, inf' I, 18, 20
Syllable	/ən(d,t)+heft+ən/		/uws+(kχ,χ)om+ən/
Initial	[ənt\$heftən]		[uws\$χom,ən]
After	<inthèften>		<ûzchòmen>
Obstruent	'fasten, inf' I, 122, 12		'come, uninfl past part' I, 214, 8

If possible, one would ignore this spelling merger. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether the Anlautgesetz was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: lenis stops, fortis stops, lenis stops and the lenis labial fricatives, fortis stops and the fortis labial fricative, all lenis obstruents, all fortis obstruents, or all obstruents.

Possible phonological changes could be in: voice, aspiration, glottalization or fortition.

Possible phonological environments could be: 'after a sonorant' for a lenition or voicing, or 'syllable initial when not after a sonorant' for a fortition or devoicing.

Voice, Aspiration or Glottalization

Without evidence to the contrary, one would want to be as vague as possible about the change the Anlautgesetz effects. That would be in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. A scholar could then allow the process to mark an aspiration, voicing, devoicing, lenition or whatever. Unfortunately, *Only Phoneme Mergers* prevents Notker from marking any change that did not merge phonemes. Since obstruents are differentiated by fortition, only a fortition or lenition could merge phonemes.

Lenition

If the process must be a change in fortition, then in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*, one would want to leave the question open as to whether it was a lenition after sonorants, or a fortition when not after sonorants. Unfortunately a lenition after sonorants conflicts with *Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs*. Notker contrasts obstruents in fortition after sonorants. A lenition would eliminate that contrast:

	/d/	/t/
Syllable	/werd+ən/	/wort+o/

Initial	[wer\$ðən]	[wor\$to]
After	<uuèrden>	<uuòrto>
Liquid	'become, inf'	'word, gen pl'
	I, 18, 13	I, 12, 6

Fortition of only /b,d,g,v/

If an analyst must specify the Anlautgesetz as a fortition, one would still want to be as vague as possible about the input of the change. It is marked in the lenis stops and lenis labial fricative. If so, one would allow the phoneme merger to be restricted to /b,d,g,v/. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*. The fortition is not conditioned by a place feature (ex: after labials). So it cannot be restricted from dental and velar fricatives.

Fortition of only /b,d,g/

If the Anlautgesetz cannot affect only /b,d,g,v/, perhaps the phoneme merger can affect only /b,d,g/. After all, specifying stops as the input does not require any place features. Unfortunately, such a phoneme merger would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*. The process is marked in labial fricatives, so /v/ needs to be included in the input of the Anlautgesetz.

	/+v/	/+f/
Syllable	/əɾ+var+ən/	No Example
Initial	[əɾ\$var,ən]	
After	<eruàren>	
Sonorant	'go, inf'	
	I, 394, 7	

Syllable	/uwf+var+ən(d,t)o/	No Example
Initial	[uwf+far,ən\$do]	
After	<ûffàrendo>	
Obstruent	'go, uninfl pres part'	
	II, 216, 26	

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/tiʌvəl/	/tiʌf+o/
Initial	[tiʌ\$vəl]	[tiʌ\$fo]
After	<tîeuel>	<tîefo>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg'	'deep, adv'
	II, 469, 23	I, 208, 23

Fortition of all Lenis Obstruents

If possible, one would like to allow the Anlautgesetz to affect all lenis obstruents, without further specifying features for phonemes. That would be in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, this would conflict with *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*. If fortition was enough to merge dental fricatives, Notker could have marked it as easily as he marked the merger of labial fricatives:

	/+ž/	/+s/
Syllable	/vure+žen(d,t)+ət/	No Example
Initial	[vur,əžženšdət]	
After	<furesèndet>	
Sonorant	'send, 3rd sg pres'	
	II, 766, 17	

Syllable	/uws+žen(d,t)+o/	No Example
Initial	*[uwsšsenšdo]	
After	*<ūzzèndo>	
Obstruent	'send, 1st sg pres'	
	II, 34, 12	

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/muwže/	/hejsən/
Initial	[muwšže]	[hejšsən]
After	<mūse>	<hèizen>
Vowel	'mouse, nom pl'	'call, inf'
	II, 488, 13	I, 37, 10

That Notker does not, can only be reconciled by differentiating dental fricatives by more than fortition. If a simple fortition was not enough to merge /ž/ with /s/, then *Only Phoneme Mergers* could account for Notker not marking fortition in them:

	/+ž/	/+s/
Syllable	/vure+žen(d,t)+ət/	No Example
Initial	[vur,əžženšdət]	
After	<furesèndet>	
Sonorant	'send, 3rd sg pres'	
	II, 766, 17	

Syllable	/uws+žen(d,t)+o/	No Example
Initial	[uwsššenšdo]	
After	<ūzsèndo>	
Obstruent	'send, 1st sg pres'	
	II, 34, 12	

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/muwže/	/hejsən/
Initial	[muwšže]	[hejšsən]
After	<mūse>	<hèizen>
Vowel	'mouse, nom pl'	'call, inf'
	II, 488, 13	I, 37, 10

The situation would then parallel a contrast already set up between /h/ and /χ/. In the section on minimal pairs, /h/ was posited as a laryngeal since its defective distribution (never next to consonants in a syllable) was not like that of any other obstruent. Since the laryngeal and velar fricative differ in more than just fortition then, a simple fortition would not merge them. And as with /ž/ with /s/, *Only Phoneme Mergers* would prevent Notker from marking Anlautgesetz in them.

	/šh/	/šχ/
Syllable	/b+heft+ət/	/ər+(kχ,χ)om+ən/
Initial	[bəšhefštət]	[əršχom _s ən]
After	<behèftet>	<erchòmen>
Sonorant	'fasten, 3rd sg pres'	'come, inf'
	I, 122, 12	I, 18, 20
Syllable	/ən(d,t)+heft+ən/	/uws+χom+ən/
Initial	*[əntšhefštən]	[uwsšχom _s ən]
After	*<intchèften>	<ûzchòmen>
Obstruent	'fasten, inf'	'come, uninfl pres part'
	I, 122, 12	I, 214, 8
	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	/ru(w,ʌ)h+ən/	/buwχ+e/
Initial	[ruh _s ən]	[buwšχe]
After	<rùhon>	<bûche>
Vowel	'raw, gen pl masc wk'	'belly, dat sg'
	I, 167, 27	II, 68, 24

Additional Dental Feature

In order to account for the defective distribution of /h/, it had to be removed from the class of obstruents. The only option seemed to classify it as a laryngeal. Happily, this distinction is also enough to differentiate it from /χ/ in more than just fortition. No additional feature specifications are required to account for why the /h≠χ/ contrast is not marked as collapsing though Anlautgesetz.

Unfortunately, that the /ž≠s/ contrast is not marked as collapsing through Anlautgesetz does require an additional feature. /ž/ and /s/ must differ in more than just fortition. An analyst might posit palatization, stridency, rhotacizing, or retroflex. Happily, *Posit as Little as Possible*, allows one to not specify what that feature is, but only mark it as [unk] for "unknown".

Fortition of all Obstruents

If possible, one would like to allow the Anlautgesetz to affect all lenis obstruents, without further specifying whether fortis ones were affected too. That would be in accordance with *Posit As Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*. Since the fortition of fortis obstruents is redundant, the process can be broadened to all obstruents.

Output

Syllable Initial Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable initially, when not inhibited by a preceding sonorant.

In addition, fortition is not enough to merge dental fricatives, so they are marked as contrasting in a second feature, [unk] for "unknown".

	oral	son	cont	fort	lab	dent	unk	vel
ž	yes	no	yes	no	---	yes	yes	---
s	yes	no	yes	yes	---	yes	no	---

Commentary

Phoneme mergers are traditionally broken down into: input, change, and environment. So, for example, in Syllable Initial Fortition:

Input: obstruents

Change: become fortis

Environment: syllable initially, when not inhibited by a preceding sonorant

The Anlautgesetz has received such attention, that one can break

down its discussion into this three part division.

Input

All scholars have noted an alternation in stops and labial fricatives. So, for example, Clausing writes:

Notker's law can be defined as follows: The spellings p-b, k-g, t-d (and sometimes f-v) alternate with each other when preceded by a voiceless or voiced sound, respectively" (Clausing 1979:358).

But does this mean that dental and velar fricatives should be excluded from the input of the phoneme merger? Few scholars address this, but Clausing seems to think so. In refuting the theory that the Anlautgesetz was motivated by a Celtic substratum he writes:

"Old Irish had, in addition to the process of lenition, nasalization of initial sounds by a preceding nasal and gemination by a preceding s. All consonants, not just p, b, d (and f) were affected. It seems odd that German would take up only the process of lenition and only for a restricted group of sounds" (Clausing 1979:362).

And Collinge, in an overview of the Anlautgesetz, remarks that:

"sibilants were not varied" (Collinge 1984:121).

Only in his 1955 article does Penzl address the issue:

"Eine Variation bei Reibelauten wie s š ch ist bei Notker nicht bezeichnet, was Heusler aus 'graphischen Rücksichten' leicht begreiflich fand, da keinerlei passende Lautzeichen zur Verfügung stehen" (Penzl 1955:208).

If anything, scholars have concentrated on the stops. So for example, the Braune Grammar opens its discussion on the Anlautgesetz with:

"Bei Notker wechseln die Wortanlaute b--p, g--k, d--t so, daß p,k,t steht" (Braune 1987:103).

The alternation between <u> and <f> does not get mentioned until the third Anmerkung.

Penzl looks to Modern Swiss for allophones of stops, not all

obstruents:

"Von großem Interesse für uns sind die Angaben in den modernen Dialektstudien, die die Stellungsvarianten (Allophone) der Phoneme *b d g p t k* beschreiben." (Penzl 1955:202).

Leaving out the fricatives is remarkable, at least for anyone who posits a fortition. Fortition in Modern German affects all obstruents, not just stops. It affects all obstruents in Middle High German too. Even in the same paragraph as the above quote, in an analysis of Basel German, Penzl does not find a process for just stops, but for all obstruents:

"Sie [Stärkegrade] hängen von der Betonungsstärke ab und finden sich bei den Verschlusslauten wie auch bei Reibelauten wie *f s š ch*." (Penzl 1955:202).

The marking of the Anlautgesetz even parallels the marking of Middle High German Syllable Final Fortition. Middle High German /*b,d,g,v*/ are all written fortis syllable finally <*p,c,t,f*>:

<libe, lip>	'body, dat and nom/acc sg'
<rade, rat>	'council, dat and nom sg'
<tage, tac>	'day, dat and nom sg'
<hove, hof>	'court, dat and nom sg'

However the fortition does not get marked in the lenis dental fricative:

<lesen, las>	'read, inf and 3rd sg pret'
--------------	-----------------------------

The /*ž≠s*/ contrast is marked syllable finally:

<es>	'it, sg nom/acc'
<ez>	'it, sg gen'

Dental fricatives contrasted here, as they did in Notker, in more than just fortition. And as Notker only marked phoneme mergers in his dialect, so did Middle High German scribes only mark them in theirs.

The writing of /*h*/ and /*χ*/ as <*h*> word finally in Middle High German is more complex, requiring perhaps the same grapheme merger proposed later in this paper for Notker.

Change

Penzl speaks for a fortition, whether full or partial. His view is echoed in the Braune Grammar:

"Notkers Anlautswechsel drückt also tatsächlich Allophone der Lenisphoneme /b/ /d/ /g/ aus" (Penzl 1972:104).

"Notkers Wechseln zwischen den Zeichen *u* und *f* (*uàren fàren*) deutet auf diese Anlautsallophone hin, wobei wie bei den Verschlusslauten zumindest eine "Halbfortis" *f* im engen Anschluß an vorhergehende Geräuschlaute wahrscheinlich ist" (Penzl 1972:102).

"Die stimmlosen Lenes werden im Satzanlaut und nach stimmlosen Konsonanten zu (Halb)-Fortis verstärkt" (Braune 1987:103 Anm. 1).

Clausing posits just the opposite, a lenition:

"Notker tends to use p,t,k (and f) at the beginning of a sentence. This usage implies that the fortis sounds are the normal values, which appear so when left in isolated position but which become lenis when put in a voiced environment" (Clausing 1979:364).

To explain why /t/ is not written <d> after vowels, he proposes:

"a slight difference in pronunciation made one form dental, voiced or unvoiced, susceptible to Notker's law and the other not" (Clausing 1979:363).

Moulton is more cautious than either scholar. He does not specify which features are changed by the Anlautgesetz, but only that:

"the opposition lenis≠fortis was suspended" (Moulton 1979:250).

Arguing however about whether the Anlautgesetz is a lenition or fortition does not necessarily establish it as either. The process might have reflected a devoicing, aspiration, or glottalization for that matter. The issue, at least as far as voicing is concerned, is most thoroughly treated by Clausing. ✓

Moulton and Penzl both assume that Notker's obstruents, both fortis and lenis, were voiceless, as in Modern Swiss. Their thoughts are echoed in the Braune Grammar:

"Die *b, d, g*, bei N sind stimmlose Lenes, an stimmhafte Laute zu denken verbieten die Sprachtatsachen" (Braune 1987:103 Anm 1).

Clausing, however, writes that the lenis obstruents, while voiceless in today's Alemannic:

"were voiced lenes in pre-literary Germanic" (Clausing 1979:365).

Conceivably then, the lenis obstruents could have been voiced in Notker's day too, and the switch to voicelessness taken place sometime in the centuries since then. If so, the Anlautgesetz might only be a devoicing of voiced lenis obstruents.

Why, according to Clausing, this should not be so, was first argued by Baesecke. Formulated by Clausing, the proposal reads:

"b, d, and g must be lenis because a b, d, or g occurring after them appears as p, t, or k. Clearly, there must be some distinction between these consonants and the sounds which produce the b, d, and g forms such as vowels and resonants, which we know are voiced. In short, b, d, and g must be devoiced, but lenis, to be distinguished from p, t, and k" (Clausing 1979:366). ✓

Penzl also gives a quick overview on which earlier scholars opted for a change in voice or fortition:

"Bezeichnenderweise herrschte aber ursprünglich keine Einigkeit unter den Forschern in der Frage der phonetischen Werte, die von Notkers Lautzeichen ausgedrückt werden. Die einen, z.B. J. Grimm, Hoefler, Holtzmann, Wilkens, Wilmanns sahen in Notkers orthographischem Anlautswechsel die Wiedergabe von stimmhaften, bzw. stimmlosen Verschlusslauten, während die anderen, z.B. Braune, Behagel, Schatz, Michels, Heusler darin den sandhibedingten Wechsel von stimmloser Lenis und stimmloser Fortis sahen." (Penzl 1955:200).

Environment

The Braune Grammar suggests:

"Bei N wechseln die Wortanlaute b-p, g-k, d-t, so daß p, t, k steht:

- 1) am Anfang eines Satzes (oder Satzteils)
- 2) im Satz, wenn das vorhergehende Wort auf einen stimmlosen Laut endigt" (Braune 1987:103).

The difference between this environment and the one proposed in this paper are perhaps threefold. First of all, stops become fortis "auf einen stimmlosen Laut" (Braune 1987:103). Voice, and not sonority, inhibits the process. Secondly, the process happens word initially, instead of syllable initially. Lastly, the grammar presupposes to know where sentences begin and end.

Moulton would restructure the grammar's proposal:

"The letters b,d,g,v are written when the words and morphemes in question follow voiced phonemes...but the letters p,t,k(c),f are written in the same words and morphemes when they follow a pause or voiceless phonemes" (Moulton 1979:241).

Again, voice is used instead of sonorancy, and he uses word and morpheme boundaries instead of syllable ones. But rather than also conditioning the Anlautgesetz by sentence boundaries, Moulton opts for speech rhythm--a speech rhythm that still plays a role in Swiss phonology today.

"At least in the Zurich dialect, the opposition lenis≠fortis is suspended not only in clusters of obstruents, but also after a pause" (Moulton 1979:250).

Why 'rhythm' ✓

But even if this was true for Notker, can one really read pauses out of the manuscript? Clausning offers a suggestion:

"Fortunately, we can be fairly sure when the pauses occur, because they are indicated in the manuscript by an orthographic system" (Clausning 1979:364).

Perhaps this orthographic system (high and low points) is what these scholars are really referring to with pause, Satzpause and Satzanlaut. If so, then these phrases can be reconciled with the four degrees of phonological boundary proposed for Notker:

Syllable
Syllable and word
Syllable and low point
Syllable and high point

Penzl spells this out:

"Die Pausen sind in den Handschriften durch die Setzung eines Punktes, manchmal durch die Großschreibung am Satzanfang charakterisiert. Die Tief- und Mittelstellung

dieses Punktes scheint auch die Länge dieser Pause auszudrücken." (Penzl 1955:205).

Syllable Internal Fortition

Input

I am unable to contrast any syllable internal sequences of obstruents in just fortition. So, for example, I cannot contrast [sp] with [sb], [žp] or even [žb]:

	/(b,p)/
Syllable	/(ž,s)(b,p)e^r+e/
Internal	[(ž,s)pe^\$re]
After	<spêre>
Obstruent	'spear, dat sg'
	II,70,18

Examples for the other obstruents can be pulled from the section on minimal pairs.

Functions

If possible, one would ignore this spelling merger. After all, that would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, it would also conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: lenis obstruents, fortis obstruents, or all obstruents.

Possible phonological changes could be in: voice, aspiration, glottalization or fortition.

Possible phonological environments would be: 'next to another obstruent in the same syllable' for a lenition or voicing, and the same environment for a fortition or devoicing.

Voice, Aspiration or Glottalization

Without evidence to the contrary, one would want to be as vague as possible about the change this process effects, in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. That way a scholar could allow it to mark an aspiration, voicing, devoicing, fortition or whatever. Unfortunately, *Only Phoneme Mergers* prevents Notker from marking any change that did not merge phonemes. Since obstruents are differentiated by fortition, only a fortition or lenition could merge phonemes.

Lenition

If the process must be a change in fortition, then in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*, one would want to leave the question open as to whether it was a lenition or a fortition. Unfortunately, according to *Relevant Spelling Mergers*, only processes that are likely for an environment can be posited. Lenition is not a likely process for the environment 'next to another obstruent in the same syllable'. Fortition, however, is.

Fortition of all Lenis Obstruents

If possible, one would like to allow the fortition to affect lenis obstruents, without specifying whether it also affected fortis ones too. That would be in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*. Since the fortition of fortis obstruents is redundant, the process can be broadened to all obstruents.

Different Phonemes

One could of course do away with this fortition, and have all sequences of fortis obstruents generate from underlying fortis phonemes:

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	*No Example	*/speʌr+e/
Internal		*[speʌ\$re]
After		<spêre>
Obstruent		'spear, dat sg'
		II, 70, 18

Nevertheless this is being more specific about what phonemes were in a morpheme, when a phoneme merger could allow you to be less specific. That is in conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*.

Output

Syllable Internal Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable internally, when next to another obstruent.

Commentary

✓ Most scholars, I think, would take this phoneme merger for granted, even uninteresting. Perhaps Moulton comments on it in his discussion of the Anlautgesetz:

"the opposition lenis≠fortis is suspended not only in clusters of obstruents" (Moulton 1979:250).

Penzl posits fortis phonemes:

"Nichtwechselnde fortis ist auch /p/ nach s (*spil*)...ebenso /k/ nach s (*scàz, fisken*)" (Penzl 1972:103).

Syllable Final Fortition

Input

Only dental and labial stops could mark fortition syllable finally, since:

Word finally, [g] and [k] are both written <g>, a grapheme merger to be developed later.

Word finally, [v] and [f] are both written <f>, a grapheme merger to be developed later.

v /ʒ#s/ differ in more than just fortition. Syllable final fortition then would not merge them, and the process not be marked according to *Only Phoneme Mergers*.

/h#χ/ differ in more than just fortition. Syllable final fortition then would not merge them, and the process not be marked according to *Only Phoneme Mergers*.

Sonority is not only binary, but also gradated. Vowels are more sonorant than liquids, liquids more sonorant than nasals, and nasals more sonorant than obstruents.

Syllable finally after nasals, /(d,t)/ is written as "fortis" <t>:

	/(d,t)/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)(d,t)+ət/
Initial	[finʂdət]
After	<f̃ndet>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 65, 18

	/va(m,n)(d,t)/
Syllable	[fant]
Final	<f̃ant>
After	'find, 3rd sg past'
Nasal	I, 98, 19

The merger must hold near %100 of the time. Although there are hundreds of examples of /(m,n)(d,t)\$/ in the Notker Wortschatz, I cannot find any written <nd>. All are written <nt>.

Syllable finally after nasals, /b/ is written as "fortis" <p>:

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/le(m,n)b+ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lemʂbər]	[gumʂpiʂtən]
After	<lèmber>	<gùmpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom sg'	'pond, acc sg'
	II, 486, 6	II, 211, 3
Syllable	/la(m,n)b/	No Example
Final	[lamp]	
After	<làmp>	
Nasal	'lamb'	
	II, 239, 9	

The merger holds %40 of the time. I can find only 15 examples of /m,n)bʂ/. They are distributed in three morphemes: /la(m,n)b/ 'lamb', /tu(m,n)b/ 'dumb', and /(kχ,χ)ru(m,n)b/ 'crooked'.

<làmb>	nom sg	II, 146, 20
<làmb>	nom sg	II, 146, 20
<làmb>	acc sg	II, 146, 26
<làmp>	acc sg	II, 239, 9
<làmp>	acc pl	II, 329, 25
<tùmb>	uninfl	II, 488, 2
<tùmbhèite>	dat sg	I, 323, 21
<tùmplich>	uninfl	II, 265, 3
<chrùm̂b>	uninfl	II, 106, 18
<chrùm̂b>	uninfl	II, 126, 13
<chrùm̂b>	uninfl	II, 169, 29
<chrùm̂b>	uninfl	II, 382, 21
<chrùm̂p>	uninfl	II, 105, 25
<gechrùm̂pta>	1st sg past	II, 197, 3
<gechrùm̂pte>	masc nom sg	I, 750, 23
	past part	

After phonemes with a higher sonority than nasals (i.e. liquids and vowels), /d/ and /b/ are written very infrequently with the "fortis" graphs <t> and <p>. I have not however compiled exact statistics.

	/b/
Syllable	/grab/
Final	[grab]

After <gràp>
Vowel 'grave, acc pl'
II, 186, 21

Syllable /halb/
Final [halb]
After <hàlp>
Liquid 'half'
II, 474, 8

Functions

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this spelling merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: lenis /b/ and /d/, lenis stops, lenis obstruents, or all obstruents.

Possible phonological changes could be in: voice, aspiration, glottalization or fortition.

Possible phonological environments could be: 'syllable finally after nasals', 'syllable finally after nasal sonority or lower'.

Voice, Aspiration or Glottalization

Without evidence to the contrary, one would want to be as vague as possible about the change this process effects. That would be in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. A scholar could then allow the process to mark an aspiration, voicing, devoicing, lenition or whatever. Unfortunately, *Only Phoneme Mergers* prevents Notker from marking any change that did not merge phonemes. Since obstruents are differentiated by fortition, only a fortition or lenition could merge phonemes.

Fortition

If the process must be a change in fortition, then in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*, one would want to leave the question open as to whether it was a lenition of /p/ to [b] syllable initially, or a fortition of /b/ to [p] syllable finally. Then the <b≠p> alternation in <lèmbër≠làmp> could come from an underlying /b/ in /le(m,n)b+ər/ and /la(m,n)b/, or an underlying /p/ in /le(m,n)p+ər/ and /la(m,n)p/. Unfortunately,

labial stops contrast syllable initially after nasals. According to *Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs* then, the stop phoneme in 'lamb' must be lenis.

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/le(m,n)b+ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lem\$bəɾ]	[gum\$pi\$ʔən]
After	<ləmber>	<gumpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl'	'pond, acc sg'
	II,486,6	II,211,3

Fortition of /b,d/ Syllable Finally after Nasals

A fortition of labial and dental stops after nasals could generate [lɒmp] from underlying /lamb/, and so account for <p> in <ləmp>. Unfortunately such a fortition, if it excluded velar stops, would conflict with *Do-Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*. Fortunately [k] and [g] are both written <g> word finally. The fortition then could be broadened to include all stops. [ŋk] from /(m,n)g/ would just be written as <ng> word finally:

	/g/	/k/
Syllable	/ʒi(m,n)g+ən/	/tsi(m,n)k+ən/
Initial	[ʒiŋ\$gən]	[tsiŋ\$ʔkən]
After	<siŋgen>	<ciŋken>
Nasal	'sing, inf'	'prong, dat sg'
	I,96,16	I,775,5

F. d. inf. are your most frequent words. However it is not customary to express regret about the way things are in language.

Syllable	/ʒa(m,n)g/	
Final	[ʒaŋk]	
After	<sàng>	No Example
Nasal	'sing, 3rd pret sg'	
	I,176,14	

Fortition of /b,d,g/ Syllable Finally after Nasals

The fortition of fortis stops is redundant, so the phoneme merger could be broadened to make all stops fortis syllable finally after nasals.

Fortition of all Stops Syllable Finally after Nasals

If possible, one would try to broaden the fortition to all obstruents. Unfortunately, even if lenis fricatives do become fortis after nasals, they should not get marked. For labials, a

grapheme merger will write both [v] and [f] as <f>. For dentals, a simple fortition is not enough to merge [ž] with [s]. For velars, only the fortis fricative could be affected by the fortition. The laryngeal does not even occur syllable internally next to any consonant, including of course nasals:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)ve/	/g+li(m,n)(pf,f)+liχ+e^ro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	glim\$pfliχ _s e^\$ro]
After	<fiñue>	<gelimflichêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl'	'suited, fem dat sg'
	I,197,29	I,781,25
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
Final	[fimf]	[glampf]
After	<fiñf>	<gelàm f>
Nasal	'five'	'suit, 3rd pret sg'
	I,66,26	I,556,5
	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/u(m,n)žər/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)an/
Initial	[un\$žər]	[un\$tsan]
After	<ùnsər>	<ùnzàn>
Nasal	'our, uninflected'	'until'
	I,77,7	I,12,24
Syllable	/u(m,n)ž/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)/
Final	[unš]	[unts]
After	<ùns>	<ùnz>
Nasal	'us'	'until'
	II,634,1	I,54,30
	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	Only Found	/(ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)+əž/
Initial	Across Morpheme	[(š,s)taŋk\$χəž]
After	Boundaries	<stànches>
Nasal		'smell, gen sg'
		I,708,2
Syllable	Not Found	/(ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)/
Final		[(š,s)taŋk]
After		<stàng>
Nasal		'smell, nom sg'
		I,291,32

So fortition cannot be marked in the fricatives. Nevertheless, according to *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*, the process should be broadened to them since it is not contradicted by them.

Fortition Syllable Finally after Nasals

The phoneme merger is already broadened to affect all obstruents. Still, according to *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*, one would like to broaden it to include obstruents after higher levels of sonority, as in Middle High German Syllable Final Fortition. Unfortunately, that would eliminate syllable final contrasts after vowels and liquids:

	/d/	/t/
Syllable	/toʌd/	/tuʌt/
Final	[toʌd]	[tuʌt]
After	<tôd>	<tûot>
Vowel	'death, nom sg'	'do, 3rd pres sg'
	I, 8, 8	I, 9, 26
Syllable	/ward/	/wort/
Final	[ward]	[wort]
After	<uuàrd>	<uuòrt>
Liquid	'become, 3rd pret sg'	'word, nom sg'
	I, 5, 17	I, 502, 18

One might however broaden the phoneme merger to make obstruents fortis after lesser grades of sonority, that is after other obstruents:

	/(d,t)/
Syllable	/i(ž,s)(d,t)/
Final	[i(š,s)t]
After	<ìst>
Obstruent	'be, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 6, 21

Of course this is vacuous. Syllable Internal Fortition already makes the /(d,t)/ in /i(ž,s)(d,t)/ fortis anyway.

Different Phonemes

One could also account for the <b≠p> contrast in <lèmbèr> <làmp> by positing different phonemes:

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/le(m,n)b+ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lemʂbər]	[gumʂpiʂtən]
After	<lèmber>	<gùmpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl'	'pond, acc sg'
	II, 486, 6	II, 21, 3
Syllable	*/la(m,n)p/	No Example
Final	[lamp]	
After	<làmp>	
Nasal	'lamb, acc sg'	
	II, 239, 9	

Such an analysis, however, is equivalent to positing two different phonemes in different declensions of the Modern German word for 'wheel'; <Rad> */raʌt/ and <Rades> /raʌd+əs/. It is also in conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*.

Whole schools
define themselves
according to
whether they permit
such conclusions
or not.

Output

Syllable Final Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable finally, when preceded by nasal sonority or less.

Commentary

Penzl proposes fortition for velar and labial stops. Obstruents are apparently already fortis word finally:

"Im Auslaut steht zum Unterschied von den Reibelauten das Lenisphonem (*kàlb, tàg, flèisg*), bei dem Fortisallophone anzunehmen sind" (Penzl 1972:104).

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut (/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /χ/) vorkommt" (Penzl 1972:102).

Penzl does, however, talk about this type of syllable final fortition--one conditioned by gradations in sonority. For Otfrid at least, a fortition conditioned by consonantal sonority or lower is posited for labial and velar stops:

"Direkte Variation deutet im Auslaut bei Lippenlauten (*irstarb, irstarp*) und Gaumenlauten (*sang, sank* >Gesang<) auf eine Tendenz zur Aufhebung der Opposition, besonders nach Sonorlaut, wohl zu Gunsten der Fortis /p/ /k/, wenn wir

den Wechsel *-/b/-:-/p/* (*lambir, lamp*) und die Verteilung bei den Reibelauten in Betracht ziehen" (Penzl 1972:86).

Dental Lenition

Input

Syllable Final Fortition.

<d> and <t> merge after <n>. Syllable initially, they get written <d>. Syllable finally, they get written <t>:

/(d,t)/

Syllable	/vi(m,n)(d,t)+ət/
Initial	[finʂdət]
After	<findet>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg pres'
	I,65,18

Syllable	/va(m,n)(d,t)/
Final	[fant]
After	<fànt>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg past'
	I,222,6

Functions

If possible, one would ignore this spelling merger. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: lenis dental stops, fortis dental stops, all dental stops, all stops, all dental obstruents.

Possible phonological changes could be in: voice, aspiration, glottalization or fortition.

Possible phonological environments could be: 'after a dental nasal', 'after all nasals', 'after all sonorants'.

Voice, Aspiration or Glottalization

Without evidence to the contrary, one would want to be as vague as possible about the change this process effects. That would be in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. A scholar could then allow the process to mark an aspiration, voicing, devoicing, lenition or whatever. Unfortunately, *Only Phoneme Mergers* prevents Notker from marking any change that did not merge phonemes. Since obstruents are differentiated by fortition, only a fortition or lenition could merge phonemes.

Fortition

If the process must be a change in fortition, then in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*, one would want to leave the question open as to whether it was a lenition of /t/ after /n/, or a fortition of /d/ syllable finally. A phoneme merger, however, was already posited making obstruents fortis syllable finally after nasals. This allows either /t/ or /d/ to generate <t> in <fànt>. To also allow either /t/ or /d/ to generate <d> in <finden> then would require a lenition. A lenition is also perhaps the only way to account for the <d> from /t/, when a word boundary separates the stop from the nasal:

	/(d,t)/ Separated by Syllable Boundary from Nasal	/t/ Separated by Syllable and Word Boundary from Nasal
Syllable	/vin(d,t)+ət/	/mijn+tejl/
Initial	[finʂdət]	[mijnʂdejl]
After	<findet>	<mîn dèil>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg pres' I, 65, 18	'my part' Nps 16, 17

Lenition of /ʂt/ after /n/

A lenition of /t/ to [d] syllable initially would merge /t/ and /d/ to [d] in <finden>. It would also prevent the lenition from affecting syllable final dental in <fànt>. Syllable Final Fortition however, will already make the dental in <fànt> fortis. So Dental Lenition could be broadened then to lenite /t/ after /n/ everywhere. The phoneme merger would of course have to be ordered before Syllable Final Fortition.

It would be good to talk about ordering when we meet.

Lenition of /t/ or /(d,t)/ after /n/

A lenition of /t/ to [d] would also apply vacuously to /d/. According to *Broaden Phoneme Mergers* then, the process should be expanded to lenite all dental stops after /n/.

Lenition of Dental Stops after all Nasals

The lenition /*(d,t)*/ also seems to happen after other nasals. (ex: <rũmɔa> from underlying /ruwm+ta/. The spelling merger will be treated under Nasal Assimilation. If possible, one would however want to broaden the lenition, to lenite dental stops after all nasals. Unfortunately, that would be specifying a place feature in the input of a phoneme merger (dental), without also specifying that place feature in the phoneme merger's conditioning (after all nasals). That is of course in conflict with *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*.

Change your text of of course, fortunately and unfortunately

Lenition of all Stops after all Nasals

One could remedy this by taking out the place restriction on the input of the phoneme merger. All stops could lenite after all nasals. Unfortunately, this would conflict with *Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs*. Labial and velar stops contrast after nasals.

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/le(m,n)b+ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lem\$bər]	[gum\$pi\$tən]
After	<lèmber>	<gùmpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl'	'pond, acc sg'
	II, 486, 6	II, 211, 3
Syllable	/ži(m,n)g+ən/	/tsi(m,n)k+ən/
Initial	[žin\$gən]	[tsin\$kən]
After	<siŋgen>	<ciŋken>
Nasal	'sing, inf'	'prong, dat sg'
	I, 96, 16	I, 775, 5

Lenition of all Dental Obstruents after /n/

If the lenition cannot be broadened to the other stops, perhaps it can be broadened in another direction, to the other dentals. All dental obstruents, not just stops, could lenite after the dental nasal. Unfortunately, this lenition is not reflected with a spelling merger in dental fricatives after nasals:

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/u(m,n)žər/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)an/
Initial	[un\$žər]	[un\$tsan]
After	<ùnsər>	<ùnzən>
Nasal	'our, uninfl'	'until'
	I, 77, 7	I, 12, 24

Syllable	/u(m,n)ž/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)/
Final	[unš]	[unts]
After	<unš>	<unz>
Nasal	'us'	'until'
	II, 634, 1	I, 54, 30

✓ /ž/ and /s/, however, contrast in more than just fortition. A simple lenition then would not be marked in them, according to *Only Phoneme Mergers*. In addition however, a phoneme merger proposed later will put an epenthetic fortis stop between a nasal and a following fortis fricative. So a fortis fricative would never come after a nasal, as long as Epenthesis is ordered before Dental Lenition.

Lenition of all Dental Obstruents after Dental Sonorants

One could further broaden the phoneme merger, by having dental obstruents (lenite) after all dental sonorants, whether nasal or not. Unfortunately, /t/ and /d/ contrast after liquids:

	/d/	/t/
Syllable	/werd+ən/	/wort+o/
Initial	[weršdən]	[woršto]
After	<uuèrden>	<uuòrto>
Liquid	'become, inf'	'word, gen pl'
	I, 18, 13	I, 12, 6
Syllable	/ward/	/wort/
Final	[ward]	[wort]
After	<uuàrd>	<uuòrt>
Liquid	'become, 3rd sg past'	'word, nom sg'
	I, 5, 17	I, 502, 18

The lenition of all dental obstruents after dental sonorants would then entail specifying liquids as not dental, in conflict with *Posit as Little as Possible*.

Lenition of all Dental Obstruents after Dental Sonorants of like Continuancy

v? One could have the dental obstruent continuants (i.e. fricatives /ž≠s/) lenite to [ž≠z] after dental sonorant continuants (i.e. liquids /l,r/). Similarly, the dental obstruent non-continuants (i.e. stops /d≠t/) could lenite to [d] after the dental sonorant non-continuant (i.e. the nasal /n/). Intuitively, I prefer this phoneme merger to the lenition of all dental obstruents after

[n]. Unfortunately, this entails specifying /l/ and /r/ as dental, in conflict with *Posit as Little as Possible*.

Separate Phonemes

One could dispense with the lenition and fortition, and just posit /t/ in <fànt> and /d/ in <fìnden>. That is, however, the equivalent to positing two different phonemes in different declensions of the Modern German word for 'wheel'; <Rad> */raʌt/ and <Rades> /raʌd+əs/. It is also in conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*. This same function, *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*, would prevent positing either just /t/ or /d/, if /(d,t)/ could be posited, and the alternation <fìnden> <fànt> get generated through phoneme mergers.

So
what!

Output

Dental Lenition:

Dental obstruents lenite after the dental nasal, even across a syllable boundary.

Commentary

Jellinek

Clausing writes that Grimm was the first to differentiate the two dental stops in Notker (Clausing 1979:363). The <t> that does not alternate with <d> reflected Alemannic /t/, from Proto-Germanic */d/. Hoefler (Hoefler 1873:200), in a rebuttal to Grimm, attempted to show that there was only one dental stop. He published a list of examples where Alemannic */t/ was indeed written <d> after sonorants. The controversy was not answered until 23 years later by Jellinek. He pointed out that Notker's <t> does alternate with <d>, but only if syllable initial and preceded by a nasal:

"richtig formuliert hat das lautgesetz zu heissen: im innern des satztactes wird silbenanlautendes t zu d, wenn die vorhergehende silbe auf nasal ausgeht" (Jellinek 1897:86).

The examples he lists include ones with the consonants separated by word, and so syllable boundaries:

"èinen dag 65,25, in dæg 112,11" (Jellinek 1897:84).

He also has the lenition conditioned after all nasals:

"dass nach *-m* überhaupt nur *t* vorkommt (Boeth. 4 mal, Marc. Cap. 2 mal, Kat. 1 mal) ist gewis nur zufällig. wegen der Psalmen" (Jellinek 1897:87).

Penzl

Like Jellinek, Penzl would specify an underlying /t/, and restrict Dental Lenition from affecting syllable final dentals:

"Im Inlaut und öfter bei engem Anschluß nach auslautendem *-n* ist /t/ zu /d/ geworden (*lânt*, Gen. *lândes*)." (Penzl 1972:104).

Unlike Jellinek, Penzl only has the lenition conditioned after /n/, not all nasals.

Nasal Assimilation

Input

Dental Lenition.

<m> and <n> contrast before word final <f>:

Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
Final	[fimf]	[glampf]
After	<finf>	<gelàmff>
Nasal	'five' I, 66, 26	'suit, 3rd sg past' I, 556, 5

<n> however comes before an <f> from Germanic */f/, and <m> before an <f> from Germanic */p/. Technically, an <m> that alternates with <n> comes before an <f#> from Germanic */f/, while an <m> that alternates with <mp> or <mph> comes before an <f#> from Germanic */p/. A grapheme merger will be proposed later, merging [f] and [v] to <f> word finally. <m> and <n> then can graphologically contrast before the same graph <f>, yet phonologically be in complementary distribution before different phonemes /v/ and /f/. Other than before word final <f>, I am unable to contrast nasals before obstruent graphs. <m> comes before <b,p,f>, and <n> comes before <v,d,t,s,z,k,g,ch>:

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/le(m,n)b+ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lem\$bər]	[gum\$pi\$tən]
After	<lèmber>	<gùmpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl' II, 486, 6	'pond, acc sg' II, 211, 3

Syllable	/la(m,n)b/	No Example
Final	[lamp]	
After	<làmp>	
Nasal	'lamb, acc sg' II, 239, 9	

/(d,t)/

Syllable	/vi(m,n)(d,t)+ət/
Initial	[fin\$dət]
After	<findet>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg pres' I, 65, 18

Syllable	/va(m,n)(d,t)/
Final	[fant]
After	<fànt>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg past' I, 222, 6

	/g/	/k/
Syllable	/ži(m,n)g+ən/	/tsi(m,n)k+ən/
Initial	[žiŋ\$gən]	[tsiŋ\$kən]
After	<singen>	<cinken>
Nasal	'sing, inf' I, 96, 16	'prong, dat sg' I, 775, 5

Syllable	/ža(m,n)g/	No Example
Final	[žaŋk]	
After	<sàng>	
Nasal	'sing, 3rd sg past' I, 176, 14	

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)ve/	/g+li(m,n)(pf,f)+liχ+eΛro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	glim\$pfliχ _s eΛ\$ro]
After	<fìnuè>	<gelimflichêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl' I, 197, 29	'suited, fem dat sg' I, 781, 25

Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
Final	[fimf]	[glampf]
After	<fìnf>	<gelàm f>
Nasal	'five' I, 66, 26	'suit, 3rd sg past' I, 556, 5

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/u(m,n)žər/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)an/
Initial	[un\$žər]	[un\$tsan]
After	<ùnsər>	<ùnzan>
Nasal	'our, uninfl' I, 77, 7	'until' I, 12, 24

Syllable	/u(m,n)ž/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)/
Final	[unš]	[unts]
After	<ùnš>	<ùnz>

Nasal	'us' II, 634, 1	'until' I, 54, 30
	/h/	/χ/
Syllable Initial After Nasal	Only Found Across Morpheme Boundaries	/((ž, s) (d, t) a (m, n) (kχ, χ) +əž/ [(š, s) taŋk\$χəž] <stàanches> 'smell, gen sg' I, 708, 2
Syllable Final After Nasal	Not Found	/((ž, s) (d, t) a (m, n) (kχ, χ) / [(š, s) taŋk] <stàng> 'smell, nom sg' I, 291, 32

There is a sequence in dental preterites that can only be analyzed as underlying /m+t/. It is written as <md>.

/r+ə/	/n+ə/	/m+ə/
/ler+ən/ [ler, ən] <lèren> 'teach, inf' I, 46, 11	/ər+(kχ, χ) enn+ən/ [ər\$χen\$ən] <erchènenn> 'know, inf' II, 401, 8	/nemm+ən/ [nem\$mən] <nèmmen> 'name, inf' I, 107, 10
		/ruwm+ən/ [ruw\$mən] <rûmen> 'praise, inf' I, 28, 15
/r+t/	/n+t/	/m+t/
/ler+ta/ [ler\$ta] <lèrta> 'teach, 3rd sg pst' I, 101, 29	/ər+(kχ, χ) ann+ta/ [ər\$χan\$da] <erchànda> 'know, 3rd sg pst' II, 384, 4	/namm+ta/ [nan\$da] <nàmda> 'name, 3rd sg pst' I, 132, 10
		/ruwm+ta/ [ruwn\$da] <rûmda> 'praise, 3rd sg pst' I, 810, 22

That the <m> in <nàmda> and <rûmda> is /m/ can be shown by the infinitives <nèmmen> and <rûmen>. That the <d> in <nàmda> and <rûmda> is /t/ can be shown by <lèrta>, where the same dental preterite /ta/ is not (lenited) by [n]. That the <d> in <nàmda> and <rûmda> comes from Dental Lenition, can be shown by comparing the process to that in <erchènnen> and <erchànda>. Dental Lenition has already been posited after the dental nasal.

Functions

If possible, one would ignore these spelling mergers. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether these mergers were phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: the dental nasal, or all nasals.

Possible phonological changes could be in: assimilation in place.

Possible phonological environments could be: 'before a dental stop', 'before a dental obstruent', 'before all obstruents'.

Nasal Assimilation before /t/

Unfortunately, it looks like <nàmda> and <rûmda> must reflect an assimilation of /m/ to /n/ before /t/, even across syllable boundaries. Otherwise a preceding dental nasal could not lenite the dental through Dental Lenition. Lenition of [t] by [m] would of course violate *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*. If a scholar must be specific about the phonological change however, one would still try to be as vague as possible about the phonological environment. That would be in accordance with *Posit as Little as Possible*. An analyst could then allow the process to mark an assimilation of nasals to /t/, or to /t/ and some other obstruents, or to /t/ and all other obstruents.

Nasal Assimilation before all Obstruents

Unfortunately, nasals do not contrast before any obstruents. So *Broaden Phoneme Mergers* broadens the assimilation to occur before all obstruents. *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes* does the same. Nasal Assimilation before all obstruents allows /*(m,n)*/ to generate [ŋ] before [g] in <singen>, [n] before [d] in <finden>, and [m] before [b] in <lēmber>. The alternative would be to specify labial nasals before labial obstruents, dental nasals before dental ones, and either have a velar nasal phoneme, or specify either an /n/ or /m/ before velar obstruents. All of this would be in conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*.

Output

Nasal Assimilation:

Nasals assimilate in place to a following obstruent, even across a syllable boundary.

Commentary

Penzl does not comment on the lenition of /t/ to [d] after /m/. He does however, propose some nasal assimilation, at least before velars and /f/. For Notker:

"Bei den Nasalphonemen /n/ /m/ weisen die Folgentwicklung auf ein velares Allophon vor Gaumenlaut z.B. *dīng*(64), *lāngo*(144), Allophone in der Sprache der Gegenwart auf ein labiodentales Allophon des /m/ vor *f* (*chūmftig*, *sēmfte*)" (Penzl 1972:102).

For Old High German in general:

"/m/ before /f/ as in *fimf* may have had a labiodental allophone in Old High German since we find it in modern dialects. It is generally assumed that /n/ before velars as in *lang*, *danc*, *bringan* had the velar allophone [ŋ]." (Penzl 1968b:342).

Penzl does not address the merger of /m/ and /n/ to <n> before <f#> from Germanic */f/, but to <m> before <f#> from Germanic */p/. This is unfortunate, since any discussion of nasal assimilation can stumble on that graph alternation. It is also surprising, since the scholar has written an essay on nasals in Old High German (Penzl 1968b), and one on <f> in Old High German (Penzl 1964).

Perhaps he has Germanic */p/ shifted to /pf/ after nasals, since

he usually only discusses nasals before Germanic */f/:

"Zwischen Frühahd. und Spätahd. ist in den Denkmälern ein Ersatz von <mf> durch <nf> eingetreten. Isidors *fimf* steht Tatians *fimf finf, uinf*, Otfrids *finf*, Notkers *finf, uinf*, (in den Psalmen *funf*) gegenüber. Wir müssen annehmen, daß <m> wirklich das Phonem /m/, <n> wirklich /n/ bedeutet, also ein Phonemwandel, nicht bloß ein orthographische Veränderung vorliegt." (Penzl 1964:297).

Braune Grammar

The Braune Grammar does mention the merger <md> from underlying /m+t/:

"Auch nach *m* hat N *d*: *rûmda*" (Braune 1987:163 Anm 5).

The grammar also notes that <n> comes before <f> from Germanic */f/, but <m> before <f> from Germanic */p/:

"Während *m* vor ahd. *ph, pf, f* (=germ. *p* §131) in der Regel bleibt (z.B. *kempfo, kemfo*, nur ausnahmsweise *kenfo* T), zeigt das *m* vor germ. *f* im Ahd. die Neigung, in *n* überzugehen. Zunächst nur im Fränk, seit dem 9. Jh. Hierher gehören *fimf* '5', *zumft* (zu *zeman*), *kumft* (zu *queman*), *samft, semfti* 'sanft' u.a. Bei Is steht noch *m* (*fimf, chumft*), T schwankt (*fimf* und *finf* usw., Sievers §11), bei O aber ist *n* schon völlig durchgedrungen, also *finf, kunft, kunftig, gezunft* (aber stets *limphan* etc). Im Obd. halt sich *m* länger. Bis ins 11 Jh. ist *n* in obd. Quellen in der Minderheit (vgl. z.B. Kögel 59; *unsenftiu* Rd, Gl 1,284); selbst bei N steht meist *m* (neben *n*, bes. in Nps). Erst im Mhd. herrscht auch obd. *n*. Der Übergang des *m* in (labiodentales) *n* scheint darauf zu deuten, daß das früher bilabiale germ. *f* im Ahd. labiodental geworden war." (Braune 1987:123 Anm. 1).

So Germanic */f/ (Alemannic /v/) was once bilabial and had <m> written before it, but in Notker's day is becoming labiodental, and has <n> written before it. The same logic apparently does not hold for Germanic */p/ (Alemannic /f/), which in Notker's day is preceded by an <m>: e

"Die Meinung, daß germ. *f* labiodental, das neue aus *p* entstandene (*f, ff*) dagegen bilabial gewesen sei (Beitr 1, 168, Kögel 72), ist unerweislich und kaum berechtigt. Im Mhd. reimen auslautend beide *f* aufeinander" (Braune 1987:137 Anm. 1).

Epenthesis

Input

Syllable Initial Fortition.

Syllable Final Fortition.

Nasal Assimilation.

Assume that /F/ is any fortis fricative, /L/ its corresponding lenis fricative, and /N/ its corresponding nasal. Nasal Assimilation and Syllable Final Fortition then should merge any /NL\$/ and /NF\$/ to /NF\$/.

Since /h≠χ/ differ in more than just fortition, this process should not merge those phonemes. And anyway /h/, as a laryngeal, does not come after anything less than vocalic sonority in a syllable.

Since /ž≠s/ differ in more than just fortition, this process should not merge the phonemes.

The /v≠f/ contrast however is just fortition. Syllable Initial Fortition was enough to merge the labial fricatives, and so was marked in them:

	/+v/	/+f/
Syllable	/əɾ+var+ən/	No Example
Initial	[əɾ\$var,ən]	
After	<eruàren>	
Sonorant	'go, inf' I,394,7	
Syllable	/uwf+var+ən(d,t)o/	No Example
Initial	[uwf+far,ən\$do]	
After	<ûffàrendo>	
Obstruent	'go, uninfl pres part' II,216,26	
	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/tiAvəl/	/tiAf+o/
Initial	[tiA\$vəl]	[tiA\$fo]
After	<tîeuel>	<tîefo>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg' II,469,23	'deep, adv' I,208,23

Nevertheless, /Nv\$/ and /Nf\$/ are marked differently, even though both, through Nasal Assimilation and Syllable Final Fortition, should become [mf\$]:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	*/g+la(m,n)f/
Final	[fimf]	*[glamf]
After	<fìnf>	<gelàmf>
Nasal	'five'	'suit, 3rd sg past'
	I, 66, 26	I, 556, 5

Nasals before /v/ merge to <n>, while nasals before /f/ merge to <m>. This merger is also kept for syllable initial fricatives, where /(m,n)\$v/ and /(m,n)\$f/ get marked as <nv> and <mf> respectively:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v+e/	*/g+li(m,n)f+liχ+e^ro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	*[glim\$fliχ _s e^\$ro]
After	<fìnue>	<gelìmflichêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl'	'suited, fem dat sg'
	I, 197, 29	I, 781, 25

Functions

If possible, one would ignore this spelling merger. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: nasals, lenis labial fricatives, all lenis fricatives, all labial fricatives, all fricatives, or even zero.

Possible phonological changes could be in: assimilation in place for nasals, fortition or lenition for fricatives, or epenthesis for zero.

Possible phonological environments could be: 'before /v/', 'before /f/', 'after nasals', 'between a nasal and /f/', 'between a nasal and any fortis fricative', 'between a nasal and any fricative'.

No Assimilation of Nasals before /v/

One could ammend Nasal Assimilation so that it did not apply before the lenis labial fricative. An /n/ then would have to be specified in */vinv/, and not go through assimilation to give <finf>. Unfortunately, that would be in conflict with *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*.

Assimilation of Nasals before a /v≠f/ contrast in place

One could leave Nasal Assimilation unammended, and have nasals assimilate in place to all obstruents. Perhaps /v/ however, could be given another place feature. Nasals could then assimilate to /v/ differently than to /f/, and Notker mark that in <nv> and <mf>. Historically, scholars have talked about Germanic /f/ being bilabial, and Old High German /f/ being labialdental (Braune 1987:137 Anm.1). Unfortunately, this would conflict with the Anlautgesetz and *Only Phoneme Mergers*. The Anlautgesetz, a simple fortition, was enough to merge /f/ and /v/ to [f]:

	/+v/	/+f/
Syllable	/ə r +var+ən/	No Example
Initial	[ə r \$var,ən]	
After	<eruàren>	
Sonorant	'go, inf' I, 394, 7	
Syllable	/uw f +var+ən(d,t)o/	No Example
Initial	[uw f +far,ən\$do]	
After	<ûffàrendo>	
Obstruent	'go, uninfl pres part' II, 216, 26	
	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/ti v ə1/	/ti f +o/
Initial	[ti v \$və1]	[ti f \$fo]
After	<t v ieuel>	<t f iefo>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg' II, 469, 23	'deep, adv' I, 208, 23

If only phoneme mergers get marked, then /v≠f/ must only differ in fortition.

Fortition/Lenition of a Labial Fricative

One could also try to explain the spelling merger through some sort of lenition or fortition restricted to one labial fricative. I am not sure how to do this however, without violating *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place*.

Epenthesis between Nasal and /f/

One could explain the <nv≠mf> merger by having it mark an epenthetic [p] between the nasal and the labial fricative. The <nv≠mf> graph contrast would then reflect an [m\$ v≠m\$ pf] for syllable initial fricatives. The analysis might even be supported by an occasional spelling of <mf> as <mpf>.

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v+e/	*/g+li(m,n)f+liχ+eΛro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	[glim\$pfliχ _s eΛ\$ro]
After	<finue>	<gelimflichêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl' I, 197, 29	'suited, fem dat sg' I, 781, 25
		*/g+li(m,n)f+liχ+eΛro/ [glim\$pfliχ _s eΛ\$ro] <gelim mp flichêro> 'suited, fem dat sg' I, 775, 30

Because of Syllable Final Fortition, the contrast would be [mf≠mpf] syllable finally.

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	*/g+la(m,n)f/
Final	[fimf]	[glampf]
After	<finf>	<gelàm mp f>
Nasal	'five' I, 66, 26	'suit, 3rd sg past' I, 556, 5

Either /mf/ or /mpf/ to Generate [mpf]

If <mf> marks [mpf], then a scholar need not specify whether <gelimflichêro> came from /g+li(m,n)f+liχ+eΛro/ or /g+li(m,n)pf+liχ+eΛro/. That would be in accordance with *Posit*

as Little as Possible.

Only /mpf/ to Generate [mpf]

One could eliminate Epenthesis. [mpf] in [glim\$pfliχ_se^\$ro] could then just come from underlying /mpf/ in /g+limpf+liχ+e^ro/. Although that would eliminate a phoneme merger, it would require being more specific about an underlying form. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*.

Epenthesis before all Fortis Fricatives

In accordance with *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*, one could broaden Epenthesis to the dental and velar fortis fricatives too. Indeed, in the section on Velar Deletion, Epenthesis will be needed to account for the <g> in <stàng>.

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/u(m,n)žər/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)an/
Initial	[unšžər]	[unštsan]
After	<unser>	<unzan>
Nasal	'our, uninfl'	'until'
	I, 77, 7	I, 12, 24
Syllable	/u(m,n)ž/	/u(m,n)(ts,s)/
Final	[unš]	[unts]
After	<unš>	<unz>
Nasal	'us'	'until'
	II, 634, 1	I, 54, 30
	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	Only Found	/((ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)+əž/
Initial	Across Morpheme	[(š,s)taŋkšχəž]
After	Boundaries	<stanches>
Nasal		'smell, gen sg'
		I, 708, 2
Syllable	Not Found	/((ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)/
Final		[(š,s)taŋk]
After		<stàng>
Nasal		'smell, nom sg'
		I, 291, 32

Epenthesis before all Fricatives

One could further broaden the phoneme merger to apply to all fricatives, but that would eliminate the contrast just developed between / $(m,n)v$ / and / $(m,n)f$ /.

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
Final	*[fimpf]	[glampf]
After	<finf>	<gelàmƒ>
Nasal	'five'	'suit, 3rd sg past'
	I, 66, 26	I, 556, 5

Epenthesis before all Fortis Obstruents

One could further broaden the phoneme merger to take place before fortis stops (and so all fortis obstruents). So, for example, one analysis of the word <empty> in English could have an epenthetic [p] placed between the labial nasal and dental [t]:

/mt/
 /emti/
 [empʂti]
 <empty>

The /m/ and /t/ in /emti/ had of course different place features, the nasal labial, the stop dental. Nasal Assimilation was already posited for Notker. If it is ordered before Epenthesis, this sequence should not arise. Of course one can still broaden the phoneme merger to the stops, and so for example place an epenthetic [k] between the velars [ŋ] and [k] in:

	/g/	/k/
Syllable	/ʒi(m,n)g+ən/	/tsi(m,n)k+ən/
Initial	[ʒiŋʂgən]	*[tsiŋkʂkən]
After	<siŋgen>	<ciŋken>
Nasal	'sing, inf'	'prong, dat sg'
	I, 96, 16	I, 775, 5

The issue is trivial, but since my functions do not handle it well, it should be pointed out.

Output

Epenthesis:

An epenthetic fortis stop is placed between a nasal and a fortis fricative, even if they are separated by a syllable

boundary.

Commentary

I cannot find any scholar who talks about Epenthesis for Notker. Perhaps they get around this by positing affricates after nasals. An epenthetic stop is then more or less in the underlying form. So Penzl would posit a velar affricate instead of a fricative after nasals.

"Die velare Affrikata *kχ*...wahrscheinlich auch nach Nasal mit Zeichenüberschneidung (*dànche*), wenn ich den parallelen Auslautwechsel mit *g* richtig deute (*pòg, dàng*)." (Penzl 1972:103).

This affricate is reduced to a velar stop syllable finally:

"könnte *ch* das Zeichen der einfachen Affrikate sein, die im Auslaut bei Nasal als Verschlusslaut (*dàng*)...vertreten ist" (Penzl 1968a:146).

Velar Deletion

Input

Word finally, [h] and [χ] are both written <h>, a grapheme merger to be developed later.

Word finally, [g] and [k] are both written <g>, a grapheme merger to be developed later.

Nasal Assimilation.

Epenthesis.

Syllable Final Fortition.

/g/ and /χ/ contrast as <g> and <ch> syllable initially. Syllable finally after vowels and liquids, the contrast is retained as <g> and <h>:

	/g/	/χ/
Syllable	/wɪjg+e/	/buwχ+e/
Initial	[wɪj\$ge]	[buw\$χe]
After	<uuɪge>	<bûche>
Vowel	'battle, dat sg'	'belly, dat sg'
	I, 23, 1	II, 68, 24
Syllable	/wɪjg/	/buwχ/
Final	[wɪjg]	[buwχ]
After	<uuɪg>	<bûh>
Vowel	'battle, nom sg'	'belly, nom sg'
	II, 84, 2	II, 166, 15
Syllable	/burg+o/	/werχ+əž/
Initial	[bur\$go]	[wer\$χəž]
After	<bùrgo>	<uuèrches>
Liquid	'castle, gen pl'	'work, gen sg'
	I, 113, 18	I, 40, 12
Syllable	/burg/	/werχ/
Final	[burg]	[werχ]
After	<bùrg>	<uuèrh>
Liquid	'castle, nom sg'	'work, nom sg'
	I, 703, 23	I, 487, 15

Syllable finally after nasals and obstruents however, /g/ and /χ/

merge to <g>:

	/g/	/χ/
Syllable	/ži(m,n)g+ən/	/((ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)+əž/
Initial	[žiŋ\$gən]	[((š,s)taŋk\$χəž]
After	<siŋgen>	<stànches>
Nasal	'sing, inf'	'smell, gen sg'
	I, 96, 16	I, 708, 2
Syllable	/ža(m,n)g/	/((ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)/
Final	[žaŋk]	[((š,s)taŋk]
After	<sàng>	<stàng>
Nasal	'sing, 3rd sg past'	'smell, nom sg'
	I, 176, 14	I, 291, 32
Syllable	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)+ən/	/blikχ+əž/
Initial	[fi(š,s)\$kən]	[blik\$χəž]
After	<fi\$ken>	<blicches>
Obstruent	'fish, dat pl'	'glance, gen sg'
	I, 751, 23	I, 751, 28
Syllable	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)/	/blikχ/
Final	[fi(š,s)k]	[blik]
After	<fi\$g>	<bli\$g>
Obstruent	'fish, nom sg'	'glance, nom sg'
	I, 167, 28	I, 743, 23

Functions

If possible, one would ignore this spelling merger. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

I have something to say about such paragraphs

A Grapheme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Possible phonological inputs could be: velar fricatives, velar stop fricative sequences (affricates), velar stops.

Possible phonological changes could be in: deletion for velar obstruents.

Possible phonological environments could be: 'syllable finally after velar obstruent', 'between velar obstruent and a syllable boundary'.

Deletion of /χ/, in /kχš/

Word internally, [χ] is written <ch>. The <cch> graph can be integrated into this formula if the first <c> is taken as marking [k], and <ch> taken as marking [χ]:

	/g/	/χ/
Syllable	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)+ən/	/blikχ+əž/
Initial	[fi(š,s)škən]	[blikšχəž]
After	<fišken>	<blicches>
Obstruent	'fish, dat pl'	'glance, gen sg'
	I,751,23	I,751,28

Word finally, a grapheme merger will have [χ] marked as <h>. Another grapheme merger will have [k] marked as <g> word finally. In addition, Epenthesis should put a [k] between [ŋ] and [χ] in underlying / (m,n) (kχ,χ) /. This of course would entail marking /χ/ as fortis. Unless another rule is posited, Notker will mark word (and so syllable) final [kχ] with <g>--the same graph as the uses for word final [k] or [g]. I can only think of one phoneme merger to avoid that; Velar Deletion could merge [kχ] and [k] to [k] syllable finally. Notker could delete a velar obstruent when it came after another velar obstruent and before a syllable boundary.

	/g/	/χ/
Syllable	/wijg/	
Final	[wijg]	
After	<uuig>	
Vowel	'battle, nom sg'	
	II,84,2	
Syllable	/burg/	
Final	[burg]	
After	<bùrg>	
Liquid	'castle, nom sg'	
	I,703,23	
Syllable	/ža(m,n)g/	/((ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)/
Final	[žan̩k]	[((š,s)tan̩k]
After	<sàng>	<stàng>

Nasal	'sing, 3rd sg past' I,176,14	'smell, nom sg' I,291,32
Syllable	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)/	/blikχ/
Final	[fi(ž,s)k]	[blik]
After	<fiſg>	<bliſg>
Obstruent	'fish, nom sg' I,167,28	'glance, nom sg' I,743,23

Deletion of /χ/, after a Velar Obstruent and before a Syllable Boundary

Since [χ] does not come after [g] or [k] syllable finally, the phoneme merger could be broadened. Syllable final [χ] could delete after any velar obstruent.

Deletion of a Velar Obstruent after a Velar Obstruent and before a Syllable Boundary

Since [g] or [k] does not come after velar obstruents syllable finally, the phoneme merger could be broadened. Any syllable final velar obstruents could delete after any velar obstruent.

Deletion of a Velar Obstruent between a Velar Obstruent and a Syllable Boundary

Syllable initially, I am unable to contrast a three-way [k≠χ≠kχ] contrast between fortis velar obstruents. Velar deletion then could be broadened to that environment too. As [kχ\$] reduces to [k\$], so could [\$kχ] reduce to [\$χ]. In each case, a velar obstruent is deleted if in between another velar obstruent and a syllable boundary. If the phoneme merger can be so broadened, then according to *Broaden Phoneme Mergers* it should be:

	/h/	/(kχ,χ)/
Syllable	Not Found	/(kχ,χ)i(m,n)(d,t)/
Internal		[χint]
After		<chint>
Obstruent		'child, nom sg' I,62,15

Deletion of Any Obstruent between Another of the Same Place and a Syllable Boundary

If possible, one would like to broaden Velar Deletion to all obstruents. Unfortunately, that would eliminate contrasts in the labials and dentals. Here fortis obstruents keep a three-way

contrast at syllable boundaries. So, for example, [p≠f≠pf] contrast in:

	/v/		/f/
Syllable	/hov/		/ti^f/
Final	[hof]		[ti^\$f]
After	<hòf>		<tief>
Vowel	'court, nom sg'		'deep, uninfl'
	I, 736, 26		II, 389, 1

Syllable	No Example		/(kχ,χ)opf/
Final			[χopf]
After			<chòpf>
Obstruent			'head, nom sg'
			I, 765, 6

[t≠s≠ts] contrast in:

	/ž/		/s/
Syllable	/muwž/		/hi^s/
Final	[muwž]		[hi^s]
After	<mûs>		<hîez>
Vowel	'mouse, acc sg'		'call, 3rd sg past'
	II, 438, 13		I, 5, 16

Syllable	No Example		/(ž,s)(g,k)ats/
Final			[(ž,s)kats]
After			<scàz>
Obstruent			'treasure, nom sg'
			I, 76, 2

Phonemes instead of Phoneme Mergers

[\$χ] need not be generated by phoneme merger from /\$(kχ,χ)/. One could just posit /χ/ in:

	/h/		/χ/
Syllable	Not Found		*/χi(m,n)(d,t)/
Internal			[χint]
After			<chìnt>
Obstruent			'child, nom sg'
			I, 62, 15

A scholar could avoid [\$kχ] without having to expand Velar Deletion to include syllable initial affricates. Nevertheless

this would mean being more specific about what phonemes were in a morpheme, when a phoneme merger could allow one to be less specific. That would conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*. Not expanding the phoneme merger when it could be would also conflict with *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*.

Output

Velar Deletion:

A velar obstruent deletes, when in between another velar obstruent and a syllable boundary.

Commentary

Syllable Final / (kχ, χ) /

Penzl specifies an affricate phoneme, that gets reduced syllable finally to a fricative after liquids, but to a stop after vowels or nasals:

"Die Orthographie deutet bei *cch* auf eine geminierte Affrikate [kχ], die im Auslaut zu einem Verschußlaut (*pòg*) geworden ist, aber vor Konsonant zu einer Spirans wurde (*zùhta*). Nach Konsonant könnte *ch* das Zeichen der einfachen Affrikate sein, die im Auslaut bei Nasal als Verschußlaut (*dàng*), bei Liquida als Spirans (*uuèrh*, *scàlh*) vertreten ist" (Penzl 1968a:146).

The Braune grammar does not posit a phoneme, but seems to reflect this (Braune 1987:144 Anm. 5).

Syllable Initial / (kχ, χ) /

As mentioned in the introduction, Penzl's analysis of word initial <ch> changed from 1968 to 1972:

"*ch* im Anlaut in *chùning* 'König', *chràft* 'Kraft', *chòmen* 'kommen', *chlèine* 'klein' auch als Affrikate [kχ] bestimmt werden könnte. Auf Grund der modernen Dialektverhältnisse wäre die Spirans [χ] im Anlaut durchaus möglich. Der erwähnte paradigmatische Wechsel mit *g* spricht aber dafür, daß *ch* auch das Zeichen für die Affrikate sein kann. R. Pestalozzi nahm für *ch* im Anlaut den Wert eines stark aspirierten Verschußlautes an." (Penzl 1968a:146).

"Ich sehe im *ch* des Anlauts (*chùninga*, *chèiser*) die Spirans

/χ/" (Penzl 1972:103).

The Braune grammar allows for doubt :

"*k, c (qu)* statt *ch* ist im älteren Obd. weit verbreitet. Man wird darin eine ungenaue Bezeichnung der Affrikata sehen müssen" (Braune 1987:144 Anm.2).

"Für den Anlaut (*chint, chuning* etc.) ist aus der Schreibung mit Sicherheit nichts zu beweisen" (Braune 1987:144 Anm. 5).

Word Final <g>

Input

Syllable Internal Fortition.

Word finally, <g> and <k> do not contrast, but only <g> is written:

	/g/	/k/
Syllable	/wijg+e/	/gowkə1+e/
Initial	[wij\$ge]	[cow\$kə1,e]
After	<uuige>	<còukele>
Vowel	'battle, dat sg'	'trickery, dat sg'
	I, 23, 1	II, 246, 224
Syllable	/wijg/	/rok/
Final	[wijg]	[rok]
After	<uuig>	<rògh>
Vowel	'battle, nom sg'	'robe, nom sg.'
	II, 84, 2	I, 523, 24
Syllable	/burg+o/	/furk+ən/
Initial	[bur\$go]	[fur\$kən]
After	<bùrgo>	<fùrkun>
Liquid	'castle, gen pl'	'trident, acc sg'
	I, 113, 18	I, 742, 3
Syllable	/burg/	No Example
Final	[burg]	
After	<bùrg>	
Liquid	'castle, nom sg'	
	I, 703, 23	
Syllable	/ži(m,n)g+ən/	/tsi(m,n)k+ən/
Initial	[žin\$gən]	[tsin\$kən]
After	<singen>	<cinken>
Nasal	'sing, inf'	'prong, dat sg'
	I, 96, 16	I, 775, 5
Syllable	/ža(m,n)g/	No Example
Final	[žan\$g]	
After	<sàng>	
Nasal	'sing, 3rd sg past'	

I, 176, 14

Syllable /vi(ž,s)(g,k)+ən/
 Initial [fi(š,s)škən]
 After <fìsken>
 Obstruent 'fish, dat pl'
 I, 751, 23

Syllable /vi(ž,s)(g,k)/
 Final [fi(š,s)k]
 After <fìsg>
 Obstruent 'fish, nom sg'
 I, 167, 28

/g/

/χ/

Syllable /ži(m,n)g+ən/
 Initial [žiŋšgən]
 After <siŋgen>
 Nasal 'sing, inf'
 I, 96, 16

/(ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)+əž/
 [(š,s)taŋkšχəž]
 <stànches>
 'smell, gen sg'
 I, 708, 2

Syllable /ža(m,n)g/
 Final [žaŋk]
 After <sàng>
 Nasal 'sing, 3rd sg past'
 I, 176, 14

/(ž,s)(d,t)a(m,n)(kχ,χ)/
 [(š,s)taŋk]
 <stàng>
 'smell, nom sg'
 I, 291, 32

Syllable /vi(ž,s)(g,k)+ən/
 Initial [fi(š,s)škən]
 After <fìsken>
 Obstruent 'fish, dat pl'
 I, 751, 23

/blikχ+əž/
 [blikšχəž]
 <blicches>
 'glance, gen sg'
 I, 751, 28

Syllable /vi(ž,s)(g,k)/
 Final [fi(š,s)k]
 After <fìsg>
 Obstruent 'fish, nom sg'
 I, 167, 28

/blikχ/
 [blik]
 <bliḡ>
 'glance, nom sg'
 I, 743, 23

Functions

If possible, one would ignore the this spelling merger. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling*

Mergers.

Phoneme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this spelling merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

If one accepts Syllable Internal Fortition, then the velar stop in <fìsg> must be fortis. That <k> and <g> merge to <g> in <fìsg> (dat pl <fìsken>) cannot, I think, be explained phonologically. Even if it could, such an explanation should probably be linked to why <g> is written in <stàng> (gen sg <stànches>).

Grapheme Merger

A grapheme merger could have both [k] and [g] spelled <g> word finally. Of course, such a merger would have to pass *Only Posit Natural Grapheme Mergers*.

Latin did not have <k> for [k] word finally. So a grapheme merger restricting <k> from occurring there would not be unnatural. Classical Latin did however have <c> for [k] word finally (ex: <hic, haec, hoc>). However by Medieval Latin /k/ is palatizing in certain environments. The Braune Grammar has these palatized stops reflected in German loanwords for that era:

"In anderen Lehnwörtern dagegen vertritt das ahd. z (c) lat. c vor e, i, wie zins (lat. census), kruzi, cruci (lat. crucem), dēcemo, dēzemo (lat. decima 163 A. 8)" (Braune 1987:159 Anm 1).

I of course do not know whether Notker's Latin had syllable final /k/ palatized. If so, then the source writing system for Notker would not have <c> or <k> for [k] word finally, and a grapheme merger restricting a scribe to use <g> for [k] would not be unnatural. <c> is occasionally, although rarely, used by other Old High German scribes to mark the affricate <ts> word finally:

"sprincuurc, scelliuurc (d.i. wurz) G13,513" (Braune 1987:159 Anm 2).

Output

Word Final <g>:
 [g] and [k] are both written <g> word finally.

Commentary

Braune Grammar

The Braune grammar cites examples of <g> marking [k] or [g] word finally (Braune 1987:177).

<g> ist im Ahd. 1. die gewöhnliche Entsprechung des germ.-got. g, und zwar regelmäßig im Fränkischen (*gēban, ouga, tag*); aber auch überwiegend im Oberdeutschen...nicht selten für k in der Verbindung sk, besonders in-und auslautend (*asga, fisg*)" (Braune 1987:177).

Penzl

At first glance, Penzl seems to confirm a grapheme merger:

"sg im Auslaut wie bei *fisg, flëisg* stimmt mit der sonstigen Schreibung des velaren Verschlußlautes überrein" (Penzl 1968a:149).

However, for the labial and velar stops:

"Es besteht keine phonemische Opposition zwischen Lenis und Fortis im Auslaut" (Penzl 1968a:149).

Since [g] and [k] would both become [k] word finally, Penzl would not need a grapheme merger of [k\$#] and [g\$#] to <g#>.

Word Final <f>

Input

Word finally, /v/ and /f/ are both written <f>:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/tiʌvə1/	/uwfən/
Initial	[tiʌ\$və1]	[uw\$fən]
After	<tʰiue1>	<ûfen>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg'	'on'
	II, 469, 23	I, 75, 15
Syllable	/hov/	/g+traf/
Final	[hof]	[gə\$traf]
After	<hòf>	<getràf>
Vowel	'court, nom sg'	'meet, 3rd sg past'
	I, 736, 26	II, 215, 27
Syllable	/wolv+a/	/helf+ən/
Initial	[wol\$va]	[hel\$fən]
After	<uuòlua>	<hèlfen>
Liquid	'wolf, nom pl'	'help, inf'
	II, 238, 1	I, 265, 22
Syllable	/wolv/	/half/
Final	[wolv]	[half]
After	<uuòlf>	<hàlf>
Liquid	'wolf, nom sg'	'help, 3rd sg past'
	II, 345, 2	II, 95, 6
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v+e/	/g+li(m,n)(pf,f)+liχ+e^ro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	[glim\$pfliχ,e^\$ro]
After	<finue>	<gelimflichêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl'	'suited, fem dat sg'
	I, 197, 29	I, 781, 25
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
Final	[fimf]	[glampf]
After	<finf>	<gelàm f>
Nasal	'five'	'suit, 3rd sg past'
	I, 66, 26	I, 556, 5
Syllable	No Example	/opfər/

Initial	[op\$fər]
After	<òpfer>
Obstruent	'sacrifice, nom sg'
	I, 75, 19

Syllable	No Example	/(kχ, χ)opf/
Final		[χopf]
After		<chòpf>
Obstruent		'head, nom sg'
		I, 765, 6

Functions

If possible, one would ignore the this spelling merger. After all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

Phoneme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this spelling merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Separate Phonemes

One could posit separate phonemes in different declensions of 'wolf', a lenis /v/ in the plural /wolv+a/, and a fortis /f/ in the singular /wolf/:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/wolv+a/	/helf+ən/
Initial	[wol\$va]	[hel\$fən]
After	<uuòlua>	<hèlfen>
Liquid	'wolf, nom pl'	'help, inf'
	II, 238, 1	I, 265, 22
	*/f/	/f/
Syllable	*/wolf/	/half/
Final	*[wolf]	[half]
After	<uuòlf>	<hàlf>
Liquid	'wolf, nom sg'	'help, 3rd sg past'

II,345,2

II,95,6

This is the approach of Penzl and Simmler, and I think the bulk of all Old High German scholarship on the Konsonantenschwächung. The analysis however, is identical to positing different dental stop phonemes in Modern German <Rad> and <Rades>, */raʌt/ and /raʌd+əs/.

In addition, there is merger in preceding graphs to explain. A nasal is written <n> before <f> from Germanic */f/ (ex: <fīnf>), but <m> before <f> from Germanic */p/ (ex: <gelāmf>). This is difficult to explain if both words end in the same phoneme /f/.

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v+e/	*/g+li(m,n)f+liχ+eʌro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	[glim\$pfliχ ₅ eʌ\$ro]
After	<fīnue>	<gelīmflīchêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl'	'suited, fem dat sg'
	I,197,29	I,781,25

	*/f/	/f/
Syllable	*/vi(m,n)f/	*/g+la(m,n)f/
Final	*/[fimpf]	[glāmpf]
After	<fīnf>	<gelāmf>
Nasal	'five'	'suit, 3rd sg past'
	I,66,26	I,556,5

One can get around this of course by positing an affricate /pf/ in /g+la(m,n)pf/, and getting rid of Epenthesis. Positing /vi(m,n)v+e/ and */vi(m,n)f/ however, is still identical to positing different dental stop phonemes in Modern German <Rad> and <Rades>, */raʌt/ and /raʌd+əs/.

	/v/	*/pf/
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v+e/	*/g+li(m,n)pf+liχ+eʌro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	[glim\$pfliχ ₅ eʌ\$ro]
After	<fīnue>	<gelīmflīchêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl'	'suited, fem dat sg'
	I,197,29	I,781,25

	*/f/	*/pf/
Syllable	*/vi(m,n)f/	*/g+la(m,n)pf/
Final	*/[fimpf]	[glāmpf]
After	<fīnf>	<gelāmf>

Nasal	'five' I, 66, 26	'suit, 3rd sg past' I, 556, 5
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Fortition of /v/ Syllable Finally

One could posit the same /v/ phoneme in all declensions of 'wolf', /wol υ +a/ and /wol υ /. A syllable final fortition phoneme merger could then make the /v/ fortis in [wolf], but leave it lenis in [wol $\$$ va]. Of course such a process would have to be a fortition. A devoicing or aspiration would not merge phonemes, and so not get marked according to *Only Phoneme Mergers*. A lenition would not make sense syllable finally, and so be conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/wol υ +a/	/helf+ən/
Initial	[wol $\$$ va]	[hel $\$$ fən]
After	<uuòlua>	<hèlfen>
Liquid	'wolf, nom pl' II, 238, 1	'help, inf' I, 265, 22
Syllable	/wol υ /	/half/
Final	*[wolf]	[half]
After	<uuòlf>	<hàlf>
Liquid	'wolf, nom sg' II, 345, 2	'help, 3rd sg past' II, 95, 6

Fortition of all Fricatives Syllable Finally

At first glance, it seems *Do Not Restrict Input by Place Unless Conditioned by Place* would prevent this. Although the labial fricatives are not written with different graphs word finally, the dentals are:

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/ti \wedge v+əɪ/	/ti \wedge f+o/
Final	[ti \wedge $\$$ vəɪ]	[ti \wedge $\$$ f+o]
After	<tîeuel>	<tîefo>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg' II, 469, 23	'deep, adv ' I, 208, 23
Syllable	/hov/	/ti \wedge f/
Final	*[hof]	[ti \wedge $\$$ f]
After	<hòf>	<tîef>
Vowel	'court, nom sg' I, 736, 26	'deep, uninfl' II, 389, 1

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/muwže/	/hejsən/
Initial	[muwʒe]	[hejʒsən]
After	<mŭse>	<hèizen>
Vowel	'mouse, nom pl'	'call, inf'
	II, 488, 13	I, 37, 10
Syllable	/muwž/	/hiʌs/
Final	*[muws]	[hiʌs]
After	*<mŭz>	<hîez>
Vowel	'mouse, acc sg'	'call, 3rd sg past'
	II, 438, 13	I, 5, 16

This fortition would have to be restricted from dental fricatives. However, /ž≠s/ (and /h≠χ/ for that matter) differ in more than fortition. A syllable final fortition for fricatives then would not merge those phonemes, allowing Notker to still write them differently:

Syllable	/muwž/	/hiʌs/
Final	*[muwʒ]	[hiʌs]
After	<mŭs>	<hîez>
Vowel	'mouse, acc sg'	'call, 3rd sg past'
	II, 438, 13	I, 5, 16

Broaden Phoneme Mergers

If possible, one would like to broaden this phoneme merger to include the stops too. The phoneme merger would then be the same as in Middle High and Modern German. Unfortunately, a contrast in the dental stops would prevent this:

	/d/	/t/
Syllable	/toʌd+ɛž/	/taʌt+ɛn/
Initial	[toʌʒdɛž]	[taʌʒtɛn]
After	<tôdes>	<tâten>
Vowel	'death, gen sg'	'do, 3rd pl past'
	I, 118, 15	I, 11, 27
Syllable	/toʌd/	/tuʌt/
Final	[toʌd]	[tuʌt]
After	<tôd>	<tûot>
Vowel	'death, nom sg'	'do, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 8, 8	I, 9, 26

In addition, syllable final fortition for all obstruents after

nasals was already proposed to explain the <b#p, d#t> alternations in:

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/le(m,n)b+ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lem\$bəɾ]	[gum\$pi\$tən]
After	<ləmber>	<gumpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl' II, 486, 6	'pond, acc sg' II, 21, 3

	/la(m,n)b/	No Example
Final	[lamp]	
After	<ləmp>	
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl' II, 239, 9	

/(d,t)/

Syllable	/vi(m,n)(d,t)+ət/
Initial	[fin\$dət]
After	<findet>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg pres' I, 65, 18

Syllable	/va(m,n)(d,t)/
Final	[fant]
After	<fànt>
Nasal	'find, 3rd sg past' I, 222, 6

The fortition, if amended to generate [hof] and [wolf] from /hov/ and /wolv/, would broaden in application. Unfortunately, that would also complicate the phoneme merger, something prevented by *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*:

*Obstruent Syllable Final Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable finally, when preceded by nasal sonority or lower. In addition, fricatives become fortis syllable finally, regardless of the sonority of a preceding phoneme.

An honest question would be why not accept the fortition of syllable final fricatives. Then the fortition of all obstruents after nasals could be thrown out as a complication. The <d#t> and <b#p> alternations after nasals could then be explained otherwise.

By limiting <finden> to an underlying /t/ in */fint+ən/, the <t> in <fànt> could be explained. That would however conflict with *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Phonemes*. In addition, under this scenario, Dental Lenition would have to be restricted to affecting only dentals followed by another sonorant. That would conflict with *Broaden Phoneme Mergers*.

To explain the labials without a fortition would require either a lenition or a grapheme merger. A lenition would wipe out the contrast in <lèmbèr> and <gùmpiten>, and so conflict with *Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs*. Going the other way, the <p> in <làmp> could be derived graphologically from *[lamb]. Of course such a grapheme merger would have to be justified by *Natural Grapheme Mergers*. Would a restriction on word final <mb> reflect Latin spelling patterns?

Intuitively, I would rather limit a fortition by gradations on sonority in the environment, than by the continuancy of an obstruent in the input. A fortition conditioned by nasal sonority or less seems preferable to one that only affected fricatives. This was however not laid out as a function.

Yes!

Natural Grapheme Mergers

Word initially and internally, <u> occurs as a glide in Classical Latin, or a fricative in Medieval Latin. Our modern dictionaries transcribe it as <v> (ex: <vinum> 'wine, nom sg', <avis> 'bird, nom sg'). Word finally, <u> can only mark a vowel (ex: <manu> 'hand, dat sg'). Given this, could Notker have really marked [wolv] 'wolf, nom sg' as *<uuòlu>? A grapheme merger would then be natural if it restricted <u> from marking a fricative word finally, and instead wrote both [v] and [f] there as <f>.

Output

Word Final <f>:

[v] and [f] are both written <f> word finally.

Commentary

Moulton

In his most recent essay, Moulton posits only one labial fricative /f/. Word finally, it is fortis:

"Auslautend war er kurz und fortis: kurz weil niemals -ff-geschrieben, fortis weil niemals -u geschrieben." (Moulton 1987:79).

Since there is only one labial fricative, there is no need for a grapheme merger; [f\$#] is written <f#>.

Penzl

Penzl's analysis is phonologically different from Moulton's, but graphologically similar. /v/ and /f/ are posited as separate fricative phonemes. Word finally however, only [f] (from /f/) appears:

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut(/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /χ/) vorkommt." (Penzl 1972:102).

Since he only has one velar fricative word finally, he too would not need a grapheme merger. In a paper devoted to Old High German /f/ he confirms this:

"Also stehen im Ahd. im Inlaut zwei historische f-Laute im Gegensatz, von denen nur einer im Anlaut vorkommt und im Auslaut kein orthographischer Unterschied gemacht wird" (Penzl 1964:291).

"Wir können im Ahd. beobachten, daß auslautendes <f> in Morphemen zweierlei Wechsel zeigt, entweder mit inlautend <v> oder mit inlautend <ff>: z B. *hof*, Dat. *hove*, *fimf*, *finvi*, *wolf*, Gen. *wolves* und *scif*, Gen. *sciffes*, *scuof* und *giscafan*. Eine innere Rekonstruktion aus diesem Wechsel ergäbe ein früheres auslautendes *f in Opposition zu auslautendem *ff. Die Auslautstellung erwies sich aus dem Wechsel eindeutig als entscheidend für den Zusammenfall im Vorahd., also einer der historisch belegten unmittelbar vorhergehenden Stufe." (Penzl 1964:294).

Simmler

Simmler analyzed three ninthth century Franconian manuscripts for insight into the Second Sound Shift. In each manuscript, he establishes phonemes word initially, internally and finally. I include him, because his work is the most comprehensive (about 900 pages) and recent (1981) analysis I can find for Old High German manuscripts. Notker and Old Franconian certainly differed. Simmler is perhaps worth citing however in the two grapheme mergers I reference him.

Otfrid's Evangelienbuch Codexes:

Word finally, Simmler only posits /f/. The examples he cites

include those from Germanic */p/ (ex: <slaf> 'sleep, nom sg') and Germanic */f/ (ex: <zuelif> 'twelve, uninfl') (Simmler 1981:189). He must then have these falling together before Otfrid.

Codex Leipzig Rep. II.6:

Word finally, Simmler cannot establish word final /f/ through minimal pairs, but needs diachronic evidence. In any case, /f/ is not contrasted with a second, word final, labial fricative /v/. (Simmler 1981:481-486)

Codex Köln Dombibliothek CVIII:

Here too, Simmler confesses that:

"keine Glossen tradiert sind, deren Graphe ein /f/ repräsentieren könnten" (Simmler 1981:633).

Word final /f/ might be confirmed through diachronic evidence though. In any case however, /f/ is not contrasted with a second, word final, labial fricative /v/.

So in all three codexes, a grapheme merger would not be needed to mark [v\$#] and [f\$#] as <f#>.

Word Final <h>

Input

Word finally, /h/ and /χ/ are both written <h>:

	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	/ru(w,^)h+ən/	/buwχ+e/
Initial	[ruh _s ən]	[buw\$χe]
After	<rùhon>	<bûche>
Vowel	'raw, gen pl masc wk' I, 167, 27	'belly, dat sg' II, 68, 24
Syllable	/ru(w,^)h/	/buwχ/
Final	[ru^h]	[buwχ]
After	<rûoh>	<bûh>
Vowel	'raw, uninfl' I, 167, 28	'belly, nom sg' II, 166, 15
Syllable	Only Found	/werχ+əž/
Initial	Across Morpheme	[wer\$χəž]
After	Boundaries	<uuèrches>
Liquid		'work, gen sg' I, 40, 12
Syllable	Not Found	/werχ/
Final		[werχ]
After		<uuèrh>
Liquid		'work, nom sg' I, 487, 15

The pattern however is not as strict as word final <f> for /v/.
/χ/ is often written <ch> word finally, especially in the Psalms.

	/χ/
Syllable	/buwχ/
Final	*[puwχ]
After	<pûch>
Vowel	'belly, nom sg' II, 166, 16

Functions

If possible, one would ignore the this spelling merger. After

all, that would be in line with *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, that would conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*.

Phoneme Merger

Ideally, one would not specify whether this merger was phonologically or graphologically conditioned. That would be in the spirit of *Posit as Little as Possible*. Unfortunately, according to *Prefer Phoneme Mergers over Grapheme Mergers*, an analyst should try first to explain the spelling merger as phonologically conditioned.

Separate Phonemes

One could posit separate phonemes in different declensions of 'raw', a laryngeal /h/ in the /ru(w,^)h+ən/, and a fortis /χ/ in /ru^χ/:

	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	/ru(w,^)h+ən/	/buwχ+e/
Initial	[ruh _h ən]	[buw _h χe]
After	<rûhon>	<bûche>
Vowel	'raw, gen pl masc wk' I,167,27	'belly, dat sg' II,68,24
Syllable	*/ru(w,^)χ/	/buwχ/
Final	*[ru^χ]	[buwχ]
After	<rûoh>	<bûh>
Vowel	'raw, uninfl' I,167,28	'belly, nom sg' II,166,15

As with the labial fricatives, this is the approach of Penzl and Simmler, and I think the bulk of all Old High German scholarship on the Konsonantenschwächung. And as with the labial fricatives, this is identical to positing different phonemes in different declensions of the Modern German word for 'wheel'; <Rad> */ra^t/ and <Rades> /ra^d+əs/.

In addition, as with the labials, there is merger in preceding graphs to explain. The /χ/ in */ru(w,^)χ/ *[ru^χ] corresponds to a lowered non-syllabic high vowel, while the /χ/ in /buwχ/ [buwχ] does not.

Fortition of /h/ Syllable Finally

One could posit the same /h/ phoneme in all declensions of 'raw', /ru(w,ʌ)hən/ and /ru(w,ʌ)h/. Syllable Final Fortition could then make the /h/ fortis in *[ruʌχ], but leave it lenis in [ruh_sən]. Of course such a process would have to be a fortition. A devoicing or aspiration would not merge phonemes, and so not get marked according to *Only Phoneme Mergers*. A lenition would not make sense if syllable final, and so conflict with *Relevant Spelling Mergers*:

	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	/ru(w,ʌ)h+ən/	/buwχ+e/
Initial	[ruh _s ən]	[buw\$χe]
After	<rūhon>	<būche>
Vowel	'raw, gen pl masc wk' I,167,27	'belly, dat sg' II,68,24
Syllable	/ru(w,ʌ)h/	/buwχ/
Final	*[ruʌχ]	[buwχ]
After	<rūoh>	<būh>
Vowel	'raw, uninfl' I,167,28	'belly, nom sg' II,166,15

Technically, since /h/ is a laryngeal, such a syllable final fortition would also have to change the laryngeal to an obstruent. Unfortunately, a fortition to explain word final <h> would run into the same difficulties that such a phoneme merger did for word final <f>. The phoneme merger will complicate the already existing fortition for all obstruents after nasal sonority or less.

Natural Grapheme Mergers

<ch> does not occur word finally in Latin, so a grapheme merger restricting it from that position would not be unnatural.

Output

Word Final <h>:

[h] and [χ] are both written <h> word finally.

Commentary

Moulton

It would appear that Moulton agrees with this grapheme merger, both [h] and [χ] get written as <h>:

"Wieso gebrauchten die althochdeutschen Schreiber denselben Buchstaben *h* für zwei so verschiedene Laute wie den Hauchlaut [h] und den velaren Frikativ [x]? Die Antwort auf diese Frage ist wohl sehr einfach: für [h] war *h* das gegebene Symbol, und für [x] lieferte das lateinische Alphabet kein besseres Symbol (Moulton 1987:80).

The only difference is that he derives [h] and [χ] from the same phoneme:

"Der Frikativ /h~x/, das heißt teils Hauchlaut, teils velarer Frikativ" (Moulton 1987:79).

Only the fortis allophone [χ] comes syllable finally:

"Parallel zum labialen Frikativ dürfen wir wohl auch hier annehmen, daß dieses Phonem anlautend (KV-) und inlautend einfach (-VKV-) lenis, aber inlautend geminiert (-VKKV-) und auslautend (-VK-) fortis war" (Moulton 1987:79).

Since then only [χ] comes word finally, he would not need a grapheme merger of word final [h] and [χ] to <h>.

Penzl

Penzl's analysis is phonologically different from Moulton's, but graphologically similar. /h/ and /χ/ are posited as separate fricative phonemes. Word finally however, only [χ] (from /χ/) appears:

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut (/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /χ/) vorkommt." (Penzl 1972:102).

Since he only has one velar fricative word finally, he too would not need a grapheme merger.

Simmler

In all three manuscripts, Simmler has /h/ already fallen together with /χ/.

For Otfrid's Evangelienbuch Codexes:

"germ. k und germ. h in finaler postvokalischer Position in der Sprache Otfrids zu einem Phonem /x/ zusammengefallen

sind" (Simmler 1981:98).

"Das Fehlen des /h/ in finaler Position wird im noch aufzustellenden konsonantischen Phonemsystem der Sprache Otfrids durch ein leeres Dreieck signalisiert" (Simmler 1981:209).

For the Codex Leipzig Rep. II.6:

"der Zusammenfall der Reflexe des germ. k und h in finaler postvokalischer Position zum /x/" (Simmler 1981:492).

"Das /h/ kann in absoluter finaler Position im Codex Leipzig Rep. II.6 und in den anderen mittelfränkischen Handschriften nicht nachgewiesen werden." (Simmler 1981:496).

For the Codex Köln Dombibliothek CVIII:

"Das /x/ ist...in absoluter finaler Position nicht festzustellen, weil aus Gründen der lexematischen Überlieferung keine Glossen vorkommen, welche /x/ in dieser Distribution zeigen konnten...Beim /x/ führte der Vergleich zum Codex Leipzig Rep. II.6 dazu, es auch für den Codex Köln Dombibliothek CVIII anzusetzen. Eine solche Schlußfolgerung ist beim /h/ nicht möglich, weil im Codex Leipzig Rep. II.6 unter diachronem Aspekt ein Übergang des germanischen Phonems /h/ zum Phonem /x/ festzustellen ist." (Simmler 1981:636).

Since Simmler also has /h/ and /χ/ already merged to /χ/ word finally, he too would not need a grapheme merger.

✓ Venneman

Venneman however, would agree with this grapheme merger. In an article on the age of the second soundshift, he refutes an argument based on the Old High German monophthongization before Germanic */h/.

"Dieser Versuch scheitert daran, daß man nur zwei verschiedene, beide durch <h> bezeichnete Frikative anzunehmen braucht, deren verschiedenes Alter sich in verschiedenen Positionen auf der universellen Entwicklungsskala x>χ>h>Null, manifestiert. Ich selbst nehme eine Opposition von χ ("germanisch h") und x ("althochdeutsch h") an, indem auf diese Weise zugleich erklärlich wird, warum es überhaupt zur Monophthongierung in

den bekannten Umgebungen kommt". (Venneman 1987:46).

Syllable Division Revisited

Benware's three principles of syllable division (Benware 1984:87) for Modern German were:

Onsets are maximized

Word boundaries are always syllable boundaries

No interlude may divide so as to yield sequences which do not also occur word initially or word finally.

Following them, Modern German <erheblich> and <Feigling> should divide as:

remove this phrase entirely!

/ɛr+heʌb+liχ/	/fajg+liŋ/
[ɛrʂheʌʂbliχ]	[fajʂgliŋ]
<erheblich>	<Feigling>

After all, [eʌ] and [aj] come word finally in:

/zeʌ/	/zaj/
[zeʌ]	[zaj]
<See>	<sei>

And [bl] and [gl] both appear word initially in:

/blik/	/glajt/
[blik]	[glajt]
<Blick>	<gleit>

Dividing before the obstruent would then maximize onsets, without creating any syllable that began or ended with sequences that did not also occur word initially or finally. Incidentally, Syllable Final Fortition would not affect the obstruents. Since onsets are maximized, the obstruents come at the beginning of the second syllable:

	/ɛr+heʌb+liχ/	/fajg+liŋ/
Syl Division	[ɛrʂheʌʂbliχ]	[fajʂgliŋ]
Syl Final Fort	No Effect	No Effect
	<erheblich>	<Feigling>

According to Benware however, syllables may divide differently:

"when obstruent and sonorant stand on opposite sides of the morpheme boundary" (Benware 1984:86).

By sonorant, Benware means here consonantal sonorant, not vowels. Onsets in these sequences need not be maximized. Such an alternate division would then allow Syllable Final Fortition to take effect:

	/ər+heʌb+liχ/	/fajg+liŋ/
Syl Division	[ər\$heʌb\$liχ]	[fajg\$liŋ]
Syl Final Fort	[ər\$heʌp\$liχ]	[fajk\$liŋ]
	<erheblich>	<Feigling>

If possible, one would like to see where Notker stands on this. Evidence or lack of evidence of Syllable Final Fortition in these clusters could lead to a further refinement of syllable division. Unlike in Modern German however, Syllable Final Fortition for Notker was posited as only occurring after nasals. Examples then would have to be restricted to the fourpart cluster /NL+R/; nasal plus lenis obstruent plus morpheme boundary plus consonantal sonorant.

In addition, the 'lenis obstruent plus consonantal sonorant' cluster would have to be an acceptable word beginning. Since a nasal is an acceptable word end, the syllable boundary could then come after the nasal, and so not correspond with the morpheme boundary.

Ideally, one would examine all six sets of obstruents--labial, dental and velar stops and fricatives. Unfortunately, fortition should not be marked in the dental and velar fricatives. It would not be a phoneme merger, since /ʒ≠s/ and /h≠χ/ contrast in more than just fortition. And in the labial fricatives, a grapheme merger has [v] and [f] marked as <f> word finally. For the stops, another grapheme merger has [g] and [k] both marked as <g> word finally. Syllable Final Fortition then was only marked in two sets of obstruents; the labial and dental stops.

Labial Stop

I can honestly only find one example of /NL+R/, where the lenis stop is a labial, and the /LR/ is an acceptable word onset. Nevertheless, a pattern might be started in Notker's morpheme for 'dumb' /tumb/, where the lenis obstruent can be compared before vocalic and consonantal sonorants:

/tumb+ər/	<tumber>	'dumb, nom masc sg'	II,488,2
/tumb+liχ/	<tumplich>	'dumblike, uninfl'	II,265,3

Before Vocalic Sonorant

[mb] is not an acceptable word beginning, but [b] is:

/buwχ/
 [buwχ]
 <bûh>
 'belly, nom sg'
 II,166,5

So /tumb+ər/ gets divided before the obstruent, and Syllable Final Fortition cannot make the [b] fortis after a nasal:

	/tumb+ər/
Syllable Division	[tum\$bər]
Syllable Final Fortition	No Effect
	<tumber>
	'dumb, nom masc sg'
	II,488,2

Before Consonantal Sonorant

Without evidence to the contrary, one would assume the same division for the /mb+l/ sequence in /tumb+liχ/. After all, [mbl] is not an acceptable word onset, but [bl] is:

/blikχ/
 [blik]
 <blig>
 'glance, acc sg'
 I,743,23

So /tumb+liχ/ would get divided before the obstruent, and Syllable Final Fortition would not make the [b] fortis after a nasal:

	/tumb+liχ/
Syllable Division	*[tum\$bliχ]
Syllable Final Fortition	*No Effect
	*<tumblich>
	'dumblelike, uninfl'
	II,265,3

Unfortunately, the lenis /b/ phoneme in <tumplich> gets marked with the "fortis graph" <p>.

Dental Stop

For the dentals, a similar pattern might be seen in the verb prefix /ən(d,t)/, where one can compare a lenited stop before obstruents, laryngeals, vowels and consonantal sonorants:

/ən(d,t)+žag+ət/	<intsàget>	'say'	II,103,21
/ən(d,t)+hab+ən/	<inthàben>	'have'	I,64,4
/ən(d,t)+eAr+ət/	<indêret>	'honor'	I,36,17
/ən(d,t)+riχt+ət/	<intrih̄tet>	'right'	II,404,20

Dental Lenition should lenite the dental after /n/ to [d] in all these words.

Before Obstruent

[ntž] is not an acceptable word beginning. [tž] might be, but for sure /ž/ is:

/žag+ət/
 [žagšət]
 <sàget>
 'say, 3rd sg pres'
 I,41,16

So, /ən(d,t)+žag+ət/ should divide after the dental, and Syllable Final Fortition make the [d] fortis after a nasal:

	/ən(d,t)+žag+ət/
Syllable Division	[ən(d,t)šžagšət]
Dental Lenition	[əndšžagšət]
Syllable Final Fortition	[əntššagšət]
	<intsàget>
	'say, 3rd sg pres'
	II,103,21

Before Laryngeal

[nth] and [th] are not acceptable word beginnings, but /h/ is:

/halb/
 [halb]
 <hàlb>
 'half, uninfl'
 I,857,13

So, /ən(d,t)+hab+ən/ should divide after the dental, and Syllable Final Fortition make the [d] fortis after lenition.

	/ən(d,t)+hab+ən/
Syllable Division	[ən(d,t)šhabšən]
Dental Lenition	[əndšhabšən]
Syllable Final Fortition	[əntšhabšən]

<inthàben>
'have, inf'
I, 64, 4

Before Vocalic Sonorant

[nd] is not an acceptable word beginning, but [d] is:

/dɑʌr/
[dɑʌr]
<dâr>
'there'
I, 108, 22

So /ən(d,t)eʌrət/ gets divided before the dental, and Syllable Final Fortition cannot make the [d] fortis after a nasal:

	/ən(d,t)+eʌr+ət/
Syllabification	[ənʒ(d,t)eʌr,ət]
Dental Lenition	[ənʒdeʌr,ət]
Syllable Final Fortition	No Effect
	<indêret>
	'honor, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 36, 17

Before Consonantal Sonorant

[ndr] is not an acceptable word beginning, but [dr] is:

/driʝ/
[driʝ]
<drî>
'three'
I, 233, 27

So, /ən(d,t)+riχt+ət/ should divide before the dental, and Syllable Final Fortition should not make the [d] fortis after a nasal:

	/ən(d,t)+riχt+ət/
Syllable Division	*[ənʒ(d,t)riχstət]
Dental Lenition	[ənʒdriχstət]
Syllable Final Fortition	*No Effect
	*<indrîhtet>
	'right, 3rd sg pres'
	II, 404, 20

Unfortunately, the lenis dental obstruent in <intrih̄tet> gets written "fortis" before the consonantal sonorant, just as the labial did in <tùmplich>.

If this can be accounted for phonologically, then according to the functions it should. Perhaps the only way to do this is to use Benware's alternate syllabification and divide on the morpheme boundary between an obstruent and consonantal sonorant. Do this even if it means not maximizing onsets with an acceptable cluster found at word beginnings. /tumb+liχ/ and /ən(d,t)+riχt+ət/ could then get generated as:

	/tumb+liχ/	/ən(d,t)+riχt+ət/
Syllable Division	[tumb\$liχ]	[ən(d,t)\$riχ\$stət]
Dental Lenition	No Effect	[ənd\$riχ\$stət]
Syllable Final Fortition	[tump\$liχ]	[ənt\$riχ\$stət]
	<tùmplich>	<intrih̄tet>

There are quite a few examples of /NL+R/ for the dentals. So, for example, several compounds have /han(d,t)/ or /lan(d,t)/ in the first element, and a second element that begins with a consonantal sonorant:

<hàntuuerch> 'handwork, nom sg' II,569,12
 <làntrehten> 'landright, dat pl' II,400,15

Expressed formally, the preceding discussion would be:

Input

Syllable Final Fortition.
 Benware's three rules for syllable division.
 The forms cited above.

Functions

Syllable Division.

Output

Divide syllables on the morpheme boundary between an obstruent and consonantal sonorant, even if it means not maximizing onsets.

Commentary

Jellinek

Jellinek uses a similar tactic to comment on syllable division for Notker. Although the net effect is just to maximize onsets, his Dental Lenition rule is sensitive to syllable boundaries:

"im innern des satztactes wird silbenanlautendes *t* zu *d*, wenn die vorhergehende silbe auf nasal ausgeht. (Jellinek 1897:86).

In some examples for the rule however, the <d> comes morpheme finally. A morpheme boundary for Notker is not necessarily a syllable one:

"Auf verschiebung der silbengrenze beruht es, wenn das ursprünglich auslautende *t* des prafixes *int-* vor vocal zu *d* wird. Im Boethius findet sich *indêret* 36,17/18, *indânotêr* 37,19, *indèdelet* 160,14, in den Kategorieen *indânot* 450,90. (Jellinek 1897:86).

Braune Grammar

The grammar echoes Jellinek's examples:

"mit Verschiebung der Silbengrenze *indêret*, *indânotêr*, *indèdelet* aus *int-êret* usw." (Braune 1987:163 Anm 5).

System Summary

Phonemes

Notker contrasted six stops, five fricatives and one laryngeal. They can be minimally described as:

	oral	son	cont	fort	lab	dent	unk	vel
b	yes	no	no	no	yes	---	---	---
p	yes	no	no	yes	yes	---	---	---
d	yes	no	no	no	---	yes	---	---
t	yes	no	no	yes	---	yes	---	---
g	yes	no	no	no	---	---	---	yes
k	yes	no	no	yes	---	---	---	yes
v	yes	no	yes	no	yes	---	---	---
f	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	---	---	---
ʒ	yes	no	yes	no	---	yes	yes	---
s	yes	no	yes	yes	---	yes	no	---
χ	yes	no	yes	---	---	---	---	yes
h	no	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Syllable Division

Onsets are maximized.

Word boundaries are always syllable boundaries.

No interlude may divide so as to yield sequences which do not also occur word initially or word finally.

Divide syllables on the morpheme boundary between an obstruent and consonantal sonorant, even if it means not maximizing onsets.

Phoneme Mergers

Syllable Initial Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable initially, when not inhibited by a preceding sonorant.

Syllable Internal Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable internally, when next to another obstruent.

Syllable Final Fortition:

Obstruents become fortis syllable finally, when preceded by nasal sonority or less.

Dental Lenition:

Dental obstruents lenite after the dental nasal, even across a syllable boundary.

Nasal Assimilation:

Nasals assimilate in place to a following obstruent, even across a syllable boundary.

Epenthesis:

An epenthetic fortis stop is placed between a nasal and a fortis fricative, even if they are separated by a syllable boundary.

Velar Deletion:

A velar obstruent deletes, if in between another velar obstruent and a syllable boundary.

Grapheme Mergers

Word Final <g>:

[g] and [k] are both written <g> word finally.

Word Final <f>:

[v] and [f] are both written <f> word finally.

Word Final <h>:

[h] and [χ] are both written <h> word finally.

Rule Orderings

Of course Syllable Division is ordered before any phoneme mergers, and all phoneme mergers are ordered before grapheme mergers. In addition however, some phoneme mergers need to be ordered before each other.

Nasal Assimilation before Epenthesis

Otherwise /χ/ could not generate <g> in <stàng>:

	/ (ž, s) (d, t) a (m, n) χ /
Epenthesis	* [(š, s) ta (m, n) (p, t) χ]
Nasal Assimilation	* [(š, s) ta (mp, nt) χ]
Velar Deletion	*No Effect
	* <stànch>
	'smell, nom sg'
	I, 291, 32

Nasal Assimilation before Dental Lenition

Otherwise /mʃt/ could not generate <md> in <rûmda>:

	/ruwm+ta/
Dental Lenition	*No Effect
Nasal Assimilation	[ruwnʃta]
	*<rûmta>
	'praise, 3rd sg past'
	I, 810, 22

Epenthesis before Velar Deletion

Otherwise /χ/ could not generate <g> in <stàng>:

	/ (ž, s) (d, t) a (m, n) χ /
Nasal Assimilation	[(š, s) taŋχ]
Velar Deletion	*No Effect
Epenthesis	* [(š, s) taŋkχ]
	* <stànch>
	'smell, nom sg'
	I, 291, 32

Epenthesis before Syllable Final Fortition

Otherwise / (m, n) v \$ ≠ (m, n) f / will not generate the <nf≠mf> contrast word finally:

	/vi (m, n) v/	/g+la (m, n) (pf, f) /
Nasal Assimilation	[vimv]	[glamf]
Syl Final Fort	[fimf]	[glampf]
Epenthesis	*[fimpf]	[glampf]
	*<fimf>	<gelàm f>
	'five, uninfl'	'suit, 3rd sg past'
	I, 66, 26	I, 556, 5

Dental Lenition before Syllable Final Fortition

Otherwise / (d, t) / cannot generate <t> in <fànt>:

	/va (m, n) (d, t) /
Nasal Assimilation	[van(d, t)]
Syl Final Fort	*[vant]
Dental Lenition	*[vand]
	*<fànd>
	'find, 3rd sg past'
	I, 222, 6

EFFECTS ON THE HISTORY OF GERMAN

Much of the output of the walkthrough is by nature only significant for the synchronic phonology of Notker. There are however at least three areas in the history of German that the analysis might affect: rule orderings, Syllable Final Fortition, and the Konsonantenschwächung.

Rule Orderings

A considerable amount of ink has been spent on rule re-ordering and insertion. Rules may have been reordered to minimize bleeding orders in the Kesswill dialect of Switzerland (Bynon 1977:127). They may have been re-ordered in Canadian English to maximize feeding (Bynon 1977:130). A rule insertion may explain Lachmann's Law in Latin (Bynon 1977:118). It is hotly disputed whether any of these tactics can be used on living languages, much less in reconstructing a dead one. Indeed Bynon cuts through much of the discussion by declaring:

"Let it however be noted from the outset that the present position is that new rules may be added at one point only, namely at the end of the phonological rules--strictly speaking at the end of the rules which change absolute feature values and before the 'low-level' rules which assign quantified values" (Bynon 1977:118).

So, for example, some Old High German dialects look like ^{as though} they have undergone the second sound shift along with some syllable final or initial fortition. It is unknown whether both these processes were ever active in any one dialect at the same time. To allow that possibility however, the second sound shift would have to be ordered before the fortition: ✓

	/mag/	/brak/
2nd Sound Shift	No Effect	[braχ]
Syl Final Fortition	[mak]	[braχ]
	'can'	'broke'

Otherwise lenis stops would get shifted to fortis spirants and affricates:

	/mag/	/brak/
Syl Final Fortition	[mak]	[braχ]
2nd Sound Shift	*[maχ]	[braχ]
	'can'	'broke'

As the second sound shift would have to come first in the synchronic grammar, so would most scholars place it ahead of syllable final fortition in the diachronic grammar. As Bynon stresses a second time:

"rule addition at the end of the phonological component remains the only acceptable kind of rule addition" (Bynon 1977:120).

Does this mean that the rule orderings proposed for a text can be used to propose the relative diachronic chronology of them? So, for example, if Dental Lenition should come before Syllable Final Fortition in Notker, does that mean that that Dental Lenition took place in Alemannic before Syllable Final Fortition? If so, then the synchronic rule orderings for a text could be a powerful tool for historical phonology. ~~Of course however,~~ diffusion and analogy could have obscured the chronology of rule additions. In addition, the whole concept of rule orderings is hotly debated. So Lass writes:

"The topic of rule ordering is immensely complex, and perhaps ultimately unrewarding; the need for extrinsic ordering is strictly a function of abstract analysis, which has been, if not discredited, certainly rendered suspect." (Lass 1984:234).

In any case ~~however~~, a scholar might compare his synchronic rule orderings with the order scholars believe these processes took place in history. One might also compare the scope. A rule ordered later would hopefully have happened more recently, and to a smaller group of languages.

Nasal Assimilation

Nasal Assimilation, if already productive in Proto-Germanic, can account for an alternation in ~~in~~ the word for 'think' in English and Notker:

<dènchet> [denʃχət] 'thinks' I, 766, 2
<dàhta> [dahʃta] 'thought' II, 154, 14

In the Proto-Germanic preterite of 'think', nasals assimilated to a velar fricative, only to be later deleted before [χʃ] or [hʃ]:

*[da(m,n)χʃta] -> *[danχʃta] -> *[dahʃta] 'thought'

Nasal Assimilation in Notker could then reflect an ancient

phoneme merger, inherited from Proto-Germanic. Coincidentally, in Notker, Nasal Assimilation gets ordered before four phoneme mergers: Epenthesis, Dental Lenition, and through these two, Velar Deletion and Syllable Final Fortition.

Epenthesis

Epenthesis was ordered after Nasal Assimilation, but before two phoneme mergers: Velar Deletion and Syllable Final Fortition. It occurs in Modern English and German, and seems to be marked in other Old High German dialects:

<limphen> 'to suit' Otfrid

Dental Lenition

Dental Lenition is ordered after one phoneme merger (Nasal Assimilation), and before only one (Syllable Final Fortition). As far as I can tell, Dental Lenition is limited to southern dialects in Old High German:

<finden> 'to find' Notker
<fintan> 'to find' Tatian

Velar Deletion

Velar Deletion was placed after two phoneme mergers (Nasal Assimilation and Epenthesis) and before none. Its scope seems limited to Alemannic. One would ~~also~~ have to date it after the second sound shift, ~~however~~, since its input is a syllable initial and final shifted /k/.

Syllable Final Fortition

Syllable Final Fortition was placed after three phoneme mergers (Nasal Assimilation, Epenthesis, Dental Lenition), and before none. Although its scope includes now much of Modern German ~~and~~ ~~Slavic~~, this must be through diffusion, not an inherited phoneme merger from Proto-Germanic. Indeed, Syllable Final Fortition should not predate the second sound shift; otherwise those stops made fortis after nasals would have shifted. In addition, Syllable Final Fortition in Notker could be seen as only the first stage towards a more general process in Middle High German. With this in mind, one might argue that the phoneme merger is so new in Notker that it is not even all here yet.

Syllable Final Fortition

Bynon speaks of:

"the addition of the devoicing (i.e. fortition) rule into the grammar of early Middle High German" (Bynon 1977:155).

How this change took place ~~however~~ is unknown. Without evidence to the contrary, one would ~~just~~ assume that fortition for all obstruents was adopted into Medieval German dialects. That would be the simplest explanation. Bynon after all takes about:

"the addition of the devoicing (i.e. fortition) rule" (Bynon 1977:155).

Penzl sees thereafter:

"ein Wechsel zwischen Fortis im Auslaut und Lenis im Inlaut weit verbreitet" (Penzl 1972:164).

The examples he cites have obstruents becoming fortis across the board--after vocalic and consonantal sonorants:

"lop Gen. lobes; golt Gen. goldes, tac Gen. tages" (Penzl 1972:164).

The fortition for Notker speaks for a more gradated process, a gradation that Penzl perhaps hints at in his analysis of Otfrid:

"Direkte Variation deutet im Auslaut bei Lippenlauten (*irstarb, irstarp*) und Gaumenlauten (*sang, sank >Gesang<*) auf eine Tendenz zur Aufhebung der Opposition, besonders nach Sonorlaut, wohl zu Gunsten der Fortis /p/ /k/, wenn wir den Wechsel *-/b/-:-/p/ (lambir, lamp)* und die Verteilung bei den Reibelauten in Betracht ziehen" (Penzl 1972:86).

If one accepts the phoneme merger, then Syllable Final Fortition can be added to German dialects in stages, and relative degrees of sonority condition those stages.

Konsonantenschwächung

Both the grapheme mergers for velar and labial fricatives could simplify formulations of the Old High German Konsonantenschwächung. The Braune Grammar writes:

"seit Beginn der Textüberlieferung ist eine Lenisierung der stimmlosen Spiranten germ. f, þ, s, χ feststellbar" (Braune 1987:102a).

If I understand this correctly, ~~then these~~ Germanic fortis fricatives became lenis, the lenis version of /χ/ eventually being a laryngeal /h/, the lenis version of /þ/ eventually being a stop /d/. Except in some combinations with other consonants, the shift happens syllable (and so also word) finally:

*/f/ -> /v/
 */þ/ -> /d/
 */š/ -> /ž/
 */χ/ -> /h/

Also, sometime before the literary period, Germanic fortis stops became fortis fricatives through the Second Sound Shift. There is of course a big exception syllable initially when not preceded by a sonorant. There the stops become affricates or stops or fricatives depending on the dialect or stop. Except for some combinations with other consonants, the shift happens syllable (and so also word) finally:

*/p/ -> /f/
 */d/ -> /t/
 */t/ -> /s/
 */k/ -> /χ/

So in Notker, word (and so syllable) finally, the phonemes were written as:

/v\$#/ -> [v\$#] -> <f#>
 /f\$#/ -> [f\$#] -> <f#>
 /d\$#/ -> [d\$#] -> <d#>
 /t\$#/ -> [t\$#] -> <t#>
 /ž\$#/ -> [ž\$#] -> <s#>
 /s\$#/ -> [s\$#] -> <z#>
 /h\$#/ -> [h\$#] -> <h#>

/χ\$#/ -> [χ\$#] -> <h#>

✓ Two grapheme mergers, however, are needed to allow the [v\$#f\$] and [h\$#χ\$] contrasts to be marked by <f#> and <h#> respectively.

Later, Middle High German Syllable Final (and so word final) Fortition eliminates the need for the grapheme merger of [f\$#] and [v\$#] to <f>. Loss of syllable final /h/ eliminates the need for the grapheme merger of [χ\$#] and [h\$#] to <h>:

/v\$#/ -> [f\$#]
/f\$#/ -> [f\$#] -> <f#>

/d\$#/ -> [t\$#]
/t\$#/ -> [t\$#] -> <t#>

/ž\$#/ -> [š\$#] -> <s#>
/s\$#/ -> [s\$#] -> <z#>

/h\$#/ -> Ø
/χ\$#/ -> [χ\$#] -> <h#>

✓ But if you do not have those grapheme mergers in Old High German, then the spelling mergers get analyzed phonologically. This entails several problems:]?

1. Syllable finally, Germanic */f/ and */χ/ remain fortis, and merge there with the new fricatives from Germanic */p/ and */k/. The Konsonantenschwächung, rather than a lenition of all fricatives, is a lenition of all except for syllable final labial and velar fricatives. That is, a challenging rule to write. Something like this must be behind Penzl and Simmler when they posit different phonemes (not allophones of the same phoneme) in different declensions of <hòf> <hòues>, <rûoh>, <rûhen>. } NB!

2. Word finally, nasals are written <n> before the /f/ from Germanic */f/, and <m> before the /f/ from Germanic */p/:

*/vi(m,n)f/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
*[fimpf]	[glampf]
<fînf>	<gelàmff>
'five'	'suit, 3rd sg past'
I, 66, 26	I, 556, 5

The merger mimics an alternation in nasals word internally:

/vi(m,n)ve/	/g+li(m,n)(pf,f)+liχ+eΛro/
-------------	----------------------------

[fim\$ve]
 <finue>
 'five, fem pl'
 I, 197, 29

[glim\$pfliχ_se^\$ro]
 <gelimflichêro>
 'suited, fem dat sg'
 I, 781, 25

This is hard to explain if the two phonemes merged into /f/ syllable finally before the literary period.

3. Positioning /f/ in <hòf> and /v/ in <hòue> entails positioning two different phonemes in different declensions of the same noun. That is odd, especially since the fortis phoneme is placed at an easily identifiable phonological (syllable final) or graphological (word final) environment. The analysis is identical to positioning two different phonemes in different declensions of German word for 'wheel': <Rad> */ra^t/, <Rades> /ra^d+əs/.

4. Nearly all syllable final [f≠v] contrasts from Old High German are lost to us through Middle High German Syllable Final Fortition. Nevertheless, syllable final Germanic */p/ and */f/ still contrast in German, if only after nasals. The syllable codas of Notker's <fînf> and <gelàmff> contrast, just as they do in Modern German <fünf> and <glimpflich>. It is odd to have this contrast in ~~in~~ Proto-Germanic, then merge it in Old High German, only to have it again in Modern German. Of course one could get around this by having Germanic */p/ shift to /pf/ after nasals.

5. Word finally, a long high vowel is written differently before the /χ/ from Germanic */χ/, and the one from Germanic */k/:

*/ru(w,^)^χ/
 *[ru^χ]
 <rûoh>
 'raw, uninfl'
 I, 167, 28

/buwχ/
 [buwχ]
 <bûh>
 'belly, nom sg'
 II, 166, 15

The merger corresponds to another graph alternation word internally:

/ru(w,^)^hən/
 [ruh_sən]
 <rûhon>
 'raw, gen pl masc wk'
 I, 167, 27

/buwχ+e/
 [buw\$χe]
 <bûche>
 'belly, dat sg'
 II, 68, 24

This is hard to explain, if the two phonemes merged into /χ/ syllable finally before the literary period.

6. The off glide of the long high vowel seems lowered before the /χ/ from Germanic */χ/:

*/ru(w,ʌ)χ/

*[ruʌχ]

<rûoh>

'raw, uninfl'

I,167,28

! favorite word

That is an odd process for a (possibly [+hi]) velar fricative, but a very natural one for a laryngeal.

Yes!
cal

7. Positing /χ/ in <rûoh> and /h/ in <rûhon> entails positing two different phonemes in different declensions of the same noun. That is odd, especially since the fortis phoneme is placed at an easily identifiable phonological (syllable final) or graphological (word final) environment. The analysis is identical to positing two different phonemes in different declensions of German word for 'wheel': <Rad> */raʌt/, <Rades> /raʌd+əs/.

8. Syllable final [h] no longer occurs in Modern German. Nevertheless, a [h≠χ] contrast does survive into the modern language, although in an amended [Ø≠χ] form. The syllable codas of Notker's <rûoh> and <bûh> contrast just as they do in Modern German <roh> and <Bauch>. It is odd to have this contrast in Proto-Germanic, then merge it in Old High German, only to have it again in Modern German.

EPILOGUE

There is a lot in this paper that if not new, is at least the minority view. That is perhaps unfortunate, new things are often incorrect. They are also often not new either, just written someplace else. In any case however, perhaps these ideas should get touched on. They could be divided into: output, functions, and format.

Output

The /v≠f/ and /h≠χ/ contrasts are posited syllable finally, and their marking as <f> and <h> taken as grapheme mergers.

These two grapheme mergers should simplify the Konsonantenschwächung, processes conditioned by word final /h/, and the alternation between <m> and <n> before word final <f>.

The Anlautgesetz is examined for all six sets of obstruents, and the two where it is not marked (dental and velar fricatives) is explained. A fortition was not enough to merge phonemes for (ž≠s) and (h≠χ).

<ch> in <chöpf> is, without reference to Modern Swiss, established as a fricative [χ]. A process that reduced velar affricates syllable finally (<blicches> <blig>) can be broadened to reduce them at both syllable boundaries.

The rule orderings proposed for Notker's synchronic grammar mirror the order that these processes were added in history.

Syllable Final Fortition is posited for Notker. Perhaps more importantly though, it is conditioned by gradations in sonority. This may give us a window into how the process was introduced into German dialects.

This fortition can be used to refine our understanding of syllable division in Notker.

There is one thing more. Unfortunately I have not had time to provide the data for it here. The Braune grammar writes that the Anlautgesetz is:

"so genau beobachtet, daß die vereinzeltten Verstöße wohl nur der Überlieferung zur Last fallen" (Braune 1987:103).

Who was an undergraduate?

This may not be entirely accurate. As an undergraduate, Professor Firchow let me borrow a computer printout of her de

Nuptiis edition. I looked at how often syllable initial /b,d,g/ were written <p,t,k(c,q)> after low point and high point, when a sonorant preceded the point. Vowels are more likely to inhibit fortition than consonantal sonorants. The pattern holds out in the six areas examined (ex: /b/ after low point, /d/ after high point, etc.). So the Anlautgesetz, at least in de Nuptiis, is sensitive to gradations in sonority. This is all the more remarkable, since most of the examples for consonantal sonorants are of nasals before /d/. Dentals lenite after [n]. So if the Anlautgesetz was not sensitive to sonority grades, one might expect to see fortition less frequently, rather than more, after consonantal sonorants. This type of syllable initial fortition also perhaps reinforces the type of fortition I propose syllable finally--one sensitive to gradations in sonority.

Functions

In his analysis of Old High German /f/, Penzl writes:

"Aus der Anwendung aller dieser Bestimmungsmethoden sollte man eine Reihe von gesicherten Ergebnissen erwarten, doch ist die Ausbeute verhältnismäßig gering. Wichtiger und einleuchtender ist aber die Bewertung der Wirksamkeit der Methoden selbst." (Penzl 1964:291).

Like Penzl then, I am perhaps more partial to the methods, than to what they output.

Posit as Little as Possible can delimit our field. If a scholar can show the Anlautgesetz is a fortition, then his work is done. He need not go further, and argue that the Anlautgesetz shows whether Notker had a glottal stop (Clausing 1979), or whether the scribe was bilingual in Latin (Penzl 1955).

I have used *Only Phoneme Mergers* as a sort of "scribal universal". This ~~of course~~ may not be true, but it seems to account well for the marking of fortitions in Notker and Middle High German. Together with *Posit as Little as Possible*, the function might cut through half the theories extracted from texts.

Our discipline can look to modern phonology for ideas on what a natural phoneme merger would be. What makes a grapheme merger natural however, will have to be addressed by us. ~~Of course~~ a scribe would have trouble marking phonemes that were not in the source script. So Clausing writes:

"the primary reason for Notker's failure to indicate affricates or rounded front vowels was the lack of suitable orthographic symbols at his disposal" (Clausing 1979:367).

In *Only Posit Natural Grapheme Mergers* I argue that we should go beyond this, and also look at the source language's spelling patterns. Medieval Latin did have /v/ and a sign for it in <u>. Nevertheless, <u> does not mark a fricative word finally in Latin, so it would be natural if Old High German scribes did not use it as one there either.

How minimal pairs are used to posit processes should be more comprehensive. So, for example, there are 12 non-sonorants in Notker. Except for the laryngeal /h/, they all come after nasals, both syllable initially and finally. According to *Contrast Phonemes in Minimal Pairs* then, one should cite all 22 of these sequences. A reader could see the one sequence where nasals still contrast, before word (and so syllable) final <f>. I have great respect for Penzl, this paper would not have been possible without him, but this is not enough data for a discussion of nasal assimilation:

"Bei den Nasalphonemen /n/ /m/ weisen die Folgenentwicklung auf ein velares Allophon vor Gaumenlaut z.B. *dìng*(64), *làngo*(144), Allophone in der Sprache der Gegenwart auf ein labiodentales Allophon des /m/ vor f (*chùmftig*, *sèmfte*)" (Penzl 1972:102).

Only Restrict Input by Place if Conditioned by Place certainly needs to be refined. But we should not allow, for example, a syllable final fortition that only affects selected obstruents:

"Im Auslaut steht zum Unterschied von den Reibelauten das Lenisphonem (*kàlb*, *tàg*, *flèisg*), bei dem Fortisallophone anzunehmen sind" (Penzl 1972:104).

One can also not discuss phonological processes without establishing the base phonological boundary--the syllable. So, for example, in <*zìhen*> and <*lîehti*> the <h> is word medial. The processes seem contradictory, if one allows the root vowels in both to come from underlying /ij/ or /i^/. *Syllable Division* however establishes the laryngeal in the first word as syllable initial, and the laryngeal in the second as syllable final. Without that information, a scholar is left to write something like this:

"eine phonetische Erklärung der Kürzung durch Einwirkung des Lenisreibelautes h ist ebenso schwierig wie die der scheinbaren Monophthongierung in *zìhen* (aus *ziehen*?), die wie eine genaue Umkehrung des Wandels i zu ie in *lîehti*, *nîeht*, *îeht* erscheint." (Penzl 1968a:139).

Similarly, several graphological processes are conditioned by the base graphological boundary--the word. *Differentiate Phonological from Graphological Boundary* establishes that. Terms like "Im Inlaut" or "in medial position" only blur the distinction between the two types of processes.

"Maximizing Rules" is taught in perhaps any introductory phonology course. If a student sees that /b/ is pronounced [p] syllable finally, he checks if the other lenis obstruents are also fortis there. If so, then he also vacuously includes the fortis obstruents in the input of his fortition rule. He checks if obstruents become fortis syllable initially, and so at all syllable boundaries. What stops a rule from maximizing though in a living language is easy--just phonetic transcriptions that would contradict a maximized rule. Since texts ~~however~~ are not phonetic transcriptions, *Broaden Phoneme Mergers* allows rules to maximize until they would force an unnatural grapheme merger. This may not be correct, but the issue should be discussed.

Format

Perhaps more important to me than even the paper's methods, is its format. A programmer takes input, and walks it through functions to get output. A mathematician takes assumptions, and runs them through theorems to confirm postulates. The functions and theorems though are **external** from the data. So, for example, a mathematician cannot develop one version of the theorem of transitivity on one problem, then develop another for a second problem. At least he would never be published. We may never be able to write "phonological proofs" in the mathematical sense, but I think we should try. It forces an accountability on our discipline. Whatever methods a scholar used on one text, could then be run against any other text.

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MINIMAL PAIRS

All sequences are morpheme internal. I have treated affricates as sequences of fortis phonemes. This is perhaps unfortunate, since it does not capture how Syllable Internal Fortition allows affricates to get generated by underlying lenis phonemes too. /ʒ/ and /s/ however differ in more than just fortition and so would generate different affricates. Also, I feel the underlying forms are hard enough to read now anyway. The situation would get only worse if, for example, every [pf] came from underlying /*(b,p)* *(v,f)*/.

Labial Stops

	/b/	/p/
Syllable	/wɨj b +ən/	/(<i>ʒ</i> ,s)kaʌpaʌre/
Initial	[wɨj ʂ bən]	[(<i>ʂ</i> ,s)kaʌʂpaʌʂre]
After	<uu ɨ bən>	<skâpâre>
Vowel	'woman, dat pl' I, 776, 32	'sheepskin, dat sg' II, 283, 25
Syllable	/wɨj b /	No Example
Final	[wɨj b]	
After	<uu ɨ b>	
Vowel	'woman, nom sg' I, 13, 4	
Syllable	/wer b +ən/	/purperən/
Initial	[wer ʂ bən]	[purʂpər,ən]
After	<uuèr b ən>	<pùrpurun>
Liquid	'recruit, inf' I, 810, 11	'purple, gen sg' I, 167, 24
Syllable	/war b /	No Example
Final	[war b]	
After	<uuàr b >	
Liquid	'recruit, 1st sg past' II, 279, 18	
Syllable	/le(m,n) b +ər/	/gu(m,n)pit+ən/
Initial	[lem ʂ bər]	[gumʂpiʂtən]
After	<lèm ɨ ber>	<gùmpiten>
Nasal	'lamb, nom pl' II, 486, 6	'pond, acc sg' II, 211, 3

Syllable	/la(m,n)b/	No Example
Final	[lamp]	
After	<lamp>	
Nasal	'lamb, acc sg'	
	II, 239, 9	

Syllable	No Example	No Example
Initial		
After		
Obstruent		

Syllable	No Example	No Example
Final		
After		
Obstruent		

Syllable	/(ž,s)(b,p)eʌr+e/
Internal	[(š,s)peʌšre]
After	<spêre>
Obstruent	'spear, dat sg'
	II, 70, 18

Dental Stops

	/d/	/t/
Syllable	/toʌd+əž/	/taʌt+ən/
Initial	[toʌʂdəž]	[taʌʂtən]
After	<tôdes>	<tâten>
Vowel	'death, gen sg'	'do, 3rd pl past'
	I, 118, 15	I, 11, 27
Syllable	/toʌd/	/tuʌt/
Final	[toʌd]	[tuʌt]
After	<tôd>	<tûot>
Vowel	'death, nom sg'	'do, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 8, 8	I, 9, 26
Syllable	/werdən/	/wort+o/
Initial	[werʂdən]	[worʂto]
After	<uuèrden>	<uuòrto>
Liquid	'become, inf'	'word, gen pl'
	I, 18, 13	I, 12, 6
Syllable	/ward/	/wort/
Final	[ward]	[wort]
After	<uuàrd>	<uuòrt>
Liquid	'become, 3rd sg past'	'word, nom sg'
	I, 5, 17	I, 502, 18
Syllable		/vi(m,n)(d,t)+ət/
Initial		[finʂdət]
After		<fîndet>
Nasal		'find, 3rd sg pres'
		I, 65, 18
Syllable		/va(m,n)(d,t)/
Final		[fant]
After		<fânt>
Nasal		'find, 3rd sg past'
		I, 222, 6
Syllable		/ve(ž,s)(d,t)+e/
Initial		[fe(š,s)ʂte]
After		<fèste>
Obstruent		'firm, uninfl'
		I, 165, 3

Syllable	/i(ž,s)(d,t)/
Final	[i(š,s)t]
After	<ist>
Obstruent	'be, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 6, 21

Syllable	/(ž,s)(d,t)ern+ən/
Internal	[(š,s)teršnən]
After	<stèrnen>
Obstruent	'star, nom pl'
	I, 17, 9

Velar Stop

	/g/	/k/
Syllable	/wijg+e/	/gowkə1+e/
Initial	[wij\$ge]	[cow\$ke1,e]
After	<uuige>	<còukele>
Vowel	'battle, dat sg'	'trickery, dat sg'
	I, 23, 1	II, 246, 224
Syllable	/wijg/	/rok/
Final	[wijg]	[rok]
After	<uuig>	<rògh>
Vowel	'battle, nom sg'	'robe, nom sg.'
	II, 84, 2	I, 523, 24
Syllable	/burg+o/	/furk+ən/
Initial	[bur\$go]	[fur\$ken]
After	<bùrgo>	<fùrkun>
Liquid	'castle, gen pl'	'trident, acc sg'
	I, 113, 18	I, 742, 3
Syllable	/burg/	No Example
Final	[burg]	
After	<bùrg>	
Liquid	'castle, nom sg'	
	I, 703, 23	
Syllable	/ži(m,n)g+ən/	/tsi(m,n)k+ən/
Initial	[žiŋ\$gən]	[tsiŋ\$ken]
After	<sìngen>	<cìnken>
Nasal	'sing, inf'	'prong, dat sg'
	I, 96, 16	I, 775, 5
Syllable	/ža(m,n)g/	No Example
Final	[žaŋk]	
After	<sàng>	
Nasal	'sing, 3rd sg past'	
	I, 176, 14	
Syllable	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)+ən/	
Initial	[fi(š,s)\$ken]	
After	<fiŋken>	
Obstruent	'fish, dat pl'	
	I, 751, 23	

Syllable	/vi(ž,s)(g,k)/
Final	[fi(š,s)k]
After	<fišg>
Obstruent	'fish, nom sg'
	I, 167, 28

Syllable	/(ž,s)(g,k)ijn+ət/
Internal	[(š,s)kijšnət]
After	<skînet>
Obstruent	'shine, 3rd sg pres'
	I, 8, 15

Labial Fricative

	/v/	/f/
Syllable	/tiʌvəl/	/tiʌf+o/
Initial	[tiʌ\$vəl]	[tiʌ\$fo]
After	<tʰieuel>	<tʰiefo>
Vowel	'devil, nom sg' II, 469, 23	'deep, adv' I, 208, 23
Syllable	/hov/	/tiʌf/
Final	[hof]	[tiʌ\$f]
After	<hòf>	<tʰief>
Vowel	'court, nom sg' I, 736, 26	'deep, uninfl' II, 389, 1
Syllable	/wolv+a/	/helfən/
Initial	[wol\$va]	[hel\$fən]
After	<uuòlua>	<hèlfen>
Liquid	'wolf, nom pl' II, 238, 1	'help, inf' I, 265, 22
Syllable	/wolv/	/half/
Final	[wolv]	[half]
After	<uuòlf>	<hàlf>
Liquid	'wolf, nom sg' II, 345, 2	'help, 3rd sg past' II, 95, 6
Syllable	/vi(m,n)ve/	/g+li(m,n)(pf,f)+liχ+eʌro/
Initial	[fim\$ve]	[glim\$pfliχ,eʌ\$ro]
After	<fìnue>	<gelimflichêro>
Nasal	'five, fem pl' I, 197, 29	'suited, fem dat sg' I, 781, 25
Syllable	/vi(m,n)v/	/g+la(m,n)(pf,f)/
Final	[fimf]	[glampf]
After	<fìnf>	<gelàmff>
Nasal	'five' I, 66, 26	'suit, 3rd sg past' I, 556, 5
Syllable	No Example	/opfər/
Initial		[op\$fər]
After		<òpfer>
Obstruent		'sacrifice, nom sg' I, 75, 19

Syllable No Example
 Final
 After
 Obstruent

/(kχ,χ)opf/
 [χopf]
 <chòpf>
 'head, nom sg'
 I, 765, 6

Syllable No Example
 Internal
 After
 Obstruent

/pflegə(ž,s)(d,t)/
 [pfleg_sə(ž,s)t]
 <flègest>
 'care, 2nd sg pres subj'
 I, 815, 20

Dental Fricative

	/ž/	/s/
Syllable	/muwže/	/hejsən/
Initial	[muwšže]	[hejšsən]
After	<múse>	<hèizen>
Vowel	'mouse, nom pl' II, 488, 13	'call, inf' I, 37, 10
Syllable	/muwž/	/hiʌs/
Final	[muwž]	[hiʌs]
After	<múš>	<hîez>
Vowel	'mouse, acc sg' II, 438, 13	'call, 3rd sg past' I, 5, 16
Syllable	/alžo/	/((ž, s) (d, t)ur(ts, s)+a/
Initial	[alšžo]	[(š, s) turš(ts, s)a]
After	<àlso>	<stùrza>
Liquid	'thus' I, 8, 15	'support, nom pl' I, 52, 18
Syllable	/nalž/	/((ž, s) (d, t)ur(ts, s)/
Final	[nalž]	[(š, s) tur(ts, s)]
After	<nàls>	<stùrz>
Liquid	'not at all' I, 14, 20	'support, nom sg' I, 62, 27
Syllable	/u(m, n)žər/	/u(m, n) (ts, s)an/
Initial	[unšžər]	[unštsan]
After	<ùnser>	<ùnzan>
Nasal	'our, uninfl' I, 77, 7	'until' I, 12, 24
Syllable	/u(m, n)ž/	/u(m, n) (ts, s)/
Final	[unš]	[unts]
After	<ùns>	<ùnz>
Nasal	'us' II, 634, 1	'until' I, 54, 30
Syllable	No Example	/žitsən/
Initial		[žitšsən]
After		<šìzzen>
Obstruent		'sit, inf' I, 5, 9

Syllable	No Example	/ (ž, s) (g, k) ats /
Final		[(ž, s) kats]
After		<scàz>
Obstruent		'treasure, nom sg'
		I, 76, 2

Syllable	No Example	/ tsijšte /
Internal		[tsijšte]
After		<zîte>
Obstruent		'time, nom pl'
		I, 98, 3

Laryngeal and Velar Fricative

	/h/	/χ/
Syllable	/ru(w,ʌ)h+ən/	/buwχ+e/
Initial	[ruh _ə ən]	[buw\$χe]
After	<rùhon>	<bûche>
Vowel	'raw, gen pl masc wk' I, 167, 27	'belly, dat sg' II, 68, 24
Syllable	/ru(w,ʌ)h/	/buwχ/
Final	[ruʌh]	[buwχ]
After	<rùoh>	<bûh>
Vowel	'raw, uninfl' I, 167, 28	'belly, nom sg' II, 166, 15
Syllable	Only Found	/werχ+əž/
Initial	Across Morpheme	[wer\$χəž]
After	Boundaries	<uuèrches>
Liquid		'work, gen sg' I, 40, 12
Syllable	Not Found	/werχ/
Final		[werχ]
After		<uuèrh>
Liquid		'work, nom sg' I, 487, 15
Syllable	Only Found	/ (ž, s) (d, t) a (m, n) (kχ, χ) +əž /
Initial	Across Morpheme	[(š, s) taŋk\$χəž]
After	Boundaries	<stànches>
Nasal		'smell, gen sg' I, 708, 2
Syllable	Not Found	/ (ž, s) (d, t) a (m, n) (kχ, χ) /
Final		[(š, s) taŋk]
After		<stàng>
Nasal		'smell, nom sg' I, 291, 32
Syllable	Only Found	/blikχ+əž/
Initial	Across Morpheme	[blik\$χəž]
After	Boundaries	<blicches>
Obstruent		'glance, gen sg' I, 751, 28

Syllable Not Found
 Final
 After
 Obstruent

/blik χ /
 [blik]
 <blig>
 'glance, acc sg'
 I, 743, 23

Syllable Not Found
 Internal
 After
 Obstruent

/(k χ , χ)i(m,n)(d,t)/
 [χ int]
 <chint>
 'child, nom sg'
 I, 62, 15